

Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies:

How methods and methodologies
contribute to equitable coastal transition
through empowerment and inclusivity

Edited by:

Madeleine Gustavsson, Sunniva Solnør, Katrina Rønningen
(Ruralis – Institute for Rural and Regional Research)

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Front Cover: Norway. Credit: Ida Jörgensen

Photo shown here: Træna. Credit: Sunniva Solnør

Abstract

In reflecting on methods and methodologies used in the EmpowerUs Horizon Europe (2022-2025) project, this Handbook assesses their potentialities for inclusivity in building more equitable processes and outcomes for coastal communities in their sustainability transitions. To date, there has been little explicit, critical and reflexive exploration of the use of methods and methodologies and how they, in turn, impact inclusive processes and outcomes for community transition. In responding to the need for this conversation, our Handbook brings together a variety of reflections on some of the challenges, strengths, lessons learned, and broader insights for how to use and develop methods and methodologies to reach broader goals around Leaving No One Behind, inclusivity, empowerment and equity.

The Handbook particularly focuses on key considerations for gathering and analysing data from diverse groups in coastal communities. Going beyond describing a particular methodology or method, it reflects on practical experiences gained through research and innovation in coastal community transitions – drawing out wider insights that can be used beyond the EmpowerUs project. Such experiences and knowledge gained by researchers are usually not shared – or perhaps not reflected upon at all – and the opportunity for shared learning is often missed. Through reflexivity, we critically examine our research and innovation practice to open the lid on the process of doing co-creative research to make visible and knowable methodological insights and development. Without hiding or overlooking these challenges – we aim to share the difficult adaptations, trade-offs and sometimes failures that allow for collective methodological knowledge development.

EmpowerUs uses several methods and methodologies to support the empowerment of coastal communities – from a Community Governance Audit to Q methodology and ocean literacy as well as the development of a Digital Twin. Many of the specific methods used in EmpowerUs either feed into, or are inspired by a living lab methodology – which is organised into six ‘Transitional Coastal Labs’ (TCLs) across Europe: Burgas, Bulgaria; Limassol, Cyprus; Åland, Finland;

Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland; Træna, Norway; and Cap de Creus, Spain – to pilot and test varying projects aimed at building sustainable, inclusive and empowered trajectories for equitable coastal community transitions.

Our Handbook consists of 14 chapters including an introduction and conclusion by the editors. The introduction introduces the EmpowerUs project and discusses key concepts that our inclusive methodologies try to capture and mobilise. The chapters that follow are structured into three parts: 1. Co-creation: planning, designing and doing; 2. Methods and methodologies for scientific knowledge production; and 3. Methods and methodologies for empowerment. While the chapters focus on a particular method or methodology, they explore how they contributed to inclusive coastal transition and reflect on the lessons learned, challenges, strengths and adaptations required to deploy such methods in coastal community transition contexts. Taken together, the chapters make theoretical, empirical, applied, reflexive and ethical contributions that can be transferred to other research and innovation projects focused on coastal community transition and beyond. The Handbook’s conclusion reflects on the chapters that precede it highlights key challenges and lessons learned, as well as cross-cutting themes.

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Part I: INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction: Inclusive Methodologies for Equitable Coastal Community Transitions

Authors: Madeleine Gustavsson, Sunniva Solnør, Katrina Rønningen (Ruralis – Institute for Rural and Regional Research)

1.1 Setting the scene

Coastal communities in Europe are experiencing challenges around their future sustainability and resilience linked to a wide range of issues such as depopulation, environmental degradation, climate change, marginalisation of communities in the blue growth agenda, vulnerability of social groups on the coast, economic decline, and challenges for traditional users (e.g. fishers) associated with the introduction of new sectors such as tourism, aquaculture and wind energy (Bennet et al., 2021). While the trajectories of coastal community development are often framed by mega-trends and wider inter/national policy directions, there is a need for communities to be empowered to set their own agenda for their futures. Empowerment cannot be achieved from external efforts alone – communities have to be enabled or supported to empower themselves. These were the key issues that the Horizon Europe project EmpowerUs ‘Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as Users of the Sea to ensure sustainable coastal development’ set out to explore.

While there is a need for communities to be empowered, to plan and act for change, there is also a need to recognise that communities are diverse – they are constituted by diverse groups of people and individuals that may come at issues from varying perspectives. How, then, can we promote sustainability and resilience within coastal community transitions while ensuring inclusivity as well as equity?

EmpowerUs draws upon two key concepts in understanding diversity in coastal communities and the importance of including diverse social groups in transition processes. First, the concept ‘**Users of the Sea**’ draws on gender and intersectional perspectives in conceptualising who has a stake in coastal community transition.

‘In EmpowerUs we define ‘Users of the Sea’ not only in terms of those who are present at sea daily (e.g. fishers, or offshore workers) but focus on

the wider context in which decisions, innovations and change is embedded – that is, coastal communities operating in ocean as well as coastal spaces, where women, men and youth are active agents of continuation and change. In doing so, we importantly attend to the wider context in which the ocean economy and relations to ocean space operates’ (Gustavsson & Solnør 2022, p. 11).

Second, we draw on the European Green Deal agenda and its stated ambition to ‘**Leave No One Behind**’¹ (LNOB) in arguing for the importance of ensuring inclusivity for equitable processes and outcomes of green transitions. The European Green Deal states:

‘the Commission will propose a Just Transition Mechanism, including a Just Transition Fund, to leave no one behind. The [green] transition can only succeed if it is conducted in a fair and inclusive way. The most vulnerable are the most exposed to the harmful effects of climate change and environmental degradation.’ (European Commission, 2019, p. 16)

While the European Green Deal heavily focus on carbon neutrality there is an argument that community transitions go beyond climate change and is a broader issue around community development. The EmpowerUs project takes as its starting point that Leaving No One Behind remains an equally important principle in broader coastal community transitions (which may include climate and environmental concerns) as well.

While the challenges around coastal community transitions are multifarious, this Handbook takes on a particular challenge in understanding how coastal community transition can be inclusive and equitable – that is, how methods and methodologies, as well as knowledge production, innovation, impact and empowerment processes can be inclusive. In doing so, we reflect on the methods and methodologies used in the large and complex Horizon Europe Research and Innovation project EmpowerUs.

¹LNOB is also part of the UN 2030 Agenda and its Sustainable Development Goals, which includes SDG 10 on Reducing Inequalities as well as a commitment to Leave No One Behind (LNOB).

We seek to open the lid on the process of doing research, innovation and co-production/co-creation to explore our, sometimes hard earned, lessons learned. The Handbook intends to draw out key insights that other researchers, students and practitioners can learn from in designing and implementing their own research, innovation and impact projects concerned with coastal community transitions. Importantly, we bring light to the challenges embedded in the ambition to Leave No One Behind from a methodological standpoint.

1.2 Inclusive methodologies: key themes

To achieve and explore equitable coastal community transitions that leave no one behind, there is a need for tools and approaches that are inclusive. In this Handbook we interrogate and examine the concept of 'Inclusive Methodologies' drawing on our experiences from EmpowerUs. The following equitation can help to illustrate the underpinning principles of the concept:

How (Methodology) + Who (Inclusion) = Inclusive methodologies

Inclusive methodologies can, in addition, have varying purposes – for example to achieve empowerment and/or to lead to equitable coastal community transitions.

To more carefully understand what is meant by 'Inclusive Methodologies' we introduce a number of associated concepts: i) inclusion, ii) empowerment; and iii) gender and intersectionality. By methods and methodologies here we mean approaches and tools that either are: a) used to produce knowledge about something (i.e. research focused), or b) processes or approaches that are intended to empower coastal communities (i.e. innovation and impact focused). While these categories are not mutually exclusive, they are helpful distinctions in understanding the target, aim and focus of methods and methodologies.

1.2.1 Inclusion

As mentioned earlier, the EU's vision for a Green Deal emphasises the importance of equity through inclusion (European Commission, 2019). However, uncertainties regarding the practical implementation of inclusion and the various nuances of its definition stress the need to explore the meaning of inclusion. While inclusion in common parlance can

be synonymous with participation, Quick & Feldman (2011) argue inclusion goes beyond participation. While participation focus on a fair and equitable participatory process (see e.g. the oft cited ladder of participation by Arnstein, 1969), inclusion further highlights the need for capacity building and to build 'communities of practice' (Leino & Puumala, 2020; Quick & Feldman, 2011). Quick and Feldman (2022, p. 286) writes: 'Engaging multiple ways of knowing, coproducing the content and process, and sustaining temporal openness are key features of inclusion that contribute to the building of community'.

Arguably, inclusion goes beyond the inclusion of someone to also include their knowledge, perspectives, views and values in addition to 'power-sharing in shaping the process and defining the content/focus of an initiative – that is, the structure and approach of the inclusion process is a key concern' (Sørensen et al., 2025). Further, Morrison et al. (2020) attend to how the dynamics of inclusion and exclusion are deeply intertwined with societal structures, encompassing everything from physical spaces to attitudes and policies. Individuals with disabilities, for example, often find themselves navigating a world where their inclusion is contingent upon how accommodating or restrictive these societal and physical structures are (Layton & Steel, 2015). Societal structures and, by extension, the built environment, policies or approaches can either exclude or foster a sense of belonging and inclusion.

Drawing on these literatures, Sørensen et al (2025) conceptualise inclusion around three aspects: i) inclusion of someone (diverse people and more-than-human beings), ii) inclusion of something (diverse knowledge, perspectives and values) and iii) structures that enable inclusion through (infra)structures/settings/approaches. Taken together, inclusion can be seen through the lens of recognitional, procedural and distributive justice (e.g. Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). Such concepts have commonly been drawn on in seeking to understand whether discourses around blue economy/ies and blue growth can be reshaped into discussions around blue justice (e.g. Bennett et al., 2021; Gustavsson et al., 2021; Deliverable 4.2). EmpowerUs and this Handbook engage these terms as we explore the meaning of inclusion in our methods and methodologies.

1.2.2 Empowerment

One of EmpowerUs' key objectives was to empower coastal communities. Empowerment is however a concept that can be conceptualised differently depending on perspectives and priorities. When centring issues around diversity and equity, in addition to being interested in how empowerment is achieved, EmpowerUs was interested in understanding who was empowered and how. Interrelated to these discussions is the power groups and individuals have and how this shapes the empowerment of coastal communities and their members/inhabitants. EmpowerUs has mainly drawn on Avelino's (2017, p. 512) definition of empowerment:

'The process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilize resources and institutions to achieve a goal. This process of 'gaining capacity' is unpacked along three dimensions: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies to mobilize them and (3) the willingness to do so.'

Another field that has drawn on empowerment as a key concept is women and gender studies. Within this field empowerment has often been conceptualised as 'the ability to exercise choice' (Kabeer 1999, p.435) highlighting the need to focus on resources, agency and achievements. The Gender and Diversity Plan – Deliverable D1.1 – Gustavsson and Solnør (2022) reviewed some of this literature and highlighted Pettersen and Solbakken's (1998) three conditions of women's empowerment (see Box 1.1).

Box 1.1 Pettersen and Solbakken's (1998) three conditions of women's empowerment

1. *Participation* can be shaped by top-down or bottom-up processes and intentions and the extent to which participation can be empowering depend on how participation is done. While forms of participation which is shaped by top-down agendas may be less empowering, 'transformative participation', Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p. 322) argue, is 'both a means to empowerment, and an end in itself' as actors experiences of being involved is itself transformative. They conclude by arguing 'the quality of participation depends on who is involved, how and on whose terms' (Pettersen and Solbakken 1998, p. 322).
2. *Conscientization* highlights the importance of understanding one's own situation as being embedded in (for example gendered, racialized and classed) structures of power. Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p. 322) highlight that '[t]ransformative participation implies bringing about understanding of one's situation'.
3. The importance of moving from individual to collective action through *solidarity*.

Pettersen and Solbakken (1998, p.324) highlight that women are not powerless as they 'can have considerable power in households, families and in rural communities, but this does not necessarily lead to structural power'. In EmpowerUs we have drawn on these insights to emphasise the need to view women and other marginalised groups as individuals and groups with agency – yet their agency may be constrained in varying contexts which need to be understood and taken into account in our methods and methodologies.

1.2.3 Gender and Intersectionality

In building on the ambition to Leave No One Behind, inclusion and empowerment, EmpowerUs has had a strong emphasis on gender and intersectionality throughout all activities. The Gender, Equality and Diversity plan (D1.1) (Gustavsson and Solnør 2022) outlines EmpowerUs' approach by introducing themes and concepts such as Users of the Sea (see Section 1.1 above), Intersectionality (Box 1.1) and Diverse Blue Economies (Box 1.2). EmpowerUs set up a Gender and Equity Board that met regularly to discuss these issues as the project evolved.

Box 1.2 Intersectionality (Gustavsson and Solnør 2022 p.8)

'The concept of **intersectionality** was first introduced by black feminist scholar Kimberlé Williams Crenshaw (1989). The initial intention of the term was to highlight the multiple – intersecting – layers of oppression that individuals and groups experience. The concept has since been taken up in wider feminist theory and has been used to study the intersections between gender and other identities such as ethnicity, class, sexuality and so forth. ... In EmpowerUs we draw on an intersectional approach in exploring diverse coastal community members participation and empowerment.'

Box 1.3 Diverse Blue Economies (Gustavsson and Solnør 2022 p. 9-10)

Diverse Blue Economies: ‘In taking a gender and intersectional approach in exploring the empowerment of coastal communities in transitioning towards more sustainable futures, we also need to adopt a broader understanding of the ‘economy’ to enable us to include women’s and marginalised groups’ often invisible contributions to communities and to their development. Gibson-Graham’s ‘diverse economies’ perspective is particularly useful to our project as it enables us to explore complicated and often hidden relations, contributions, and work that make up the economy as we know it. ... To make this thinking more tangible and to illustrate their point Gibson-Graham (2013) developed the iceberg model which explains how particular diverse economies operates. In EmpowerUs we will draw on the diverse economies approach to broaden the scope of the economy to also include hidden and unpaid contributions and work which in ocean industries and communities are often done by women, youth, and other marginalised groups.’

‘In EmpowerUs [...] we seek to explore the links between the use of the sea and the onshore local communities who may or may not benefit from the blue economy. That is, we go beyond the sea space to also explore how the blue economy may impact local coastal communities and its diverse constituencies differently.

We want to explore and remain attentive to various configurations of social inclusion and exclusion around who ‘belongs’ (see Gustavsson,

Figure 1.1 Diverse Economies Iceberg by Community Economies Collective is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License

on those who often become marginalised in these discussions (e.g. women, ethnic minorities, migrant workers, youth). This approach is closely associated with how we understand the ‘Users of the Sea’ concept.’

1.3 EmpowerUs Research and Innovation project

EmpowerUs was an approximately €6 million project that brought together 16 partners across 9 countries over 3 years (2022-2025) to work directly

with coastal communities to inspire and enable coastal communities to tackle the most pressing environmental, economic and social challenges that exist in their communities. At the heart of the project were 6 **Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)** across Europe (see Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.2. The 6 Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)

At the core of EmpowerUs was the TCL structure, which involved working with communities in real-life settings to co-develop, test, pilot, evaluate, and refine solutions. In each TCL, local academic leads worked with a local host and community to co-produce an intervention with the aim to support local people to address issues related to developing more sustainable, resilient and equitable coastal transitions. The interventions – i.e. the pilot – were funded by the project and were carried out by the local host agency that had the capacity to make change happen in each TCL. This collaborative structure – between the local academic and host – ensured that the research was grounded in local realities and that solutions were both practical and relevant to local challenges. The TCLs will be discussed in more depth in Chapter 2.

A series of workshops served as a platform for dialogue and collaboration in each TCL. In the first workshop, community members identified key challenges that needed to be addressed. In the second workshop, participants explored possible solutions and activities to tackle these challenges (see Chapter 2). To understand the community structure, diverse contexts, and key stakeholders, a Governance Audit (Chapter 5) was conducted which involved a review of how each community was governed – alongside fieldwork to capture local realities. In combination with community interviews, fieldwork, and analyses of possibilities and potentials, these efforts led to the creation of pilot initiatives where possible solutions were tested in each community.

Åland. Credit: Kristina Svells

If successful, the pilots could be scaled up and integrated into broader research and innovation programs with long-term pathways, known as Tailored Empowerment Programs, ensuring a lasting impact beyond the EmpowerUs project. In EmpowerUs, each TCL received a €50,000 Action Fund to test their pilots and programmes to find practical solutions that could be expanded to other regions.

Figure 1.3 Voting for pilot options in the Cap de Creus, Spanish TCL Second Workshop. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

Figure 1.4 Workshop 2 in Bulgaria. Credit: Anna Antonova

The process of developing and testing the pilots has been supported by a number of methodologies and guiding principles – such as the principle of Leaving No One Behind meaning that TCLs continuously sought to improve inclusion throughout the project. The focus of this Handbook is to discuss the specific methods and methodologies that were used in EmpowerUs, with specific attention to aspects of inclusion and inclusiveness.

1.4 Introducing the Handbook's Chapters

The Handbook brings together 14 chapters that reflect on the methods and methodologies used in the EmpowerUs project to explore challenges, lessons learned and experiences concerning how project participants using those methods have managed, or struggled with, inclusiveness. This is done to open the lid on the process of doing research and innovation and enable the sharing of experiences and insights to other researchers and practitioners working in the field of coastal community transition. The overall aim of the Handbook is to explore how methods and methodologies can be inclusive, what the challenges may be, and how to potentially overcome them as well as attend to the ways in which it impacts knowledge production, empowerment and equitable outcomes of coastal transitions.

The 14 chapters are structured into five parts. The first part is introducing the Handbook (Chapter 1). Part II, III and IV are thematically structured and consists of chapters focused on methods and methodologies, written by different authors – the majority of which were project participants in EmpowerUs. The Handbook ends with a concluding chapter by the editors (Chapter 14).

1.4.1 Co-creation: planning, designing and doing

Part II of this Handbook addresses EmpowerUs' co-creation process and structure. It begins with discussing how co-creation can be designed in a research and innovation project, how it evolves over time and how methods and approaches have to be adapted, refined and sometimes revisited as the research teams learn from the communities (Chapter 2). Chapter 3 considers the funding context in which research projects – specifically those focused on the social sciences and humanities – operate and how different research paradigms can frame, collide, and restrict the potential of social science and humanities approaches. Following on from considering the underpinning structure (i.e. drawing inspiration from a living lab approach) and reflecting on the tensions and frames which the funding contexts place research projects in, Chapter 4 reflects on 'in the field experiences' in the six TCLs that the project has developed and worked with over the course of the project lifetime. While learning from the field, key lessons and methodological implications are shared and discussed by the authors.

1.4.2 Inclusive methods and methodologies for scientific knowledge production

Part III of the Handbook introduces particular methods and methodologies that have focused on scientific knowledge production. This section interrogates these methods and methodologies from an inclusivity perspective: what have been the challenges; what adaptations to these approaches have authors made and why; and what are the outcomes for inclusive and equitable coastal community transitions? Chapter 5 focuses on the Governance Audit which examines the institutional and governance contexts in each of the six country regions of EmpowerUs. Chapter 6 outlines the Realist Evaluation approach, developed to evaluate the pilot activities, what works and not – in what circumstances – and which interventions in the project could be scaled up or replicated. Other chapters include Q-methodology (Chapter 7), used to develop a baseline of empowerment in the six TCLs and Photovoice (Chapter 8), which explores connections to the ocean and community through participant-taken photos that prompted reflections and deeper, often unspoken, meanings. The final chapter in this section focuses on Reflection Interviews (Chapter 9), which is an approach developed in EmpowerUs to record, reflect and 'peer debrief' around ethical and methodological issues of inclusion in large projects.

1.4.3 Methods and methodologies for empowerment

Part IV moves on to discuss methods and methodologies that more intentionally focus on empowerment by, for example, supporting communities and by seeking to build capacity. While some of these methods also involve scientific data collection, they are generally more innovation and impact focused than targeted at data collection.

In this section, Chapter 10 discusses the extensive synthesis work that went into developing a database of Empowerment Tools through the Eklipse process. Chapter 11 considers lessons learned and outlines useful advice and recommendations for how to develop ocean literacy strategies that are inclusive. Chapter 12 discusses the development and utility of the EmpowerCoast Digital Twin – in particular in relation to the principle of Leaving No One Behind. Finally, Chapter 13 introduces us to the topic of Nature-based Solutions and how inclusive methodologies can support the development of such solutions. These chapters reflect on how their methods and methodologies can be inclusive as well as discusses challenges and experiences that authors have gained through deploying these approaches in the EmpowerUs project.

1.5 Conclusions

While there is a wider recognition that coastal community transitions are important for a more sustainable and resilient future, there is little agreement on how to achieve such grand ambitions. Even if many scholars and practitioners – and the EU Green Deal itself – highlight the need for transitions to Leave No One Behind and the importance of inclusivity to achieve those goals, there is little understanding of how equitable coastal community transitions can be achieved. This Handbook will only address one dimension of this much larger issue – that is, to explore how methods and methodologies can be inclusive in theory and in practice and how that, in turn, shapes transition outcomes around inclusion, Leaving No One Behind and equity. The Handbook ends with a concluding chapter (Chapter 14) where we bring together key themes and insights that have been learned across the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Project EmpowerUs.

Part II: CO-CREATION: PLANNING, DESIGNING AND DOING

2. Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) as co-creation

Authors: Maiken Bjørkan, Cecilie Bratt, Vida Steiro and Anette Bjørnå (Nordland Research Institute)

2.1 Introduction

In EmpowerUs, coastal communities are considered key actors and agents who can proactively decide and plan for a more resilient and sustainable future. Thus, the project developed Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) as a multi actor co-creation approach to support and empower coastal communities to act for change.

This chapter first presents how six TCLs were included in EmpowerUs as a vital part of the co-creation process from the outset of the project. Each TCL is introduced, explaining their challenges and their solutions to tackle the identified challenges. The measures and solutions for each of the TCLs are known as the pilot or pilot activities. We then show how workshops were used as the main method to co-create with the TCLs and we further reflect upon its inclusiveness. Finally, the chapter presents a number of lessons learnt and provides a shortlist of what to keep in mind when designing projects that use co-creative and iterative processes.

2.2 Transition Coastal Labs

The development of the TCLs builds upon the living laboratories methodology (Compagnucci et al., 2021; European Commission, 2018) as well as the 'Transition Super Lab approach' (Konstantinidou, & Ayfantopoulou 2024). In EmpowerUs, TCLs are collaborative spaces where coastal communities, researchers, and local organisations work together to create and test new solutions to environmental and social challenges. Unlike traditional Living Labs, which mainly focus on improving existing services or technologies, TCLs also aim to change the systems and rules that shape community life. They help develop new ideas and practices (innovative power) and explore how these can be embedded in policies, institutions, and everyday routines (transformative power). This approach supports long-term, meaningful change rather than short-term fixes (see Avelino, 2017. See also EmpowerUs Deliverable D4.2 for more on TCLs).

The TCLs were set up to involve multi-actors to co-define the challenges (**co-assessment**)

and possible solutions as well as their feasibility (**co-planning**), identify together, pilot and test co-developed solutions to coastal challenges (**co-design and co-implement**) as well as monitor and assesses their potential impact/co-benefits (**co-monitoring and co-evaluation**). Each TCL was allocated an earmarked Action Fund of €50,000 to develop pilot actions according to their needs. The needs would be defined by the local communities in workshops and developed further in collaboration with the project researchers.

In order to put together the best and most relevant team to address the challenges at hand, it was important to pre-define, at least in part, coastal communities as the main focus of our research and pre-formulate the challenges that the project was going to solve within these communities. Challenges discussed during the proposal development included blue growth, blue injustice and ecological issues. We did this by including local teams with long-term relations with the TCLs in the proposal phase. The local teams are made up of an *academic lead*, which are scientific experts located in the region; and a *host*, which are organisations located in the region with intimate knowledge, experience and skills related to the different local challenges at hand.

The TCLs are also assessing the pilot's feasibility, before implementing, testing, monitoring and evaluating the co-developed solutions. To do so, local community organisations in the TCLs were involved as key partners in the project from the application writing stage. This was to ensure that the solutions were relevant and would be implemented in a sound way in the TCLs, and that the work done by the local organisations was paid for, which was possible given that they were consortium partners.

Within the EmpowerUs project, six TCLs have been established across Europe's key sea basins: Åland (Finland), Træna (Norway), Cap de Creus (Spain), Burgas (Bulgaria), the Eastern Limassol Region (Cyprus), and Connemara and the Aran Islands (Ireland). Each TCL has focused on addressing region-specific challenges related to coastal sustainability, governance, and socio-economic resilience.

2.2.1 Åland (Finland)

In Åland the academic lead organisation, Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), collaborated with the host organisation, the Government of Åland Fisheries Agency. This Baltic Sea autonomous archipelago region is home to 6,500 islands and a population of 30,000. Åland faces multiple coastal challenges, including low fisheries profitability and a declining number of small-scale fishers, diminishing fish stocks, and a complex water ownership structure.

Figure 2.1 Photo of Åland. Credit: Åland TCL Team

The traditional fisheries as a cultural heritage is under pressure, and the Baltic Sea water environment is negatively affected by pollution and acidification. The Åland pilot aimed to create solutions and foster co-creation through workshops, seminars, a water-ownership survey, an informational campaign, a state of fisheries report, a webpage for updating fishers on administrative regulations, and cooperation with local hunting and fishing museums.

2.2.2 Træna (Norway)

Located off Norway's Helgeland coast, Træna is a small island community with 460 residents spread across its four largest islands. Kunnskapsparken Helgeland acted as the host organisation, working alongside Nordland Research Institute as the academic lead. The region struggles with out-migration, housing shortages, transportation limitations, attractiveness for

Figure 2.2 Norway TCL. Credit: Sunniva Solnør

settlement, integration, and youth retention. The pilot project, 'Hooked on Træna' aimed through targeted activities, to strengthen local expertise, promote collaboration among stakeholders, and provide training tools that enhanced local capacity and fostered lasting, sustainable initiatives and structures in the community.

2.2.3 Cap de Creus (Spain)

The Spanish TCL in Cap de Creus was led by the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), acting as both the host and academic lead organisation. This Mediterranean region grapples with the effects of mass tourism, challenges in fostering blue economy growth, a decline in pro-environmental behaviours,

Figure 2.3 Traditional fishing gear from Cap de Creus. Credit: Maria Velasco

and a loss of local seafood knowledge and cultural appreciation of nature. To address these issues, two pilot initiatives were developed. The first, 'NaturCap,' is a digital initiative providing interactive digital resources to support conservation efforts and community collaboration. This initiative sought to enhance ecological and cultural values, equip residents and visitors with participatory tools, and strengthen the region's social fabric and cooperative capacity. Complementing this, a Food Sovereignty Forum was launched as the second pilot, bringing together over a hundred participants to discuss sustainable food systems and local biodiversity. While the first edition focused on food sovereignty, future iterations are planned to expand into broader biodiversity and educational themes. Both pilots serve as key strategies for fostering community engagement and promoting sustainable practices in the region.

2.2.4 Burgas (Bulgaria)

The pilot in Burgas, a coastal city on the Black Sea, was led by the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation as the host organisation and Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU) as the academic lead. This region faces pressures related to the economic dominance of tourism, urban expansion affecting the coastline, population decline, and youth retention challenges.

Figure 2.4 Exploring Burgas. Credit: Radostina Tzenova

Additionally, local communities often feel that they have limited influence on policy, while climate change introduces new risks. The pilot aimed to enhance the connectivity between Burgas, its three lakes, and the sea, engage diverse groups in ocean literacy and citizen science, diversify tourism

offerings through ecotourism, and strengthen the role of NGOs and local citizen initiatives in blue economy development.

2.2.5 Eastern Limassol Region (Cyprus)

In Cyprus, the Eastern Limassol Region presents a landscape marked by limited connectivity between the community fabric and the coastline, limited development, heavy industrialisation, and undervaluation of its ecological significance. Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute served as the academic lead organisation, with the Development

Figure 2.5 At the coast of Eastern Limassol. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael

Agency of Limassol acting as the host. The pilot initiative, 'Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan', built on the previous work done in EmpowerUs, focusing on understanding the baseline and the challenges, setting out a strategic vision for a sustainable coastal transition of the area. The plan outlines specific actions and projects, all identified with the active engagement of local communities, groups, and authorities. This participatory effort aimed to map and promote the ecological, social, and cultural value of the coastal space of the eastern Limassol region to facilitate a shift towards a more sustainable future. The Pilot also supported the maturation of one of the proposed projects, specifically that of a coastal nature path, the implementation of which will commence soon after the end of the EmpowerUs project.

2.2.6 Connemara & the Aran Islands (Ireland)

In Ireland, the TCL covering Connemara and the Aran Islands was led by Queen's University Belfast as the academic lead and Údarás na Gaeltachta as the host organisation.

Figure 2.6 Connemara and the Aran Islands. Credit: Údarás na Gaeltachta

The region faces challenges such as displacement of local interests due to blue growth pressures, emigration of young and highly skilled individuals, limited long-term employment opportunities, and the dominance of extractive marine industries like aquaculture. The pilot focused on developing the social economy of the coast by supporting social enterprises with technical assistance, training and a best practice visit to evaluate projects in the Scottish Highlands and islands.

2.3 The EmpowerUs co-creation process

The method is a concrete yet flexible step-by-step process that can be applied in a variety of coastal contexts. The process comprises four stages, each of which is to be carried out by researchers, planners or others in close cooperation with local stakeholders. At the centre stage are the pilots that the TCLs have co-created with the scientific teams. This means that we have designed a process where all stakeholders can share the responsibility of developing a pilot and implementing it together. What is important to note is that the co-creation processes are taking place at multiple levels: between Work Package (WP) and task leads in the project, between the local teams and the WP leads; and the local teams are leading the on-the-ground co-creation processes with Users of the Sea in the

TCLs. This has been an iterative process that can be divided into four, interlinked steps: 1) ideation and exploration, 2) co-creation and co-design, 3) real-life experimentation and testing 3) evaluation and validation by end-users and stakeholders.

2.4 Workshops to co-create pilots for a sustainable future

In EmpowerUs, we have organised workshops to co-create solutions with TCLs. In these workshops, researchers and community members came together to share knowledge, explore challenges, and develop ideas for possible solutions from the ground up. Researchers also provided advice to help guide decisions. The information gathered during the workshops has been used both to design pilot projects and to support other parts of the project, including research publications and reporting.

Figure 2.7 Workshop in Ireland. Credit: Údarás na Gaeltachta

Figure 2.8 Workshop in Norway. Credit: Sunniva Solnør

Figure 2.9 Workshop in Spain. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

Figure 2.10 Workshop in Bulgaria. Credit: Anna Antonova

Workshops can be described as an arrangement in which a group of people learn, gain new knowledge, perform creative problem-solving, brainstorm, or innovate in relation to a domain-specific issue (Ødegård et al., 2023). Workshops can have different means and purposes, such as being a mean in itself or a practice or as a research methodology. EmpowerUs is based on bottom-up approaches, and as part of that approach, a series of two workshops were organised in all six TCLs. The EmpowerUs consortium co-designed the workshops as 1) a process to ensure a participatory approach to co-create sustainable pilots; 2) as a research methodology designed to produce reliable and valid data across the work packages; and 3) as a means to empower participants (skills, network, knowledge, competence). The research partners met several times to co-create a design that would fit different contexts (i.e., workshop duration, location) and to meet stakeholders' expectations (i.e., avoid repetition of other research projects and produce knowledge perceived as credible, legitimate and relevant for the participants). Importantly, before the workshops and throughout the project lifetime, the local teams used a mix of methods to involve and ground check with the TCL, as part of the

continuous co-creation. This includes workshops, interviews, Q-methodology and more. The mix of methods has been important to ensure a multi-actor approach, where the necessary measures have been taken based on the local context. For instance, in Finland and Ireland, it was somewhat difficult to get people to participate in workshops. Hence, the local teams have been using additional approaches and tools such as interviews, WhatsApp-groups and surveys to reach and recruit actors.

In the first workshop, the invited stakeholders defined their country specific challenges to which they need a strategy to address. While there were numerous challenges identified at each workshop, the stakeholders were asked to narrow it down as much as possible, focusing on sustainability issues in the area.

In the second workshop, the stakeholders worked together to envision possible future solutions to the co-defined challenges in the first workshop. They were asked to suggest measures that could be taken (by themselves and/or the municipalities) to put the TCL on a trajectory towards a desirable future. Scientists then explored and challenged the relevance of the solutions for the project goals. In addition, the solutions had to fit with the host organisation's skill sets to make sure the pilots could be implemented successfully.

2.5 Are workshops inclusive?

In order to ensure participation in practice, a workshop is often the 'go-to' method in research projects to make a space for different actors to come together around a shared goal, collaborate effectively and solve complex problems (Ødegård et al., 2023). In our experience, well-designed workshops ensure that participants are active in the discussions and open to reflections on their own and others' opinions and contribute to achieving the goals of the workshops (see also Hu, 2024).

Workshops can also bring people together in a way they perhaps have not experienced before, and sometimes with very practical outcomes. For instance, in one of the workshops conducted in the Norwegian TCL (Træna), a new inhabitant who had been looking to buy locally grown potatoes got to know a local farmer during group work. This also led to greater understanding of the type of information that newcomers might be interested in knowing when moving to Træna. In Cyprus, the community became engaged in strategic planning and in Finland, water owners have been introduced to the planning of marine protected areas.

To achieve meaningful participation, the number of people must be limited in order to ensure that everyone is heard, that they can participate actively and influence the result of the workshop. There are also practical limitations to the number of people in a workshop, such as space and costs. This means that workshops entail a participatory process where some, but not all, can be included. An important step in the living lab process was to do an initial stakeholder mapping in each TCL for including a range of local stakeholder interests. Even so, there is a risk that workshops may ‘facilitate’ participation in ways that privilege certain actors and types of action and foreclose others. For instance, immigrants may need translation, and fishers may not be able to join because of seasonal work. Parents, and particularly women, might be working during the day, but have to attend to the family needs in the afternoon. The workshop format may not be perceived as accessible to all types of stakeholders, so even if trying to invite a breadth of stakeholders, not all want to take part. Workshops may also become an arena for power asymmetry related to e.g. social and cultural capital, such as education and training in talking in the public. Since the Leaving No One Behind principle is key for EmpowerUs, we have had to ensure inclusion through a mix of methods, such as semi-structured interviews, Q method, photovoice, blue justice stories and participatory observation.

Living labs differ from traditional labs in many ways. Importantly, it is impossible to control a large number of issues that will affect the process, dynamic, interaction, level of participation and hence the success of a workshop and other methods used. All workshop dynamics are different and to some degree uncontrollable for both facilitators and participants. Sometimes, all stakeholders are active and participate and other times some participants will be more passive. In other cases, participants might have previous experiences with each other and the workshop setting and discussions can trigger these further.

2.6 Challenges and lessons learned

Establishing TCLs and having local partners in TCL teams have been key to making research activities relevant and appropriate at the community level. This is related to the long-term knowledge that the partners have about the TCL areas, as well as the languages spoken locally. In addition, co-creating, testing and implementing pilot solutions using the living labs methodology, has arguably led to continued, deep participation from

the local communities (beyond the local partner organisations) throughout the project period. This is because their involvement has been continuous throughout the project lifetime and between all actors involved in the project. This again may foster continued partnerships and collaboration, as well as sustainable practices, resulting from co-creation activities, cross learning between academic and non-academic partners, and capacity building throughout the project. Lastly, the co-creation design of this project has provided invaluable insight into bottom-up perspectives in different European coastal communities, and lessons learned about the integration of research and innovation processes in such settings. For instance, workshop 1 was planned to be a future scenario workshop, but after pushback from the TCL teams, we co-created a new workshop design. Based on the academic leads’ extensive experience in their respective regions, in their opinion the future scenario workshops were too abstract and removed from the realities on the ground. The lessons learned are to take the community and local peoples’ needs seriously: what’s in it for them?

There have also been challenges with the co-creation design of the project. There are multiple interlinkages between all Work Packages (WP) of the EmpowerUs project, and the results in the different Work Packages build on each other. The TCL teams have experienced pressure as a result of colliding and constant demands from different WPs at the same time. Due to the interlinkages, it has been challenging to keep up with all the research activities that depend on each other, and TCL teams need to constantly be on top of these and adjust their actions in the local communities in accordance with changes at the project WP levels. The practicality of having 6 different TCLs with 12 different partner organisations having to meet and collaborate with 6 different Work Package leads, and even more task leads, has also been a challenging aspect. Sometimes calendars just do not align with each other, including holiday periods of 9 different countries, and juggling EmpowerUs with other projects and work tasks.

There have also been challenges related to inclusion. The research activities were designed in the same way across all 6 TCLs. However, what feels inclusive and appropriate in one place may not be experienced the same way elsewhere. No single approach can fully capture the diversity of perspectives in every community, and there will always be limitations and blind spots (Bjørkan et al., 2023). This is why the TCL teams, with their deep

understanding of local relationships and contexts, were essential. They played a key role in adapting and translating the shared EmpowerUs methods into co-creation processes that were as inclusive as possible while staying true to the project’s goals. Their local knowledge helped ensure that participation was meaningful, even if inclusion could never be perfect or complete. While the Træna TCL worked intensively to include all – or representatives – of all groups, the Åland TCL found that it needed to narrow its focus for the inclusion of Users of the Sea. While women were the most active participants in Træna, they were quite invisible in water management in Åland and became important to target. In Cyprus, the displacement of a whole community following the inter-communal conflict and the division of the island in 1974, led to the exclusion of the displaced Turkish Cypriot community of Pentakomo from the EmpowerUs participatory process. Method triangulation on the one hand, and on the other hand the way the pilots allow for benefitting and empowering more groups than those directly participating during the TCL process, implies that measuring the success of inclusion is not a straightforward matter (something that is reflected upon in Chapter 14).

Box 2.1 Lessons learned for designing large co-creation projects

To learn from the experience of the co-creation design of the EmpowerUs project, here are some tips for designing large projects based on co-creation and iterative processes:

- Think twice about how tasks and WPs depend on each other’s work, and plan for how to most effectively make use of results from one task/WP into another without necessarily needing to demand time that could have been avoided from living lab partners.
- If possible, include living lab partners in the planning from an early point, even in the project’s conceptualisation (see Chapter 3 where this is reflected upon more in detail).
- Make sure to clearly outline the expectations from on-the-ground partners in terms of contribution to research and implementation of solutions and allocate resources accordingly.
- Double check partner organisations’ holiday schedules and adjust timelines, deliverables and milestones accordingly.

- True co-creation takes time and can cause frustration – design an adaptable and flexible project plan: one task may require several rounds of discussion within the consortium, and back and forth with living lab community members, and will not necessarily end up as initially expected, so allocate enough time and resources, and be open for adjustments in plans.
- True co-creation may not be for all issues/ challenges - ask yourself: when is co-creation a good idea? Participation can take various forms – from passively receiving information to consulting, involving, collaborating and empowering actors. What are you aiming for and how can you achieve it? See for instance Bjørkan et al. (2023) for more information about such reflections.

Getting to Know my Coastline Ocean Literacy Activity, Cyprus. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael

Finland. Credit: Viktor Eriksson

3. From proposal to implementation: reflecting on methodological path dependencies in large projects

Authors: Anna Antonova (Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society, LMU Munich), Maiken Bjørkan (Nordland Research Institute), Cecilie Helén Bratt (Nordland Research Institute)

In this chapter, we look back on the road from designing the project proposal to answer all aspects of the Horizon Europe call text, and how this proposal laid the foundation and frames for the practical implementation of what we had promised to deliver three years earlier. We first describe the process of building a social science project with a strong emphasis on inclusive, bottom-up and interactive approaches that were embedded in the project's methodological design. Reflections are then made on how the practical project design, including the novel inclusion of an unallocated amount of funding earmarked to pay for implementation of pilot interventions within the Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) pilot projects, was realised. Furthermore, we look at how tensions arise in various ways from opposing paradigms: the call emphasised social science and the humanities as important disciplines (that belong to constructivist, participatory, or even critical theory paradigms), but many of the call objectives asked for solutions proving an objective truth through monitoring and measuring effects (characteristic of positivist or post-positivist paradigms).

3.1 Writing the proposal – pre-promised activities

We were a small group of researchers who noticed the funding call 'Socio-economic Empowerment of the Users of the Sea', which led to the EmpowerUs project. Having spent most of our careers working with coastal communities and fisheries-related issues, we were excited to see an EU-funded call with a strong emphasis on the social sciences, especially the importance of resilient, inclusive, healthy, and green rural, coastal, and urban communities. Two key aspects of the call particularly resonated with us:

1. The need to 'increase our understanding of the differential impacts of climate, environmental, socio-economic, and demographic changes on rural, coastal, and urban areas to identify ways to turn these changes into equal opportunities for people wherever they live, enhancing territorial cohesion and enabling a just transition.'

2. The call to 'support bottom-up, community-led innovation to empower communities to develop, test, and upscale solutions that address global challenges in locally adapted ways.'

Social scientists working in interdisciplinary settings often find themselves working in support of nature-based or technological sciences instead of leading the agenda and priority setting in their inquiries. The opportunity to focus on empowering people to act for change has thus been particularly compelling – and needed, as this Handbook will conclude. Many of the concepts and approaches outlined in the call are familiar to the scientists, some experts in the field, including the multi-actor approach, socio-economic resilience, well-being, gender, and curiosity-driven citizen science initiatives. Developing solutions in response to the call was both an interesting challenge and a valuable opportunity to think critically about how to bring these ideas to life.

In the following sections, we explore how some of the proposed solutions evolved as they were implemented in the TCLs. In the first few sections, we reflect on the impact co-creation had on our implementation process in the context of our community workshops and pilot funds; after which we share a wider reflection on the challenge of completing a project with a 'softer' constructivist, participatory, or critical theory paradigm within a still largely postpositivist landscape of funding and reporting thought.

3.2 A workshop methodology for change

As Chapter 2 relays in more detail, EmpowerUs ran two workshops in each TCL context. The original plan for workshop 1 was to use a traditional workshop design for future scenarios (Nilsson et al., 2017). However, during the initial planning meeting, the academic leads challenged this approach. Many had already facilitated numerous workshops in the TCL regions, including Future Scenario sessions, and expressed concerns that the traditional

methodology was too abstract, contributing to stakeholder fatigue and raising questions about the tangible benefits for communities.

Rather than adhering strictly to the conventional format – developing multiple scenarios based on key drivers and using narrative techniques – we designed an alternative, highly interactive approach. Still, we never let go of the key ideas of scenario planning methods, namely, to stimulate strategic thinking and help overcome limitations by imagining multiple futures (Amer et al., 2013). This adaptation aimed to ensure the meaningful inclusion of local voices while integrating external expertise from the EmpowerUs team.

Similarly, the second set of workshops were also redesigned together with the academic leads and hosts to better reflect the project status at the time in which the workshops were to take place. Originally conceptualised as focusing more specifically on presenting Nature-based Solutions to the communities, these second workshops instead involved local stakeholders in the discussion of possible solutions for the innovative Action Fund based on the analysis developed after the first workshop. This change represented, first, ongoing work with the communities and the understanding that they would want to be involved in debating the project's solutions; and, second, a delay in developing specific Nature-based Solutions for each community through the Eklipse platform, which meant that these solutions were not yet available to be discussed at the workshop.

3.3 Implementing the Action Fund: From Ideas to Pilots

To put the ideas developed during the workshops into practice, we had an Action Fund of €50,000 for each TCL to test pilot solutions across six European TCLs. However, translating ideas into real-life pilots proved to be a significant challenge. In scientific projects, we rarely can be directly involved in testing solutions to the challenges we investigate. As a result, many practical questions arose during and after the workshops, which tend to be more theoretical in nature.

- What can we realistically pay for?
- What is truly empowering?
- How do we decide if there is disagreement between different pilot options?
- Will the EU office approve the costs as eligible? What happens if they do not?

Another complicating factor was that our selection of host organisations as project partners inherently limited our options—the pilot activities had to align with their expertise and capabilities. While our initial ambition was to allow each TCL to decide how to use the funding with minimal restrictions, we quickly encountered boundaries.

Critically, the project coordinator had to negotiate the Action Fund with the EU before signing the Grant Agreement—an unfamiliar and lengthy process for all involved. Striking a balance between ensuring TCLs had the flexibility to implement pilots that met their needs and adhering to EU funding regulations was a complex and often frustrating task. Simply put, while EmpowerUs' bottom-up approach called for as little pre-defined use of the Action Fund, EU regulations required that every euro be traceable and accounted for in advance. The negotiations with the European Commission were both time-consuming and sensitive. Several meetings were held with the project's assigned policy and financial officers, who initially insisted that the entire budget be pre-defined—down to specific activities. However, we explained that this would directly undermine the core logic of EmpowerUs, where pilot interventions were to be co-created with communities based on locally identified needs. While understandable from a fiscal accountability perspective, the initial insistence on pre-allocation of funds posed challenges to our participatory model.

Ultimately, a workable solution was reached: we would maintain flexibility in how the Action Fund was used but include **illustrative examples** of potential expenditures – such as workshops, tools, minor infrastructure, or training initiatives. These examples offered sufficient structure to meet financial accountability standards, while allowing room for communities to co-define what was needed. This compromise preserved methodological integrity while satisfying the EU's fiscal expectations. It also highlighted the deeper tension between bureaucratic systems and participatory approaches, a theme that recurred throughout EmpowerUs.

3.4 Reflections on clashing scientific paradigms

With the onset of the Horizon Europe framework program, the European Commission advanced a stronger emphasis than previous framework programs on the inclusion of social science and the humanities (SSH). Accordingly, more calls focusing explicitly on community perspectives and social processes have been published.

Ours, for example, included specific foci on 'marine environmental connectedness', 'blue spaces and well-being, coastal (eco)tourism and cultural events', and 'the deep impact of human behaviour, culture (including indigenous knowledge and practices) and history (including religion literacy) on all societal innovation and integrated sustainable coastal zone development and management'. The call also indicated that it should 'involve the effective contribution of SSH disciplines'. Since across the SSH, questions of empowerment, culture, history, and connectedness are frequently investigated through constructivist and participatory approaches that recognise the complexity of social realities (as opposed to the positivist or post-positivist pursuit of objective truth), the call's text likewise seemed to suggest that these paradigms should lead the multi-actor networks that successful projects would develop. EmpowerUs' emphasis on co-creation and Leaving No One Behind thus responded directly to this call.

However, as others have reported before, Horizon Europe calls can bear the load of multiple political and scientific needs within the Commission and beyond, resulting in long and not always fully cohesive lists of expected outcomes (Shortall & Meredith, 2025). To this challenge we add one of clashing scientific paradigms. While the core aspects of our original Horizon Europe call aligned with constructivist, participatory, or even critical theory paradigms (i.e., asking for analysis on gender-based socio-economic vulnerability and resilience), some of its objectives conversely seemed aligned with a more 'classical' positivist or postpositivist paradigm assuming the presence of an objective truth – for example, asking that the project should include 'monitoring activities on the performance and impacts of [nature-based] solutions' or even indicating that 'SSH approaches should serve through a multi-actor approach to orient and contextualise coastal STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts and mathematics) activities'. Read from a critical analytical perspective, the phrasing suggested a persistent hierarchical framing, where SSH contributions, while central in theory, were in practice still positioned in supportive roles.

Throughout the negotiation and implementation of EmpowerUs, the tensions arising from the call's opposing paradigms manifested in several ways. For example, despite being repeatedly urged to set up the TCLs as 'bottom-up' initiatives (a preference reiterated at the midterm stage evaluation by the external reviewers), the consortium was initially also

criticised for setting up open-ended Action Funds that the TCLs could utilise at a later point for needs defined first through bottom-up processes. In other words, 'bottom-up', participatory work could only be accepted when wrapped up in the safety of the pre-determined and pre-defined approaches utilised under postpositivist paradigms – an obvious contradiction.

This paradigmatic clash also intensified through the application of the standard criteria and expectations that define Horizon Europe projects as successful in the European Commission's eyes. Even a project as centrally motivated by constructivist, critical theory, and participatory paradigms as EmpowerUs must—to be 'legible' as successful (cf. Scott, 1998)—include forms of 'monitoring' and 'measurement' that follow objective truth paradigms like positivism or post-positivism. EmpowerUs, for instance, was asked to include a way of 'measuring' its success in empowering coastal communities over its duration. This caused a methodological challenge as, importantly, empowerment is neither objective nor singular, and thus cannot be 'measured'. Our project first addressed this challenge by linking Q-sorts with blue justice at the beginning of the project. These were then originally to be followed up by a second set of Q-sorts, but the perceived pressure to deliver 'measurement' led to a last-minute redesign of the second round of Q-sorts in 2025. Instead, we conducted a survey on the success of the pilot initiatives with respect to blue justice for the end of the project. Altogether, our use of Q-sorts and surveys amounted to an innovative compromise to meet both participatory integrity and funder expectations.

Nevertheless, in our experience the challenges of measuring immeasurable social processes (specifically 'empowerment') compounded the impossibility of effectively delivering complex societal change across multiple communities Europe-wide within a 36-month project. Requests of similar magnitude continue to appear in newer SSH Horizon calls. Yet the examples we have recounted from EmpowerUs betray the extent to which SSH approaches may have become more topically and methodologically present in the new Horizon Europe framework program, but SSH paradigms have yet to penetrate as deeply into its structural evaluative processes.

3.5 Take aways

Overall, we have learned that participatory and co-creative approaches can still offer challenges within the existing research funding and administrative landscape. Navigating these challenges is worthwhile but requires continuous flexibility and the willingness and ability to negotiate with both funders and communities. Some of the lessons we learned can be summarised as follows:

- Delivering pre-defined activities in dynamic, participatory contexts proved to require thoughtful adaptation, underscoring the importance of flexibility within funding frameworks.
- Making the project's goals relevant for participating communities is crucial to the ethical and ontological commitment of co-creation projects. Doing so may mean adjusting the project's goals in conversation with participating communities.
- Participatory approaches often clash with administrative expectations of pre-defined outcomes (for example, within EU Funding frameworks). In response, budget flexibility must be intentionally designed and defended. Including illustrative (rather than binding) budget examples can be a pragmatic way to balance accountability with adaptability.

- Project teams should be aware of possible paradigmatic tensions in their projects and think creatively about indicators and methodologies that allow immeasurable processes and phenomena (like “empowerment” or “change”) to be captured and reported. Ultimately, the indicators for success for projects must align with its paradigm (e.g., participatory vs positivist) and awareness of paradigmatic tensions is necessary to navigate contradictory expectations in the implementation.
- Engaging directly and early with policy and financial officers can help create mutual understanding—and occasionally shift institutional expectations.
- Methodological integrity sometimes requires negotiation (with communities, with funders, and with researchers), not just innovation.

EmpowerUs reveals the importance – and the difficulty – of reconciling participatory integrity with bureaucratic demands. Our experience illustrates not only what worked, but where tensions remain in aligning SSH-led innovation with institutional structures.

4. Inclusive methodologies: Experiences from the field

Author: Sunniva Solnør (Ruralis – Institute for Rural and Regional Research) and co-authors of each section below

As detailed in Chapter 2, the Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) serve as the centre of EmpowerUs – including both field activities and serving as spaces where stakeholder participation and co-creation are facilitated. It is within the TCLs that pilot activities, capacity-building efforts, and other key interventions take place. While the methodologies explored in other chapters of this Handbook provide valuable insights, each TCL's unique characteristics have shaped how they have engaged with the communities, how they have designed and implemented pilots as well as how they addressed inclusion and participation in their contexts. This chapter reflects upon some of the practical experiences of doing co-creation, highlighting how inclusive methodologies have been applied in the field from the perspectives of academic leads (and some local hosts). It is not a comprehensive overview of all that has happened within the TCLs but gives some snapshots and examples illustrating important reflections, lessons learned and take aways from doing inclusive methodologies.

The chapter offers a nuanced understanding of how inclusive methodologies have been adapted across different TCL contexts – shedding light on successes, challenges, and valuable insights on the following topics:

- **Eastern Limassol Region, Cyprus:** The role of geography, community structure, historical injustices and local conflict in shaping engagement.
- **Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland:** Supporting local capacity building through skills, knowledge and learning.
- **Åland, Finland:** How local traditional knowledge can be integrated and institutionalised within community initiatives.
- **Træna, Norway:** Balancing community mobilisation with stakeholder fatigue in co-creation efforts.
- **Burgas, Bulgaria:** The importance of respecting stakeholders' agency, interests, and needs in inclusive participation.
- **Cap de Creus, Spain:** The critical role of digital tools in enhancing participation and inclusion.

Every sub-chapter gives a short overview of the TCL pilots (activities or interventions aiming at

reaching sustainable, balanced and inclusive coastal development) before zooming into a deeper exploration into concrete insights and practical reflections on inclusion and co-creation efforts across diverse TCL settings.

4.1 Cyprus TCL: The role of geography, community structure, historical injustices and local conflict in shaping engagement

Author: Maria Hadjimichael, (Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute), (CMMI)

The *Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan* was chosen as the pilot for the Cyprus TCL as a way to strategically think and plan with the local community and other Users of the Sea the future of the coastal space, the legal requirements and restrictions linked to coastal resilience and the ecology of the area. The goal of the pilot is to create a coastal space in the Eastern Limassol Region that can be studied, (re)discovered and re-lived. The plan is a local development strategy, mapping local needs and challenges, and identifies potential for the future of the area, including specific activities or projects put forward by members of the community. The pilot had a second element, where one of the projects included in the strategy was developed further (maturing the project to a stage where the local authority can submit the plans to the competent authorities). This was seen as the best way to give something concrete back to the communities and enable an action that enhances the social, ecological, and economic sustainability of the coastal area. The organisation of the EmpowerUs workshops, as well as additional methods employed, such as online surveys and consultations, informed the plan and integrated inputs from different community members, incorporating ideas for smaller meaningful interventions, community engagement activities, and infrastructure improvements. Moreover, the ‘end product’ from the pilot, if successful, will be a coastal space for all to enjoy.

The approach for inclusivity in the Cypriot TCL was influenced by different parameters, be they political, social or ecological. The physical geography of the area and the proximity of the village from the sea,

the community structure and the lack of organised groups in the area, as well as the demographic changes caused by the displacement of part of the population, posed important challenges. Recognising these complexities, different methodologies were employed to reach more, as well as different people.

- Taking into consideration the **geography**: Though the TCL area is coastal, there is a poor connection between the communities and the sea, as the core of the village and the housing zones are situated at the upper side of a motorway and are approximately 3 kilometres away from the coast. Thus, engaging with people from outside the community who are Users of the Sea was also important. Onsite visits and walks offered a better understanding of how and by whom the coastline is used. Additionally, onsite visits with members of the community and authorities offered a different way to learn about the area and its values.
- Understanding **community structure**: The lack of organised local associations and civil society groups highlighted the need to create the profiles of groups of people who living in the TCL area (i.e. people living on both sides of the motorway, owners of coastal businesses, displaced Greek Cypriots living in the TCL Area, as well as people from different age groups). However, such an exercise is not necessarily enough.
- **Historical injustices** further complicate the engagement process, particularly the displacement of one of the main ethnic communities in Pentakomo. Many displaced individuals retain legal ownership of coastal properties, raising complex questions around access, equity, and inclusion. Furthermore, the political sensitivities within the community are diverse and not homogenous, requiring a careful and nuanced approach. Developing a strategy that acknowledges these historical and political contexts is essential to ensure that all voices – particularly those marginalised by past injustices – are heard and respected.
- **Local conflicts**: Community-led development processes are often vulnerable to external decisions that do not align with locally agreed priorities. For example, during the project, construction of an industrial harbour, serving the marine aquaculture industry, that local communities have been opposing begun, fragmenting the co-decided *Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan* and dividing the community's vision for the future. Though the communities are against the construction of the harbour, their concerns

were not taken into consideration. The commencement of this externally imposed project disrupted the EmpowerUs' methodological approach and deepened the community's existing sense of hopelessness and distrust.

Figure 4.1 Pentakomo coastline, preparations for the marine aquaculture harbour constructions. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael

The stepwise approach used in the EmpowerUs project (Chapter 2) enabled addressing some of the issues. Identifying these challenges early on enabled the researcher to actively search for solutions. For collecting views in the framework of the preparation of the *Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan*, different methodologies were deployed to expand the base of respondents; online surveys, open consultations where live polls sparked discussions, as well as visits at the local primary schools and group discussions with specific groups.

It is important to emphasise that the EmpowerUs project – like any other research and innovation initiative – is not carried out in a vacuum. It unfolds within a specific context shaped by geography, community structures, historical injustices and local conflicts. These contextual factors inevitably raise important questions about power dynamics, participation, and the limits of local influence.

4.2 Ireland TCL: Supporting local capacity building through skills, knowledge, and learning through local host organisation

Authors: Brendan Murtagh, Wesley Flannery and Alex Miller, (Queen's University Belfast)

The Irish TCL aims to develop the volume, scale and diversity of the social enterprise sector as a way of building alternatives to blue growth and increasing commercialisation of the coast. The local partner, Údarás na Gaeltachta, has policy responsibility for economic development, including social enterprises and has support staff, technical assistance and capital budgets to invest across Irish-speaking communities² along the west coast.

However, weak skills and poor economic literacy are barriers to growth, so the pilot focused on strengthening the competence of social enterprises, community organisations and projects that want to diversify their income streams.

Fig 4.2 Ireland TCLs Engagement Workshop in November 2024. Credit: Údarás na Gaeltachta

The Irish TCL has engaged with the leaders of local community development companies, community co-operatives, and social enterprises from across Connemara and the Aran Islands. Through a series of workshops, participants were able to share their insights into the skills and training gaps that exist in the social enterprise sector. The initial concept developed at the first workshop was to create a training programme, but this was reevaluated in the second workshop as development needs varied between size and experience of the social enterprise; the nature of the project; and because most capital developments can take time presenting different challenges at each stage.

This was then redesigned as an integrated *skills, knowledge and learning* programme, which includes bespoke support on finance and digital capacity, best practice visits and an interactive **Technical Manual**. The Manual was co-produced with social enterprises via a survey of approximately 50 businesses across the Gaeltacht; tracking its implementation on three live capital projects that used it over their own development journey; and three interactive workshops with a range of organisations to test the content, resources, case studies and layout. The idea of the Manual is to support users and funders (including Údarás na Gaeltachta) at each stage of delivery rather than in a one-off training programme. It has five parts:

- **Module 1 Assets** focuses on local context, planning systems, and data-driven funding cases. It includes mapping minority groups, socially excluded communities, and their needs.
- **Module 2 Strategy** guides organisations in shaping their project beyond the construction phase, considering objectives, impact on stakeholders, and long-term vision.

- **Module 3 Operations** covers cost-benefit analysis, risk management, and impact evaluation to inform funders, beneficiaries, and the community of progress.
- **Module 4 Governance** explores social enterprise structures, legal status, Board and Director roles, staffing, and necessary expertise for project management.
- **Module 5 Finance** examines revenue sources, financial literacy for staff and Board members, investment readiness, and income diversification.

However, the training manual and related resources have limitations in that they rely on development officers within Údarás to tailor it to the needs of each project. Technical resources need to be both applied and relatable in order to assist projects to get to the next stage of development. The Manual was translated into Irish and emphasised the need to map and target people often left out of local development processes. Benefit mapping and how such groups are engaged in the design of programmes, delivery (as staff, volunteers, Board members) and as service users, are built into project design and evaluation processes. However, achieving social impact and financial sustainability creates an ethical tension and the Manual provides guidance on the participatory systems, structures and reporting systems that ensure that such projects remain anchored in the needs and priorities of local people. Through continued engagement with social enterprise staff, the pilot initiatives have been refined and targeted to best support the needs of local communities. Working with Údarás na Gaeltachta provides the opportunity for long-term impact due to their position as a key institution with capital and revenue resources, skilled staff and support systems to deliver economic change.

4.3 Finland TCL: Documenting the 'undocumented' by reclaiming overlooked traditional coastal local knowledge

Authors: Kristina Svells, (Natural Resources Institute Finland) & Viktor Eriksson, (Fisheries Agency, Åland)

The *Åland Fisheries Appeal*, the Ålandic pilot, evaluates local opportunities for fisheries revitalisation, building on local involvement and co-governance. The pilot initiative, consisting of several connected components, features interactive workshops, community engagement events, and interviews to empower local interest groups, including the fisheries community, water owners, and local residents.

²The term 'Gaeltacht' is used to describe the regions in Ireland in which Irish is the primary spoken language.

Figure 4.3 Workshop 2 in Åland. Credit: Katrina Rønningen

It aims to increase local understanding of owners, and local residents. It aims to increase local understanding of the ecological, cultural, social and economic importance of the fisheries sector in Åland. A key part of this effort has involved uncovering and visualising undocumented and overlooked traditional coastal knowledge about protected areas.

4.3.1 International environmental commitments confront an unprepared Åland

Under the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (COM/2020/380 final), member states must protect 30% of land and sea (10% strictly) by 2030, requiring Åland to strengthen marine protection. These areas should expand the Natura 2000 network and form ecological corridors, prioritising habitats and species listed in the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), Birds Directive (2009/147/EG), and the national red list. The Nature Restoration Law (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991) mandates member states to restore 20% of degraded nature by 2030 and all ecosystems needing restoration by 2050. While Åland, as an autonomous region, is not directly bound by this law, Finland's compliance puts pressure on Åland due to its vast marine territory. Åland hosts unique ecosystems and currently protects 2.4% of land and 3.4% of its marine areas under various regimes, including Natura 2000, IBAs, RAMSAR sites, HELCOM MPAs, seal protection zones, and private conservation initiatives.

In Åland, water areas are divided into three main ownership types: private, common, and public. The current control system leads to a lack of information about the ecological state of these areas and a gap in mapping existing protected zones. Efforts to improve the monitoring system face challenges due to limited interaction between water owners, stakeholders, and the Åland Government. Despite close contact between the national administration and the population, there are few formal channels for engagement. Right now, in this relatively small society, water owners and other stakeholders have no clear way, other than a vague and lengthy

bureaucratic process to maintain an open, ongoing dialogue with the fisheries and environmental authorities.

4.3.2 Mapping & innovative aspects of documenting the undocumented by an online survey

To map unrecognised protections and traditional local knowledge, we conducted an online survey with water commons, receiving 40 responses covering a wide area of water in excess of 1 000 km². The goal was to understand their involvement in water protection measures.

Figure 4.4 Map showing areas of officially protected water areas on Åland together with restricted fishing access (demarcated orange lines). Note: There are numerous additional areas with restricted fishing that are not publicly communicated and therefore very difficult to map. This map is an initial and guiding insight, as mentioned in the text (work-in-progress). Credit: Åland TCL team.

A major challenge was establishing contact. Information was primarily sourced from the Fisheries Agency's registry, focusing on those who had previously engaged with the agency. However, many water commons, especially private, non-registered ones, and owners abroad were not reached due to incomplete records.

The survey revealed many undocumented protection schemes, such as fishing restrictions, with over 80% of respondents reporting protected areas for at least part of the year. Water commons communicate these areas through annual assemblies and recreational fishing licenses sold to tourists and second homeowners for example. Furthermore, analysing data from online sales platforms for fishing licenses provided us with an initial insight into the extent of restricted fishing areas (see Figure 4.4), which typically are protecting seasonal spawning habitats and, in some cases, remain restricted year-round or stay as limited access to local residents and water owners.

Proper documentation is needed to secure their long-term preservation and integration into the ongoing national protection network. Enforcement is also unclear. Åland's Fisheries Law (1956) outlines enforcement but is outdated and open to interpretation. Given Åland's rural nature and distant law enforcement, quick responses are rare, leaving water owners responsible for evidence collection and legal action. The results demonstrate strong community engagement in Åland's water areas. Incorporating this valuable knowledge into the national biodiversity strategy, drafted in 2023, should not be overlooked.

4.3.3 Leaflet – Cherish our fishing waters [Vårda våra fiskevatten]

Water ownership is widely spread on Åland, however, the rights and responsibilities attached to the ownership are not well known. It has to be noticed that being a water owner is not a full-time commitment. Individuals prioritise their time on everyday issues, leading to scarce and selective engagement in water management. However, one essential responsibility for both land and water owners is water management (Landskapslag (1956:39) om fiske i landskapet Åland).

To bridge the information gap, we distributed 15,750 leaflets (see Figure 4.5) covering all households on Åland with the following message:

Figure 4.5 Leaflet received by all Ålandic households 2024. Credit: EmpowerUs

As a water owner, you have an **obligation** under Åland's fisheries legislation to ensure that the water is managed in a way that enables fish populations to be safeguarded. But obligations also bring **opportunities**. We have great opportunities to make local measures that improve the conditions for viable waters because fisheries management is also in many respects environmental management of various kinds. When habitats and watercourses are restored and maintained in good condition, the fish have the opportunity to reproduce and maintain healthy stocks that provide local food, recreational opportunities and jobs.

4.3.4 The fisheries future on Åland relies on traditional local knowledge

Ensuring fair implementation of climate and biodiversity measures is emphasised by major institutions such as the EU and the UN. With the EU's timeline and for the member states to achieve the set goals, public involvement is key, needing trust, resources, and access to both official and traditional local knowledge. However, as the example above illustrates, this will not happen automatically. On Åland, it is evident that if people feel left out, trust will be hard to establish, making long-term commitments or formal protection schemes unlikely, therefore, effective methods for collecting and integrating traditional local knowledge into governance are essential.

4.4 Norway TCL: Balancing inclusion and stakeholder fatigue

Authors: Vida Maria Daae Steiro & Anette Møllersen Bjørnå (Nordland Research Institute)

The Norwegian pilot project, *Hooked on Træna (Hekta på Træna)*, focuses on engaging the local community and co-designing solutions to strengthen residents' connection to the area.

Figure 4.6 Career Day at Træna. Credit: Marta Anna Løvberg

The initiative aims to improve local infrastructure, foster social inclusion, and promote sustainable development. Some of the key activities include mapping of the current transportation system and identification of alternative innovative solutions to improve connectivity, onboarding initiatives to welcome new inhabitants to the community (including interactive workshops, career days and start-up courses), strategy development and implementation to establish Culture Hubs – dedicated spaces for culture activities in the community, promote local food knowledge, and creating coastal pathways.

In an effort to ensure local relevance of the pilot activities and empowerment through co-decision-making in the early stages of the project, the Norwegian TCL in Træna, the TCL team (host and academic lead) established local working groups. While this methodology has been successful in including local community members in decision-making and in research, it has sparked reflections on the ethics around the demand for volunteer time by participants for the sake of inclusive research.

After the two workshops (see Chapter 2), we considered that there was still a need to organise communication and continued co-creation with the local community, especially since neither the host nor the academic lead lived within the specific TCL location. It was also important that the pilot was anchored in the community for it to be empowering, relevant and keep going beyond EmpowerUs' lifetime. To continue co-creation, while spreading the task loads, four working groups were set up according to four general themes that had been identified as challenges through workshop 1: Transport; Onboarding and liveability; Nature and culture; and HUB (community building). The working groups had meetings on expectations, planning, and implementation of pilot activities, and made decisions together with the TCL team, learning digital, research and organisational skills by doing. The working groups consisted of local community members who had expressed their wish to join after having been interviewed, participated in workshop(s) or recruited through advertisements and/or public presentations of the project locally. Dividing the pilot activities into groups according to people's fields of interest and sense of ability to contribute might have opened for a larger breadth of stakeholders to participate. It was done to lower the threshold for participation and recruitment.

We also set up a steering group to ensure a holistic pilot that answered to the local challenges and needs, as well as aligning with the EmpowerUs project's principles and frames. The steering group also discussed the pilot budget and consisted of the host institution, 1-2 participants from each working group, and others, including a county representative.

Information sheets to join the working groups were also translated into Polish to try to recruit migrants, but without luck. Even though migrants did not join the working groups, their input was sought through a different method of engagement. The EmpowerUs project's explicit focus on Leaving No One Behind also led to considerations of inclusion beyond the project lifetime by those who participated in the working groups: One working group arranged a

mini workshop with migrants and refugees living in Træna. This was important for the development of a webpage with information for newcomers moving to Træna, including information they wanted when they moved, or still needed while living there. Furthermore, one working group is planning a career day, and to foster more collaboration and inclusion, schools in municipalities with similar challenges as Træna are invited to join without a cost.

Even though the working groups were important for the implementation and relevance of the pilot, it has raised reflections on whether co-creation might be setting unrealistic expectations for the level of engagement demanded from volunteering participants: What is considered 'real' inclusion in research, when are we actually Leaving No One Behind and what is desired by those volunteering their time to take part? Meetings and planning are time-consuming activities. After some months working together, some participants expressed that it was taking too much time. Some participants were part of several working groups and thus devoted significant time to the project. At the same time, they often held many roles in the local community in general. Some stopped coming to meetings and tasks were thus distributed amongst the fewer, remaining participants. Several participants responded more positively when being asked for their feedback or input on suggestions developed ahead of meetings, rather than collaborating at all steps or taking the lead on an activity. With the concern for stakeholder fatigue, the TCL team suggested to the steering group that they move away from working groups and instead include people on a one-off basis for specific tasks or activities, according to the availability and wants of participants. The response to this suggestion was positive and participants seemed relieved.

If there were unlimited funds for compensating participants in the project, the situation might have been different. The way research is funded, however, requires that participatory projects are open to

Figure 4.7 Træna. Credit: Kathrine Sørgård

adjusting expectations for engagement according to dynamics 'on the ground'. Although deep inclusion was highly relevant and important at some stages and with some people, other stages may require it less, and this needs to be reflected on through open communication with participants.

Thus, inclusion to reach empowerment does not necessarily mean engaging many people deeply all the time, but rather being flexible with methods and following the premises and needs of the participants to restructure inclusion methods along the way. Some methods allow for broad inclusion, shallower engagement, others less inclusion, deeper engagement, while some allow for broad inclusion, deep engagement for a while, but then change over time. The lessons learned from the Norwegian TCL, include the importance of being flexible and sensitive to the time commitment demanded from volunteering project participants, and being aware of the balance between empowerment and stakeholder fatigue that should be considered at every step of the process.

4.5 Bulgaria TCL: Respecting key actors and agencies: Inclusivity as an ongoing relation

Authors: Anna Antonova (Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society, LMU Munich)

The Bulgarian pilot, *Burgas on Three Lakes and One Sea*, integrates cycling and ecotourism activities, ocean literacy, and citizen science initiatives that seek to empower the local community to engage more closely with its surrounding aquatic ecosystem. Key activities include establishing a series of citizen science and engagement initiatives with and for the local community, developing the plans for a future Atanasovsko Lake information centre, and foster greater connectivity between the community and Burgas' three lakes and Black Sea via initiating a series of new cycling and ocean literacy activities and events.

For the Burgas TCL, a key goal in terms of inclusivity was reaching a wider audience than the one the host, the Bulgarian Biodiversity Foundation (BBF), ordinarily engaged with, capturing the attention of a broader set of age groups, backgrounds, and perspectives. In the local context, BBF already has an established role as an advocate for not only ecological or conservation goals, but also environmental justice concerns – a role confirmed through research done for the governance audit (Chapter 5). Expanding the organisation's reach meant also advancing aspects of procedural

justice by providing more members of the wider coastal community with knowledge about local environmental governance, as well as better access to advocacy for their needs. To that end, improving inclusivity in Burgas TCL was approached through expanding the visibility of BBF, its activities, and its messages beyond the existing core of already active and environmentally conscious citizens.

Figure 4.8 BFF, with Radostina Tzenova, Teaching Kindergarten March 2025. Credit: Anna Antonova

Methodologically, the host and academic lead approached this first by designing the pilot as a collection of activities targeting different types of audiences. These included citizen science events open to all, cycling initiatives, and ocean literacy activities, specifically involving children. As part of these efforts, BBF also expanded its reach with audiences through identifying and working with partner organisations and key stakeholders external to the EmpowerUs project, for example Burgas Municipality, a cycling activist, the GreenBurg youth association, a kindergarten group, and so on. In this sense, the availability and agency of individual stakeholders or groups helped shape the direction in which the pilot has been able to widen its inclusivity to a significant extent. Indeed, at least in the Burgas TCL case, inclusivity has evolved through the processes of co-production and co-creation initiated on the coastline as part of the pilot.

Continuing a theme raised by the Norwegian TCL in this chapter of the Handbook, a key insight in these collaborations has been the need to balance the goal of expanding inclusivity with a healthy respect for the time, agency, and own goals of our partners. This can be illustrated through the example of one key activity integrated in the Bulgarian pilot, the 'City Explorers' citizen science initiative. This series of events was chosen with the logic that citizen

science in itself can be empowering for transformative governance change, given how knowledge and power are intricately related (McAteer & Flannery, 2022). In the case of Burgas, popularising public science methods to different citizen groups offered a transformative potential in terms of engaging more people with the local coastal environment, as well as providing a better understanding for its management. To accomplish this, the ‘City Explorer’ events were offered in different locations around the city and focused on different topics (for example looking at critters in the Sea Garden, offering a night walk for identifying bats and other night species, etc.), with participants being taught to enter data into the iNaturalist open online platform.

The initiative has been very successful for BBF in terms of drawing in new types of audiences – its individual events were attended by about 20 people each time, with ages ranging from 6 to 76. At the same time, this success has been highly dependent on the agency of the activity leader, a key stakeholder whose own interests have directed the themes for each ‘City Explorer’ outing and whose passion has made each activity engaging for the audience. This stakeholder’s availability, however, could by no means be taken for granted. Given that the EmpowerUs pilot only takes place over a maximum of eighteen months, and that its budget does not foresee the hiring of additional personnel, the project cannot provide the infrastructure necessary for any job security. Thus, the stakeholder in question could only lead events in the ‘City Explorer’ series when not working full-time. Similarly, other initiatives embedded in the pilot – like the renewal of the avocet trail or the popularisation of new adventure cycling routes around Burgas and the lakes – have depended heavily on the agency of stakeholders whose voluntary unpaid or only part-time compensated involvement cannot be taken for granted. In a project as concerned with empowerment as EmpowerUs, respecting stakeholders’ long-term needs proved to be as central a theme in the pilot’s empowerment goals as the desire to engage with a wider audience.

Thus, the Burgas TCL experience has shown that inclusivity depends not only on the wishes or agenda of the activity leaders. Instead, true inclusivity can only be considered as an ongoing relationship with key stakeholders and actors, taking into account their own agency and showing respect for their own interests and needs. Moreover, inclusivity often goes beyond the (relatively) short-term concerns of a research project and instead depends on long-term goals evident in the community, which a

project can only partly help influence. In that sense, inclusivity needs to be considered as existing within the context of relationships continuing beyond the project’s duration to be truly successful.

4.6 Spain TCL: Connecting communities: seeking inclusion with participatory digital tools

Authors: Sílvia Gómez Mestres & Beatriz Patraca Dibildox, (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), (UAB)

The Spanish pilot, *NaturCap*, is a digital platform co-created in TCL Spain (Cap de Creus) as part of EmpowerUs, which aims to help and empower citizens to contribute to sustainable coastal development in the Cap de Creus region. By involving as many people as possible in activities learning about the ocean (ocean literacy), environmental management, preserving cultural heritage, sharing local community events with residents and visitors, and engaging non-experts in scientific research, the platform seeks to improve people’s understanding of science and the environment. We reflect on this process and how we have integrated citizen science to co-produce the digital platform with the idea that, in the future, it will be a scalable model within the community itself and replicable and linkable for other coastal communities.

Combining different approaches has been crucial to favour participation in the TCL. During the workshops, we utilised discussion tables, affinity diagrams, and scoring matrices. Although these methods proved highly effective, they required considerable time and resources from the local community and the research team. A ‘digital bridge’ was used between the face-to-face sessions and a WhatsApp group was used to facilitate collaboration, feedback, and inclusion, enabling broader participation and overcoming logistical barriers. While WhatsApp was effective as a collaborative tool, it brought some challenges, such as the lack of a formal structure to the platform or the uneven participation, which, while allowing voices to be added to the discussion, also meant that others were overshadowed because the digital route is not equally helpful or practical for all.

The digital messaging platform was beneficial for creating community because, apart from the co-creation process, it also served as a space to share news and events from the stakeholders themselves. Still, we found that on some occasions, these announcements were not always aligned with

the set objectives. Despite this, we opted for this organic growth of the group to generate a sense of freedom of expression. Beyond the pilot project itself, the opportunity to create a community is invaluable as it strengthens relationships of trust and creates a space for exchange.

The methodology employed by NaturCap improves inclusion and empowerment in the Cap de Creus region by designing processes that integrate diverse actors at each stage of decision-making and knowledge creation. From its conception in the first workshops, challenges were aligned with possible solutions for the co-design of NaturCap. In this last phase, concrete mechanisms were used, such as inviting divers to send photographs documenting the challenges of ocean literacy, thus transforming their personal experiences into scientific data or inviting Cap de Creus Natural Park workers to contribute to clarifying the regulatory frameworks of the area. Academic scientists provide methodological guidance, unifying criteria, and facilitating knowledge transfer between disciplines and stakeholders. NaturCap will provide scientific data for subsequent collection, analysis and the development of new research arising from these findings.

Figure 4.9 NaturCap, <https://www.naturcap-empowerus.eu/en>

The use of MIM (Mobile Instant Messaging) attempted to ensure active participation in decision-making processes, even for those who could not attend some parts of the project in person. However, we were mindful of the potential exclusion of individuals with limited digital literacy. We incorporated User Experience (UX) design principles, such as intuitive navigation, responsive interfaces, and multilingual options, to make the platform accessible to a broader audience. Navigation tools and gamified environment features were also integrated to improve engagement and inclusivity. Honesty in the use and management of the materials by the researchers and clear communication about the use of the data ensured that participants felt valued and informed throughout the process.

The project methodology considered ethical issues at various stages by prioritising equity by involving all stakeholders in co-creation processes and by collectivising decision-making. Transparency of the process was ensured through informed consent, constant communication about resolutions emerging from discussions, and how data would be managed.

4.7 Conclusion

This chapter has provided insights into the practicalities of doing inclusive methodologies across diverse contexts. It has highlighted the complexities and nuances involved in fostering inclusion and participation, revealing that these processes are neither automatic nor straightforward. Rather, they require continuous negotiation, adaptation, and sensitivity to the contexts, people, and ecologies involved.

A key takeaway is that inclusion is shaped by the structural frames of the project itself (see Chapter 3). These frames set the conditions for how inclusion can occur and influence the possibilities and limitations of participation.

Importantly, inclusion does not happen organically, but it requires continuous and intentional effort. Assuming that people are readily available and eager to participate overlooks the realities of limited time, competing commitments, and the practical constraints of voluntary or part-time involvement. This highlights how co-creation processes may set unrealistic expectations for participant engagement and underscores the need to balance inclusion with sensitivity to stakeholder fatigue – something exemplified by the Norwegian TCL.

Ensuring that inclusion efforts are anchored in the needs and priorities of local communities is vital. Here, the role of local hosts has proven to be invaluable. Across the TCLs, the local institutions have provided essential anchoring points, fostering networks, building trust, and aligning project goals with community needs. For instance, in Ireland, working with the Irish language has been an important strategy for fostering inclusion and addressing historical exclusions. Such locally rooted efforts not only enhance the legitimacy of the project but also help bridge gaps between external researchers and local communities. Flexibility in methodological approaches is also crucial. Inclusive methodologies must be adapted to the evolving needs and circumstances of participants. As seen across the TCLs, engagement often depends on the willingness to modify methods in response to local conditions. This adaptability is essential in

dynamic environments where external pressures or local conflict – such as the socio-political climate in Cyprus – can significantly affect participation and engagement.

Additionally, the availability and agency of stakeholders shapes the scope of inclusion. Highlighted, for example, by Bulgaria TCL: people's capacity to participate cannot be taken for granted; it depends on their time, resources, and existing commitments. Thus, there is a need to balance the aspiration for broad inclusion with respect for the individual agency and priorities of those involved. Another critical dimension of inclusion is the reciprocal flow of knowledge between stakeholders. Inclusive methodologies require an up-and-down exchange of ideas that recognises and values

local expertise. This relational aspect of inclusion highlights the importance of creating spaces for mutual learning and knowledge-sharing, such as in the Spanish TCL.

Finally, this chapter underscores that inclusivity is an ongoing relational process that goes beyond individual projects and requires attention to the diverse and evolving needs, interests, and capacities of participants, as highlighted in the Bulgarian TCL. Inclusion does not occur in isolation but is embedded within and is affected by broader social, political, and economic contexts. Recognising these complexities is crucial for developing and doing methodologies that are not only inclusive in intention but also in practice.

Part III: METHODS AND METHODOLOGIES FOR SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Figure III. The Ocean Literacy Activity Getting to Know my Coastline with Moni-Monagrouli Ayioi Anargyroi Primary School. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael

Dones de Mar, Cap de Creus Credit: Sílvia Gomez Mestres

5. Governance Audit

Authors: Brendan Murtagh, Wesley Flannery and Alex Miller (Queen's University Belfast)

5.1 Introduction

In a project concerned with empowerment, the distribution, nature and effects of spatial policies and how they are implemented is a critical starting point. EmpowerUs is about how coastal communities have been marginalised as a result of blue growth and the regulatory changes that affect their traditional industries, sustainability and ways of working. Assets traditionally seen as commons such as fishing stocks, beaches, seaweed, salt, coastal views and land itself have been revalorised, often for private economic development that has bypassed or excluded local people. There are, therefore, various ways in which they experience a loss of control, a sense of alienation and a shift in their traditional notions of a maritime place identity. Understanding what is happening in such circumstances involves evaluating who is driving change; the role of policy and institutions in such processes; where and how decisions are taken that impact places; and the extent to which decision-making arenas are open to scrutiny and influenced by coastal communities. This chapter examines the Governance Audit as an approach for mapping the institutional, actor and policy environment as a context for understanding change and as a way of directing the pilot intervention.

Figure 5.1 Panoramic view of Llançà, Spain. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

5.2 An institutional approach

There are different ways in which power is explained and evaluated, but here we are concerned with understanding what is happening across six very different spatial communities. In order to appreciate the wider implications for the coast, EmpowerUs developed a comparative empirical framework for mapping various forms of power and their implications for counter strategies, using the pilot intervention in each Transition Coastal Lab (TCL). Healey (1996; 2018), for example, is concerned

with spatial communities and how they relate to stakeholders with (political, economic, regulatory and so on) power; decision-making arenas, both formal and informal; the distributional implications of policy processes in their development and delivery; ways of shaping, discursively, problems and perceived solutions; and how we value and measure change and from whose perspective. In short, we need to unpack the various dimensions that constitute power and how it is enacted across policies, programmes and decisions in communities. Healey proposed a methodology for implementing and evaluating the potential of such an agenda empirically. Her *Institutional Audit* breaks down the circumstances, settings and routines through which various stakeholders have a say in policymaking, in turn, offering a way of understanding power and related strategies of empowerment. We broaden and adapt this framework to focus on the governance of the coast, with a particular emphasis on the capacity of local communities to respond as tested out in the TCL pilots.

The key propositions of the **Institutional Audit** approach are (based on Healey, 1996; 2018):

- Who has a stake in the development of regions; how far are these stakeholders actively represented in current governance arrangements?
- In what arenas does discussion currently take place? Who gets access to these? Do they inter-relate issues from the point of view of everyday life and the business world? Or do they compartmentalise them for the convenience of policymakers?
- Through what routines does discussion take place? Do they make room for diverse ways of knowing and valuing representation among stakeholders or do particular styles dominate?
- Through what policy discourses are problems identified, claims for attention prioritised and information and new ideas filtered? Do these recognise the diversity among stakeholders or again, do dominant styles win out?
- How is agreement reached, how are such agreements expressed in terms of commitments and how is agreement monitored? Is it easy for those who are critical to the implementation of the agreement to escape from the commitments?

The Institutional Audit is a conceptual framework that, as Healey (1996; 2018) emphasises needs to be applied to particular institutional contexts, spatial problems and regions. In taking it forward in EmpowerUs, an emphasis was placed in the *governance landscape* and relations of political, economic and regulatory power. Hence, it provided a basis for the Governance Audit, designed with partners, as a standard reporting template across the six TCLs.

5.3 Designing the Governance Audit

The Governance Audit was prepared as a guiding framework to organise data collection, policy reviews and analysis across the six TCLs. A standardised methodology was set out in a Workbook and used across the TCLs. The Workbook was outlined and discussed in a baseline group meeting with TCL leads and local partner organisations and refined and developed after discussions with each area. It set out guidance, explanations, questions, and methods relevant to the five tasks, based on Healey's initial audit but in the context of the applied Governance Audit, looked at: Stage 1 Understanding the Community; Stage 2 Stakeholder Mapping; Stage 3 Evaluating Policy Discourses; Stage 4 Mapping Structures; Stage 5 Understanding Policy Processes. The bullet points below describes data gathering methods used to understand the policy context and how this constrains or opens possibilities for community action.

- A desk-based study of national, regional, and local policies, plans, programmes, and relevant legislation. The scope also involved regulatory processes, including Environmental and Strategic Environmental Planning assessments, zoning regulations and planning appeals cases.
- Research studies and evaluations into the economy, labour market structure, population change and community infrastructure.
- The grey literature is important in terms of press and social media reports, campaign material by Users of the Sea, such as on depopulation, environmental controversies, and objector protests.
- A series of semi-structured in-depth interviews with stakeholders across government departments and agencies, local government representatives, politicians, NGOs, businesses, local people, and Users of the Sea.
- Different TCL research approaches involved participant observation and ethnographic

methods, especially across community meetings and events as well as several visits to better understand the area and contested sites and related projects within it.

5.4 Implementing the Audit

5.4.1 Stage 1: Stakeholder mapping

Following Healey, a stakeholder is any person or agency with a material or emotive stake in the use, development, or management of the territory (land, sea and air) in a way that impacts on the local community. These vary and each holds a different stock of power, resources and legitimacy. The University of Kansas *Community Toolbox* set out a method for Identifying and Analysing Stakeholders and Their Interests (<https://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/participation/encouraging-involvement/identify-stakeholders/main>). They see *Primary* stakeholders as people or groups that stand to be directly affected, either positively or negatively, by the actions of an agency, institution, or organisation. In coastal communities, the state, regulatory authorities, especially in planning as well as private developers reflect this group.

Secondary stakeholders are people or groups that are *indirectly* affected by decisions so for example, a hotel development might create jobs in a direct way, but also cause indirect impacts on congestion, noise and quality of the environment. *Tertiary* stakeholders are those who may be marginal to decision-making but play a role or might be enabled to play a stronger role in local activism. They may presently have little or no formal power, though they hold the potential for future involvement. The outcome from this analysis is a stakeholder map, which in turn sets the context for the analysis of policies, strategies, plans and key decisions of the respective stakeholders and related organisations.

5.4.2 Stage 2: Mapping policy processes and the enactment of power

It is important to recognise the distinct types and sources of power or what we might think of as *influence* to deliver the change we want to see. In this stage, it is important to look at the resources the stakeholder making the policy has (these might be financial, legal or regulatory); the legitimacy with which they speak (are they elected politicians, civic society representatives, bureaucrats, technical specialists and so on); and how open is a policy and decisions to public scrutiny (do local people have a chance to influence outcomes and how). In EmpowerUs, we can see a number of policy styles, so there is not one approach but different ways in which resources are allocated and a range of

opportunities for communities to influence how they are delivered. As an illustration you can map such types including, for example:

- There are clearly *Pluralist politics* which involves liberal democratic forms of voting for elected representatives who can challenge, advocate and deliver change in and for (as well as against) communities.
- *Market rational power*, evidenced by blue growth regimes often dominate, displacing traditional, indigenous and locally owned firms and labour markets.
- *Techno-rational and bureaucratic decision-making* often privilege rules-bound, professionalised and rational policy processes (particularly in land use planning), that often exclude or limit access by NGOs and community organisations.
- *Semi-judicial arenas*, including public inquiries and planning appeal hearings, can protect landscapes and natural resources but also enable new forms of extractive economic development.
- Local people exert agency through formal and informal governance arrangements, including *special committees*, campaigns, and protests in order to influence policy, shape development, and build coalitions to effect change.

5.4.3 Stage 3: Understanding discourse

We can map the policy style but it is also important to get beyond the formal description of a particular approach to look at how it is developed, who appears to be speaking most, how assumptions are made, especially about spatial communities and the narratives that are used to privilege certain outcomes and stakeholders (identified in the first mapping exercise). Rydin (2003; 2023) emphasised the centrality of discourse in shaping planning policy, decision making and priorities for investment. It is interesting to see how blue growth logics are embedded in key documents and official plans. Here, we used Rydin to understand the nature of the policy discourse and how it is rhetorically represented. There are, of course, other ways of implementing a discourse analysis, but it is useful to have a framework that is appropriate to the built and natural environment and related *spatial* communities. We can see, across marine policies as identified in the 6 TCLs:

- *Logos*, in that it is logical and rational to follow a particular policy line;

- *Pathos* such as catastrophising the challenges of coastal communities and how they need to change; and
- *Ethos*, which asks more fundamental questions about who the coast is for and how we get, for example, a more embedded and inclusive form of local growth.

Mapping out what rhetorical devices are being used in policies, investment programmes and counter campaigns is important in understanding how (economically or politically) powerful actors win out against less well-resourced stakeholders as described at the start of the audit. Drawing on EmpowerUs then, we can see:

- Many blue growth policies are coded as **logical**, even necessary, to avoid economic crises. Old industries in fishing, extraction and farming are declining, and we need innovation, new investment and ‘growth’ to rescue the most vulnerable coastal communities. Such growth can displace local voice in policy discourses that are often rendered as negative, unwilling or incapable of change or are politically conservative. The discourse, both justifies the need for new forms of growth, at the same time as it (often needs to) silences discordant voices.
- In this respect, communities and NGOs often rely on the **ethics** of decisions and how they impact communities, ecosystems, and the physical environment. We see this in ideas of *blue justice* and *right to the sea* although, because policy styles and structures (see arenas next in the Audit) really drive what is implemented, such protest alone can be limited.
- *Pathos* is also widely used in climate crises’, local impacts, loss of resources and the need for urgency in acting. We see this in justifications for offshore renewable energy in which bypassing or marginalising coastal communities is justified by a wider (often non-specific but global) climate crisis.

5.4.4 Stage 4: Evaluating decision-making arenas

The fourth element is about *where* decisions that affect the development of the coast are taken. This is critical as the scale at which decisions are taken can be better understood in the context of the ability of local stakeholders including the community to act. One of the consistent themes is the degree of *rescaling*, in which policies, capital investments (especially in infrastructure) and

planning decisions are removed from the local level to regional and especially national bodies. This restructuring is critical in a European context as EU Directives and funding programmes increasingly shape the degree of agency communities can exercise in highly sensitive coastal environments. Disempowerment can simply involve removing decisions and accountability from influence (or interference), especially if they are critical to national blue growth objectives. In turn, the EmpowerUs pilots looked at a range of interventions to strengthen participative democracy, community capacity building, citizen science, collective ownership models, and development of local assets to counter the complexity of this multilevel marine governance arena.

5.4.5 Stage 5: Measuring change

The final element of the Governance Audit is to set out a way of understanding whether the intervention has had an impact on people’s lives, especially the poorest and most excluded. Chapter 6 sets out an analysis of a Realist Evaluation design, which focuses on the pilot interventions and their potential to empower communities, voluntary organisations, state agencies, and community businesses to effect change in their area. The desired change is about strengthening empowerment, which might involve targeting marginal groups and interests in local development; strengthening environmentally responsible tourism; building economic alternatives for the coast; diversifying community engagement in local planning; and better use of community assets. The point is to understand how stakeholders, including the complex identities embedded in *communities*, are better off as a result.

5.5 Limits to the use of the audit

The Governance Audit is a framework that needs to be personalised to the area, sectors, and challenges in each case. It has analytical and empirical limitations that must be acknowledged and three are especially important:

- First is the treatment of power and powerlessness. Powerlessness results from a mix of often interlocking processes, including access to the labour market, denial of citizenship rights, unequal pay and so on that are often built into neoliberal blue growth regimes. In other words, the stakeholders are not equal in their ability to change policies or resource allocation decisions in the way that institutional theories suggest they might.

- Second, it is difficult to define stakeholders or assume that all stakeholders are visible as blue growth has created uneven spatial, economic, and social effects. Migrant workers can often dominate a seasonal and precarious labour market (in tourism, fish processing and extractive industries) and their very lack of permanence and weak economic position reduce their visibility as a stakeholder.
- Third, it assumes policy processes and arenas are open for analysis, but there are often closed and corporatist ways in which decisions are made (especially around property development) where the public does not know what is happening, let alone how to influence change.

5.6 Conclusions

The Governance Audit is a way of understanding policy processes and their implications for coastal development. It does not capture the complexity of power relations in the coast but helps to describe how places are developed, who and what is prioritised and how local people are positioned within a wider regulatory, policy, administrative and political framework. This has helped think through how pilot interventions then support the capacity of communities to act within a given structural context. By identifying common pressures, shaped by blue growth policies and how they are organised, it highlights the need to understand these processes beyond specific coastal areas and map their effects across maritime European communities.

Bulgaria. Credit: Ivo Danchev

6. Realist Evaluation: Understanding real-world impacts

Authors: Brendan Murtagh, Wesley Flannery and Alex Miller (Queen's University Belfast)

6.1 Introduction

This chapter looks at how we measure ideas of power and empowerment in policy interventions across coastal communities. The EmpowerUs project uses a Living Lab approach, meaning it tests out new ideas in real-life settings to help local people tackle challenges brought on by coastal change. Working with a local host and an Empowerment Action Fund, the Transition Coastal Labs (TCL) have supported a mix of pilot projects including the development of community plans; support for social enterprises and commons ownership; advocacy campaigns; community mobilisation and engagement; preserving heritage; and promoting responsible tourism through technology. The challenge is to deliver, and simultaneously learn, from the intervention – did it work, what failed, were there barriers and what can be scaled or replicated? To understand this in *real-time*, requires a different approach to evaluation and especially *learning* for and by the communities impacted by the pilot. While long-term results will emerge later, a **Realist Evaluation** design allows us to understand how implementation is going; to make adjustments and recalibrate the pilot; and to embed ‘measurement’ in a more interpretative understanding of the people and places we work with (HM Treasury, 2020).

6.2 Realist Evaluation

The questions asked in traditional evaluation designs are usually centred on ‘does this have an impact, how much was done or what efficiencies were achieved’, but in Realist Evaluation, it is ‘what works for whom in what circumstances?’ (Pawson & Tilley, 1997). Realist philosophy argues that an intervention works (or does not) because actors, and here we are especially concerned with place-based communities, make particular decisions in response to the intervention (in the case of EmpowerUs, the TCL pilot project). The **Context** of power shapes what they are able to do in certain (TCL) conditions, in which the pilot creates a **Mechanism** to achieve more inclusive **Outcomes**, primarily the capacity of local people to act. Thus, Pawson and Tilley propose a ‘Context-Mechanism-Outcome’ (CMO) statement as the basis for evaluating change. However, in EmpowerUs we are also concerned with a specific **Intervention** in the form of the pilot. Punton et

al. (2022) adapt the approach to introduce an additional element to the CMO configuration, to give the formulation C+I+M=O (as set out in the text box below). Because they are happening in real-time, we *hypothesise* these relationships, and it is this that we test out by delivering the pilot as an Intervention.

Box 6.1 Realist evaluation

CIM=O describes how understanding power and empowerment sets a **Context (C)** for a particular pilot **Intervention (I)** that sets off **Mechanisms (M)** which, in turn, create various **Outcomes (O)**:

- **Context:** In what context will the intervention work? In-depth interviews, baseline mapping and the Governance Audit (see chapter 5) form the basis of our understanding of the policies, laws, institutions and actors that shape the coast.
- **Intervention** is about the pilot enabled by the investment with the local host or what the pilot will actually do and how it will work. These are not Mechanisms but generate a range of processes that enable actions, which the evaluation then aims to focus on.
- **Mechanisms** are what we prioritise by focusing on the processes that are set off by the pilot in a way that strengthens community power, understood as a capacity to act.
- **Outcomes:** In what ways will the defined (coastal) community have greater power to cope, resist and transform the conditions set out in the Context?

6.3 Establishing the context

The first step in realist evaluation is to understand and map the Context. This involves evaluating the local policy and regulatory environment and how government and governance relate to place communities in each case. There are a number of conceptual frameworks for doing this and in EmpowerUs we used a Governance Audit (see Chapter 5). This maps out who has a stake in the use and development of the coast (communities, state planners, private developers, fishers and so on);

evaluates the policies and programmes that impact on places; identify where and how decisions are taken (are they open and easy to challenge or closed and hard to access); the discourses that different stakeholders use to pursue their aims; and how we understand and measure the effects of development on coastal communities and in particular the most excluded and isolated *people*. By bringing this analysis together across the European coast, EmpowerUs has identified common *contexts* about the way in which policies (tourism, energy, fishing and so on) privilege certain forms of economic growth, often at the expense of local people.

6.4 Interventions and Mechanisms?

Mechanisms are what realist evaluations are primarily interested in. In EmpowerUs, academics have worked with a local host and communities to co-produce an intervention that aims to help local people address development pressures and improve their lives. These have been funded and work with host agencies (state body, development agency, NGO and so on) that have the capacity to make change happen in each TCL. What we need to focus on next, then, is to see how these Interventions create Mechanisms that provide communities with greater power to act in a given Context. But such Mechanisms may not work, be suited to local community groups or align with coastal challenges. In Ireland, the ‘hypothesis’ was that social enterprises would want a certain type of support, including a structured training programme on areas such as business planning, how to manage finances, recruiting staff and so on. However, the three workshops conducted as part of the EmpowerUs TCL, showed that this was not a valid assumption as social enterprises did not want another training programme. Instead, they wanted a resource that could help them throughout the development of their project. For capital developments, such as a community museum or backpackers’ hostel, this could take 2 years and a one-off training intervention would have limited effects. The pilot intervention then changed to develop a technical manual to guide community businesses through the development process, with templates, guidance and tasks related to their project. This emphasises the potential of the Realist Evaluation to redirect implementation in more meaningful and engaged ways.

Box 6.2 Example from Ireland

In Ireland, the Governance Audit showed that blue growth along the west coast, especially tourism and renewable energy had negative effects on traditional Irish-speaking *Gaeltacht* areas. The *Context* then, is that much of the investment was extractive by taking money and resources out of the area with often limited local multiplier effects within the community economy. The local host, Údarás na Gaeltachta, is the economic development authority for Irish-speaking areas and the *Intervention* invested in social enterprise capacity building in a coastal community in the west of Ireland. We *hypothesise* that social enterprises would generate and capture wealth locally and offer an alternative to private-led development. The *Mechanism* was to strengthen the social economy via a technical assistance programme centred on training. However, the evaluation showed that social enterprises did not need or want a formal training programme but more bespoke and point-of-time technical assistance; that larger social enterprises needed specialist support in finance and digital capacity; and that *learning* (how to do economic development) was more important than *knowledge* (what is a social enterprise). The pilot then changed to more specialist *Mechanisms* that involved a technical manual; supported by field officers and seed funding from Údarás na Gaeltachta; specialist programmes on finance and digital capacity; and field visits to learn from other coastal communities, especially in Scotland which has a comparatively advanced social enterprise sector. The *Outcome* is the same – a stronger social economy – but the *Mechanism* has changed in response to the experience of delivering what was hypothesised after the baseline Governance Audit was completed.

Figure 6.1 Trá an Dóilín (Coral Strand) in Carraroe, the Connemara Gaeltacht area, Ireland TCL. Credit: Kristen Ounanian

6.5 Outcomes and process tracing

Evaluating the utility of a particular Mechanism involves Process Tracing, described by BetterEvaluation (n.d.), as a way to ‘assess the strength of evidence for concluding that an intervention has contributed to changes that have been observed or measured’. This means, over the life of the pilot, relating the Mechanism to particular Outcomes. This should focus on isolating the contribution of the Mechanism to the Outcome, expressed as a hypothetical relationship (as in the case above in the Ireland TCL). In turn, it means identifying and measuring other possible contributory factors. Process tracing in the form of longitudinal surveys, participation with the groups and diary records all help to differentiate causal effects and what this tells us about the efficacy of the support programme. A Workbook, bespoke to each TCL, was developed and focused on the Mechanisms and how they would impact the community’s ability to mobilise in response to their respective context. This also agreed data gathering methods, supported by structured meetings with the evaluation leads to produce a story of the pilot, in the form of a common log, over time and in a consistent way.

6.6 Methods and data gathering

The type of data gathered (and recorded in the workbook) is, of course, bespoke to each programme intervention. This often involves a mixed methods approach, but as we are interested in ideas of power, there is a stronger emphasis on qualitative methods to enable tacit knowledge, informal groups and different ways of speaking to be included in the evaluation design. As the text box below shows, the EmpowerUs TCLs used secondary data, quantitative surveys, in-depth interviews, focus groups, anthropological observations and participatory workshops to situate the intervention in the lived experience of the community. It is the case that more interpretative qualitative methods were at the core of empirical strategies because it was understanding processes of change and *causality* that was the central feature of the approach.

Box 6.3 Methods and data gathering

- Quantitative surveys were deployed with sectoral groups such as tourists, fishers, Users of the Sea, local people, community groups and social enterprises.
- A number recorded the leverage that the pilot achieved such as financial contributions by the local host, benefits in kind such as technical support or use of facilities, volunteer effort and so on.
- The numbers of people attending consultation events, using an app and web interface, attending training and participating in plan-making demonstrate the importance of understanding levels of participation and volume effects.
- The interviews that helped form the Governance Audit (chapter 4) and the Q-method (chapter 7) have been revisited to see how key stakeholders or a subset within them, think about the pilot and its implication for the TCL, policy and practice.
- Other outcomes, including unintended effects, were revealed in focus groups, participatory methods and anthropological approaches that involved being embedded in TCL areas over time.

6.7 Limitations and barriers

Realist evaluations are criticised because they focus too much on processes rather than Outcomes. The key question – are communities achieving a better life – is largely unanswered. We cannot say whether the pilot interventions have created more local power or resisted blue growth pressures, but we can better understand that Mechanisms either work or do not in particular circumstances of disempowerment. It is a conceptual model that makes assumptions about diverse communities and invites simple causal analysis when, in reality, change is far more complex and contingent. It is also data-hungry and demands an explicit political understanding of the Context and the Intervention. Identifying how and why communities are disempowered is itself a loaded concept, especially given the economic and environmental changes facing the coast. What is *real* to a community is not the same as to a property developer, politician or planner. Placing Realist Evaluation within a more explicit understanding of power is important, which is why mapping power as it relates to policy processes in the Governance Audit (Chapter 5), is critical.

6.8 Lessons and implications

Realist Evaluation techniques are not suited to every circumstance and are not better or worse than more conventional designs. It depends on the interventions, questions we are interested in and the extent to which we can learn from delivery. A number of implications for its use stem from EmpowerUs:

- The approach is especially important in assessing the effects of real-time interventions when the outputs or Outcomes will not be known or are uncertain.
- It is important to keep the focus on the unit of analysis. It is not the activity or Outcome but the causal relationship between the intervention and the change we intend and in particular on the *Mechanisms* that work or do not work.

- It should not be thought of as a separate methodological category but works effectively with a range of empirical strategies and ontologies. Clearly, the emphasis is on interpreting relationships and here methodology has tended to focus on qualitative techniques, although not exclusively.
- Context is critical and investment, time and resources in locating the problem is important, especially where this is complex, disputed and conflictual, including our understanding of power and how it is used or accessed.
- Context is also important in reflecting the contested nature of community and understanding the different, hard-to-reach, often silent or marginalised people who live in every place.

7. Q methodology – exploring local views of empowerment

Authors: Salina Spiering and Cecilie Bratt (Nordland Research Institute)

Q-methodology is an approach that combines quantitative and qualitative techniques to systematically study what different groups of people think about particular issues (Stephenson, 1935; Watts & Stenner, 2012). In EmpowerUs, we wanted to understand how empowered participants in the EmpowerUs coastal communities perceived themselves at the outset of the project and throughout the project as the experience with the pilot developments emerged. By engaging with different Users of the Sea – i.e. those living in the six coastal communities across Europe where the project's Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) were based – the Q method offers valuable insights into shared perspectives and differences.

co-creative, research practices. We conclude this chapter with a number of recommendations for other projects that use the Q methodology to assess baseline perspectives on empowerment in coastal communities.

7.1 How did we apply the Q methodology in EmpowerUs?

By combining quantitative and qualitative research methods, the Q method makes it possible to comprehensively explore the different perceptions and opinions – also known as discourses – that exist among different groups of people. The aim is to understand common and different viewpoints amongst the participants; not how many people hold a particular view. This is done using a common set of statements. The material is then used to consistently compare how groups of people think about something. This also means that it is possible to conduct a case study using only one participant, however the number of participants is usually higher.

A Q study usually entails a four-step process to assess changes in perceptions on a given topic:

1. Development of Q statements
2. Identification of participants
3. Q sorting exercises
4. Quantitative and qualitative Q-analysis

In EmpowerUs, a Q-survey was conducted at the beginning of the project to provide a baseline understanding of empowerment perceptions. As a first step, we collaboratively developed the statements for the Q survey. To make the term 'empowerment' more understandable, we drew on Blue Justice theory (Bennett et al., 2021; Jentoft et al., 2022; Blythe et al., 2023), which frames social justice through recognition, procedure, and distribution: recognitional justice addresses whether communities have the knowledge to access institutions and governance; procedural justice concerns their ability to participate in decision-making processes; and distributional justice focuses on fair outcomes and equitable resource allocation. Participants were then asked to sort the statements into a forced distribution grid indicating how much they agreed, from 'most disagree with' to 'most agree with'.

Figure 7.1 Beach in Cyprus. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael

To establish a baseline understanding of perceptions of empowerment across the six TCLs, we conducted a Q investigation in the early stages of EmpowerUs. This baseline aimed to provide insights into shared beliefs and subjective experiences of empowerment prior to the various EmpowerUs interventions.

In the following chapter we start by briefly presenting Q methodology as a method to assess stakeholder perceptions. We then reflect on the strengths and challenges of using the Q methodology in EmpowerUs. We highlight its ability to reveal diverse perspectives while requiring adaptations to address language barriers, resource constraints and the complexities of measuring empowerment, and share these insights to foster collective learning and promote inclusive,

Recognitional justice	Procedural justice	Distributional justice
1	5	9
My stakes/rights in the environment are recognised.	I have the opportunity to meaningfully participate in environmental decision-making.	The impacts of environmental management decisions are fairly distributed.
2	6	10
The historic and cultural links between my community and the sea are recognised by broader society.	I know who to contact when clashes of interest occur in relation to decision-making processes.	Government distributes resources in a way that makes it possible to live well along the coast.
3	7	11
All economic sectors in our community are valued equally.	Conflicts between different users of the sea are solved fairly when they arise.	The benefits of blue growth/coastal economy are shared fairly across communities.
4	8	12
Minorities are a significant resource to the local community.	My identity does not prevent my participation in local decision-making.	Blue growth also benefits vulnerable groups (health/poverty/insecurity).
13		
Life is better in the city-centres.		

Table 7.1: Statements for the Q-survey

Between 6-20 participants were selected per location to ensure qualitative representativeness in a range of opinions, keeping the Leaving No One Behind principle in mind. In total, 63 people completed the Q survey. Out of these, 36 % were women. In parallel to sorting statements into the predefined diagram the participants were interviewed and encouraged to reflect explicitly on why they chose to place the statements the way they did.

The first step of the Q-sort analysis was conducted using a free online quantitative sorting tool called the PQ Method (<https://qmethod.org/resources/software/>). This reduced the unique viewpoints to a few concise and general perspectives – so-called factors. In the second step of the analysis, qualitative information from the interviews was used to supplement and contextualise the various groupings of interests generated using the quantitative tool.

The Q sorting results revealed patterns by showing intersubjective arrangements of shared beliefs

among people. These patterns indicated the degree of similarity or dissimilarity in individual perspectives.

This approach has provided a structured analysis of participants' perceptions of blue justice and empowerment at the outset of the project, which helped identify prevailing perspectives and informed subsequent EmpowerUs activities.

Figure 7.2 Træna, Norway. Credit: Ida Glørstad Jørgensen

7.2 Some strengths and challenges

7.2.1 Decision for Qs – what's the rationale?

Q methodology was selected for its ability to reveal patterns in subjective opinions, making it particularly suited for understanding the perspectives of various stakeholders and making it a promising tool for exploring complex and context-dependent concepts like empowerment in coastal communities. However, measuring empowerment proved a notable challenge as it is inherently subjective, varying by context and individual experience. Capturing empowerment by using structured statements required careful consideration of cultural and linguistic nuances. For instance, the method's focus on ranking pre-defined statements could unintentionally constrain participants' ability to express nuances in their lived experiences. This challenge highlighted the tension between structure and flexibility in research methods aimed at inclusivity.

7.2.2 Statement development phase

Developing the statements for the Q sorts was both a critical and demanding phase, as the quality of the statements directly influenced the study's inclusivity and validity. The process involved iterative discussions among project team members across the six TCLs and work package leads.

In this process, Blue Justice theory was chosen as a promising framework to assess empowerment and guided the statement development. However, translating abstract theoretical concepts into accessible and meaningful statements for diverse stakeholders was not straightforward. Conveying the principles of equitable resource distribution and justice in coastal transitions required language that resonated across contexts without oversimplifying the ideas.

For instance, the TCLs reflected back that the term 'blue growth' would be difficult for participants to grasp. Terms like 'marginalised groups' held different meanings depending on cultural and social contexts. Some communities associated marginalisation with socioeconomic status, while others focused on geographic isolation or access to resources. Balancing these diverse interpretations without biasing the statements required extensive discussion.

The need to translate statements into six languages introduced additional complexity. Nuances and idiomatic expressions often did not align perfectly across languages, leading to different interpretations of the same terms. Despite careful translation efforts, some statements lost clarity or became less accessible in translation. It is important to avoid

overly complex and inaccessible language, and even though some TCLs tried to adapt and explain the term using different words when translating the Q sorts, it would have been better to have explained this term in a simpler manner from the outset.

On the other hand, the process of developing the statements facilitated a deeper understanding of the TCLs and their contexts even at this early stage. It provided opportunities for cross-country teams to share insights on local priorities, fostering a sense of shared ownership. In the end, the team agreed on a final set of statements. A shared commitment to the goals of the project facilitated decision-making and enabled the team to produce statements that were broadly representative of all six country contexts.

7.2.3 Participants selection – motivating people to attend

The EmpowerUs team interpreted 'Users of the Sea' to include a wide range of stakeholders, from fishermen and tourism operators to policy makers and local residents. Based on the different TCL contexts and a stakeholder analysis that has been conducted in another work package, we recruited different types of stakeholders in each TCL. There were minor barriers to persuading people to take part in the Q sorts. Some potential participants were sceptical about the relevance of the exercise and perceived it as being too complex, while others faced practical challenges such as language barriers, time constraints or the ability to discuss statements in real time.

7.2.4 Reflections on the practical exercise of using Q method

Conducting the Q methodology exercises revealed both challenges and some strengths of the method. Practical hurdles arose, particularly with language. Working across different countries and languages meant some statements were hard for participants to understand, such as terms like blue growth, which required additional explanation. In-person sessions proved invaluable, as they allowed for clarifications and richer discussions. Some TCLs experimented with Q-sorting with participants using online tools and this worked well. One challenge was the forced distribution of statements on the grid. Some participants found it difficult, wishing they could disagree with most statements rather than following the structured format. This highlighted the importance of capturing participants' reasoning during the process. The qualitative insights – how participants made sense of the sorting – added depth to the findings and revealed important nuances beyond the grid.

Figure 7.3 Q sorting in Cap de Creus. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

Figure 7.4 Q sorting in Cap de Creus. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

Alongside these challenges, the process has also shown some strengths. Many participants enjoyed the interactive and playful nature of working with the Q grid and statements, finding it more engaging than traditional approaches. Similarly, interviewers and local hosts appreciated how the method brought a fresh dimension to their work, moving beyond regular interviews.

7.2.5 Analysis of Qs

In our analysis of Q sorts, we used an open-source online tool for the quantitative analysis, which allowed us to process the data without additional costs. However, the tool occasionally presented stability issues, and a more robust solution might have been preferable. For the qualitative analysis, the diversity of languages required a collaborative effort. The TCL teams worked closely with the research team and put a lot of effort into interpreting the findings to ensure that cultural and contextual nuances were accurately captured.

The results varied across the six regions: in some countries only one factor emerged as statistically significant, while in others two or three different

factors were significant. This variation highlighted the challenge of comparing results across different local contexts. Despite this variation, common perceptions emerged among the stakeholders revealing common themes across the regions. These findings not only enriched our understanding of the local contexts but also provided valuable recommendations that could be applied to other coastal communities facing similar challenges.

Figure 7.5 Træna, Norway. Credit: Ida Glørstad Jørgensen

7.3 Brief summary and added value of the Q method

The Q methodology proved to be a valuable tool for capturing baseline perspectives on empowerment in coastal communities. Its structured approach helped reveal patterns in subjective opinions, even across complex and varied contexts. However, it also presented challenges. Empowerment, as a subjective and context-specific concept, was difficult to capture through predefined statements, which sometimes constrained participants' ability to fully express their experiences. Developing statements that resonated across contexts and cultures required careful collaboration and translation, highlighting the tension between inclusivity and structure. Recruiting participants and addressing practical barriers further underscored these challenges. Nevertheless, the method's iterative nature and emphasis on qualitative insights enriched the findings, allowing us to track shifts in perceptions over time and derive shared themes across diverse coastal regions. The insights gained from the Q survey have informed the development of further ocean literacy activities, the design of pilot interventions, the refinement of the Tailored Empowerment Programs (TEPs) and the further evaluation of project results.

7.4 Final conclusions – what we recommend if you want to use Q-method in your project

- Choose Q methodology for subjective perspectives: Q methodology is suitable to explore patterns in opinions and perceptions, especially for complex and subjective concepts such as empowerment or blue justice.
- Develop statements collaboratively: Involve diverse project teams in the statement development process to ensure inclusivity and relevance across contexts. Use theoretical frameworks for guidance but simplify abstract concepts for broader accessibility.
- Address language nuances: Carefully translate statements to account for idioms and cultural differences, ensuring clarity and comparability across languages.
- Adapt recruitment to local contexts: Define target participants clearly and inclusively, using local networks for recruitment. Evaluate inclusivity to avoid bias in participant selection, e.g. through stakeholder mapping.
- Leverage interactive engagement: Highlight the engaging nature of Q-sorting to increase participant interest and engagement.
- Overcome practical barriers: Anticipate and mitigate challenges such as participant availability, scepticism or language barriers through clear communication and flexible scheduling.
- Balance structure and flexibility: Be aware that forced distribution of statements may limit participants' ability to fully express nuances; consider supplementary methods to capture qualitative insights.
- Plan with interviews for greater insight: Allow sufficient time for reflection to explore participants' reasons for their choices.
- Highlight collaborative interpretations: Use both statistical tools for factor analysis and put emphasis on collaborative interpretation to effectively capture contextual nuances.
- Adapt tools to budget and needs: Use open-source tools where appropriate but consider investing in more robust solutions for greater stability of the software.

Ireland. Credit: Alex Miller

8. Participation through photography – altering the photovoice method to enable inclusion across Europe

Authors: Josefin Ekstedt, Kristen Ounanian, Janni Sørensen and Rikke Becker Jacobsen (Aalborg University), and Janni Sørensen (Aalborg University)

This chapter introduces a modified approach to photovoice developed by EmpowerUs to facilitate public participation from multiple coastal communities/TCL locations. Our deployment of this method was designed in recognition of the varying capacity for implementation of a full-scale photovoice project in the TCLs and could be called a ‘light’ version. We present the argument that this approach to photovoice is suitable as a social science data collection method that could broaden inclusion and add an additional layer of co-creation to an on-going, participatory process.

Developed as a participatory method rooted in feminist theory, photography, and critical consciousness (Wang & Burris, 1997) photovoice’s purpose is to supplement and deepen researchers’ understandings of a community and develop knowledge that can address issues and uncover injustices while building local capacity. Closely related to photo elicitation methods, these visual research methods have been used with success in coastal areas to study wellbeing (Dias & Armitage, 2021; Thomas et al., 2021), host community’s perceptions of tourism (Janusz et al., 2017) and gentrification (Bratchford, 2020). Although the distinction in the literature between photovoice and photo elicitation methods can be fuzzy, we adopt photovoice methodology which distinguishes that research participants—not researchers—generate and provide the photographs used in the interviews (Shaw, 2021).

Photovoice aims for a more inclusive methodology that explicitly seeks to address local problems and uncover injustice while building capacity in a marginalised group. The method has often been used to reach youth, language minorities, or other groups who are often left out of more standard processes of public participation (see e.g. Anderson et al., 2023; McIntyre, 2003; Murray & Nash, 2017; Wang & Burris, 1997). Furthermore, photovoice provides an alternative path for seeking inclusion of otherwise ‘hard to reach groups’ that have not been reached in more traditional workshop formats for example. Acting as co-researchers through photos and attached narratives they determine

what in their community should be photographed, documented, and analysed. In this way photovoice methodology is intended to be more than data collection. In the ideal form, goals of raising consciousness about root causes of marginalisation, building social capital and sharing knowledge that can impact communities undergoing transformation, frames the process (Anderson et al., 2023).

A key challenge to overcome when conducting the photovoice methodology is translating the abstract concept of adjacency into interview prompts and questions. Nonetheless, the chosen visual and participatory methods offer means to overcome such challenge: ‘The tacit knowledge about issues emerges as the participants go through a process of visualising the issue and producing images. The process encourages participant ownership of the question and engagement with, and empowerment in, the research process, through the narration that occurs’ (Shaw, 2021, p. 341).

8.1 How to conduct a photovoice project

The process of the photovoice is divided into several steps (Figure 8.1 a), and includes recruitment of participants, photo assignment, collecting narratives belonging to the photos, disseminating the photos and narratives, and data analysis. Participation of researchers and respondents differs between the steps, where typically, the researcher will be more involved during the start of the project and during data analysis, while the practical part of the photovoice process e.g. photography and narratives, is reliant on the participants. The process will vary depending on a research project’s scope, geographical location, and participant capacity. For example, training in usage of cameras and photography might be needed in some cases. The photovoice step-by-step process was slightly altered in the EmpowerUs project (Figure 8.1 b), where e.g. dissemination of the photovoice results was conducted subsequently to the coding and analysis of the photos and narratives. This will be further elaborated later in the chapter.

Figure 8.1 (a) by Dias & Armitage (2021) shows the process of photovoice from recruitment to final analysis. Inspired by Dias & Armitage (2021) (b) shows the adapted Photovoice process appointed in the EmpowerUs project.

A modified approach to the photovoice methodology, allowed participation from multiple TCL locations with varying capacity for implementation of a full scale photovoice project. Furthermore, it allows reflection of the usefulness of photovoice as mostly data collection that adds a layer of knowledge, context, and emotional depth that we would otherwise not be able to include.

8.2 The ‘light’ photovoice method in the EmpowerUs project

The photovoice methodology was adopted in the EmpowerUs project for empirical data collection. The data collection centred on the cross-TCL vision to ‘Re-direct the blue economy to support thriving coastal communities’ and three inductively identified strategies. Participants were asked to express their real, not ideal, experiences through e.g. expressing a critical voice, critique, and/or impediments to realising visions. Following principles of inclusion, emphasis was put on the Leave No One Behind factor in recruiting participants for the photovoice process.

The objectives for collecting this form of data in EmpowerUs were:

1. Evidence transition mechanisms: implementation/mobilisation; sustainable, social practices; structures and institutions that enable reflection and reflexivity
 - a. Document intentions, needs, and opportunities and the means to achieve vision(s) or critique vision and/or its implementation
 - b. Obtain more distinct – and comparable – empirical data across the TCLs

The intention of the methodology was to use photos as a tool to help the participants answer questions provided to them by the researchers

through written narratives. The photos were intended to help the participants think about past, present, or future periods, express emotions e.g. fears, uncertainties and wishes, or explore nature connectedness and cultural heritage. For this purpose, the participants were given a prompt to consider before and during the photo-assignment. Participants were asked to photograph or collect 3-5 photos while considering the following prompt:

What enables and/or prevents you to:

- a. Connect to the sea?
- b. Benefit from the sea and/or its resources?
- c. Promote [TCLs] [your community’s] wellbeing or vitality?

The photovoice exercise was adapted from its original format to fit the EmpowerUs project. As the planners of the photovoice process and eventual users of the data collected were project partners outside of the TCLs, emphasis was placed on not adding too much additional work to the local project partners. Building of the Leave No One Behind principles, the local hosts firstly introduced the photovoice exercise to ‘harder-to-reach’ groups, that were yet to have participated in the project – this included women, migrants, and youth. Depending on the level of participation, the exercise was then introduced to further Users of the Sea. Adapting to the spread-out locations of the TCLs, data was collected through an online portal that was translated to the TCL languages during the autumn/winter of 2024-2025. Furthermore, to avoid language-related issues, participants were encouraged to submit written narratives in their preferred language. Options were also given to record spoken narrative in cases where participants experienced challenges in writing narratives.

The format of written narratives allowed participants that are not comfortable in traditional interview formats to participate in the research.

A communal activity to highlight the outcomes of the photovoice project was encouraged to the TCLs, however, in the spirit of not adding to the local partners workload, was not mandatory. Photos and narratives from the EmpowerUs photovoice, were however, depending on given consent, shared digitally (see Figure 8.2 for example).

Figure 8.2a “Just note how clean the water is. It’s cleanest in the winter when there is the least amount of human intervention and refuse.” Credit: Photovoice participant

Figure 8.2b “In this space, I feel fortunate to be able to enjoy this exceptional environment. We must preserve this space for the wealth it represents in every sense.” Credit: Photovoice participant

8.3 Resources needed for ‘light’ photovoice

The requirement of resources for the ‘light’ photovoice-method varies depending on the objective of the specific data collection. While the photovoice-method is a highly adaptable research method, the core of photovoice involves photography and recording of a narrative (written or oral) and therefore relies on suitable technical equipment. However, the adaptability of the method means that it can be facilitated in various environments and communities and tailored depending on the resources available in the project.

While there are restricted needs of equipment to facilitate the method, the method relies on access to a (digital) camera or smartphone, as well as readiness of the photovoice participants to have some general knowledge of photography and camera usage. This could be addressed through training the participants

(Wang & Burris, 1997). Furthermore, access to develop/print pictures is needed if there is a wish in the project to include some form of exhibition to showcase project outcomes.

Box 8.1 Resources needed for the ‘light’ Photovoice

Operationalising ‘light’ photovoice – resources needed

- a) A **protocol** that operationalises the transformation objectives aim into very simple probes: the protocol should be clear enough for any layman participant to understand it without further introduction (see EmpowerUs-used example above). This includes translation and testing of the protocol.
- b) Clear **instructions** for the photo assignment – this could include suitable photography training if needed.
- c) Approval from an **Ethical Review**, to ensure that the project adhere to national and institutional ethical requirements.
- d) A **consent procedure** which includes personal data, that those depicted have agreed to feature in the photo and are above legal age, and dissemination of entries including for scientific purposes, project-related platforms, and/or to the local community.
- e) A **platform** for uploading narratives and providing consent. The EmpowerUs-project used the SurveyXact-platform.
- f) A **Data Management Plan** with a clear data owner and processor to comply with GDPR. This should include a strategy for how to assess that privacy is ensured in photo exhibition NB: if resources are applied across national institutions, the resources must adhere to all.

8.4 Strengths and weaknesses of the ‘light’ photovoice method

Reflecting on the usefulness of the photovoice, and the methodology’s application in the EmpowerUs project, several strengths and weaknesses of the method are recognised.

The photovoice-method was chosen to be used for data collection within the EmpowerUs project due to the method’s strong focus on community development and its flexibility of data collection design. Flexible data collection was also an influencing factor in the decision to digitalise the photovoice assignment in the EmpowerUs project, where the objective was to both avoid research fatigue through allowing participants

to schedule their own participation, but also to decrease the project partners responsibility of data collection. While the openness of the data collection entails that participants can schedule their own participation, it can also leave the researchers ‘in the hands’ of the participants scheduling. For this reason, researchers who chooses a more open, digital, approach should be advised to contemplate either a longer period of data collection and data analysis or to enforce a ‘hard’ deadline of data collection, to ensure sufficient time for both the participants needs and for data analysis.

In the EmpowerUs project, the research participants wrote their own narratives, without interference from the researchers. There are both benefits and disadvantages to restricting the researcher’s involvement in narrative development. While it allows the participants to manage their own time as discussed above, it also leaves responsibility for the interpretation of the photos solely with the research participants. However, the local, cultural, and social awareness of research participants – which researchers might lack - could help avoid potential misrepresentation in the data analysis, especially if the data analysis were solely in the hands of the researchers. It is possible that collection of some narratives could benefit from being facilitated through conversations between researchers and project participants. A spoken conversation would allow researchers to steer the discussions around photography, and for the participants to be guided in their reflection of their photos. In EmpowerUs, we addressed this through ensuring that the questions that were to be answered in writing were sufficiently detailed, while participants were also allowed to express their own thoughts, opinions, and reflections.

The flexibility of the method opens the possibility for wider participation, as it can be adopted to fit participants with certain needs, e.g. allowing participants who experience challenges in writing to record a spoken narrative. Furthermore, the photographs allow participants and researchers to overcome potential language barriers through the use of a visual medium, from which a translatable spoken or written narrative can be facilitated. Through overcoming language barriers, the methods ensure to Leave No One Behind. This was warranted in the EmpowerUs project through including translation of the photovoice-assignment to several languages, including minority languages in the partnering countries.

The strengths of the photovoice-method described previously in this chapter are related to the method’s strong inclusive feature and are of

benefit to the photovoice-participants, but also in the interest of researchers who wish to decrease research fatigue. There is, however, a trade-off between the inclusivity of the method and the administrative burden added to the researcher. In some contexts, it was not easy to recruit participants, and it became a time consuming and difficult task for local researchers raising questions of how to communicate the value of participation to reach goals of more inclusivity. The various administrative skills require a ‘jack of all trades’-researcher who has knowledge of e.g. consent forms, personal data protection, ethical concerns, development of digital questionnaires (if used). Researchers who adopt the method in the future are recommended to dedicate extra time during the research design-phase to accommodate the administrative burden that is added in the early part of the project.

8.5 Ethical dimensions and consent

There is a responsibility on researchers to provide a safe environment for the research participants to provide opinions when they are invited as co-investigators. This includes clarifying the voluntary aspect of participation and the option to answer anonymously. Furthermore, confidential information, such as political, cultural, and philosophical opinions, should be handled with care if obtained. Researchers should ensure that the method is a fair exchange between the researchers and participants, recognising the value for the community, and ensure that the outcomes of the photovoice reaches the community fittingly (if desired). While the participants’ contributions through photovoice are considered data collection, the photographs and connected narratives should also be regarded as the participants’ intellectual property. Participants should therefore be given the opportunity to choose if they wish to be credited for their photos (if appropriate).

It is important for participants to be aware of their surroundings and surrounding people when using a visual methodology, such as photography, to ensure confidentiality of both the participants and those (potentially) captured in photographs. While photovoice-participants are not restricted in what they photograph, they are encouraged to pay respect to those around them. To avoid featuring people who are not interested in being part of research dissemination, researchers could opt to blur/black-boxing faces, identifiable features, tattoos, etc. All those who are featured without having been blurred/black-boxed should have given consent to be featured in research dissemination.

8.6 Conclusion

Photovoice and 'light' photovoice are flexible methodologies that allow inclusive research. While the methodology comes with challenges, such as in recruitment of participants and added administrative burden in relation to data collection, the method allows participants to increase awareness of their local environment, while also (hopefully) reflecting on their own surroundings through an empowering process.

We wish to conclude with the following recommendations for those who wish to include the methodology in their research:

- Develop a clear and thorough research plan, prior to recruitment of participants
- Ensure that you, as a researcher, possess comprehensive knowledge and understanding of local social, cultural, and/or natural aspects when developing the project and prompt
- Be receptive to feedback from the research participants and local researchers and be willing to adapt part of the process.

9. Reflection interviews to secure observation data and facilitate peer debriefing

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9.1 Introduction

While spontaneous field reflections are easily overlooked and inconsistently documented during participatory research, EmpowerUs formalised the reflection process through scheduled peer debriefing (Denzin & Lincoln, 1994), capturing insights that would otherwise be lost. In a team of researchers, tasks are often divided between people doing fieldwork and researchers tasked with theorising, analysing, evaluating, and disseminating results (synthesising). To secure good collaboration and critical observational data, this chapter introduces the methodology of 'reflection interviews' which were done between researchers doing fieldwork and the synthesising researchers.

While gathering data and reflecting on the process and impact of the participatory methods used in the field, the reflection interviews also served as spaces for reflexive dialogue between the field researchers and those conducting the interviews. Although we worked on different tasks within in the project, we were peers – familiar with the collective aims, possible methodological challenges and the subjects at stake – which created good conditions for meaningful debriefing (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

In this way, reflection interviews created spaces for critical and constructive reflection and discussions on methodological choices and practices, making it possible to implement new strategies to overcome challenges related to topics such as inclusivity, methodological challenges, co-production of knowledge, and power dynamics, continuously and throughout the process.

9.2 The importance of reflection and reflexivity for participatory research

Reflection and reflexivity are acknowledged as crucial concepts and practices to enhance research quality and impact. A key contribution of reflection and reflexivity is the heightened awareness of implicit biases and assumptions. Reflexivity is often understood as the continuous process of critically reflecting on one's (the researcher's) own role, positionality, and influence on research and practice (Finlay, 2002; Berger, 2015). In a broader sense, reflexivity also generates a deeper understanding of knowledge production (Ide & Beddoe, 2023) through awareness of context and self in the process of constructing knowledge (Von Unger et al., 2022). While reflection and reflexivity are related and often intertwined concepts (Ide & Beddoe, 2023), considering both can be helpful. Reflection brings thoughtful consideration of the researchers' own experiences, actions, decisions, and their outcomes to the forefront, typically in a retrospective manner (Van Beveren et al., 2018; Ide & Beddoe, 2023). Reflexivity goes deeper and considers how the researcher's social position, power dynamics, cultural background, and biases shape the research questions, data collection, and interpretation.

In practice, reflection and reflexivity often remain as individual and unstructured thoughts. When researchers do take the step to write them down, they typically do so through journaling, memo writing, or personal notes that capture their evolving thinking as the research unfolds (Karcher et al., 2024; Olmos-Vega et al., 2022).

The increasing use of co-creation and participatory action research methods gives reason for further developing the way we use reflexivity and critical reflection.

Multiple connected objectives of reflection interviews in participatory research

Establish a flexible, but structured and organised space for support, on-the-spot strategising to solve challenges

Provide prompts for ongoing reflection on core values such as justice, inclusion, and power

To log and track progress throughout the fieldwork and document changes or adjustments made to methods

Table 9.1 Three objectives of doing reflection interviews

Participatory methodologies aim to democratise knowledge production by actively involving community partners in the research process, thereby fostering inclusivity and empowerment (Bjørkan, 2011; Edwards & Brannelly, 2017; Phillips et al., 2022). However, such collaborations are complex and can perpetuate existing power dynamics and inequalities (Sørensen et al., 2025).

Figure 9.1. Kirkehelleren Cave in Træna, Norway. Credit: Sunniva Solnør

9.3 Methodology: Reflection interviews as ‘peer-debriefing’

Writing about peer-debriefing methods as a support tool for classroom teachers, Hail, Hurst, & Camp (2011, p.76) highlight its benefits, particularly to restrict bias in the interpretation of information, providing opportunities to develop new ideas with a peer and supporting the ongoing process of creating and refining practices.

Beyond their analytical value, reflection and reflexivity can play an important role in participatory research, not just for strengthening the research itself, but also for navigating ethical concerns and addressing power imbalances that can emerge in collaborative settings (Anang et al., 2021), as well as refining and improving methodological practices. In the spirit of co-creation, shifting from individual reflexivity and reflection to a more collaborative

process among peers strengthens mutual understanding and supports shared ownership of the research process. Reflection Interviews, facilitated by a peer researcher, also free the local researchers from needing to write, systematise, and report on these reflections themselves.

9.4 Implementation and process

In the EmpowerUs project, reflection interviews were implemented as a structured methodology involving repeated, in-depth interviews with the local academic researchers, and sometimes also the local community hosts (organisations) actively engaged in the six case study communities, in the project named ‘Transition Coastal Labs’ (TCLs). These interviews aimed at promoting researcher reflexivity, critical reflection on the co-creation processes, stakeholder participation, and the power dynamics within the TCLs and throughout the project. The goal was to create a feedback mechanism that collected research data as well as supported academic and local partners by allowing them to reflect on their experiences, challenges, and the broader implications of their work, as well as to identify areas of improvement with regard to an overarching ambition to secure inclusivity.

The reflection interviews were conducted over multiple phases of the project, with each session lasting approximately 1 to 1.5 hours. The interviews were repeated four times throughout the project, allowing participants to reflect on the process and potential changes over time. We structured the reflection interviews around central participatory project events, such as after each of the two local workshops (see Chapter 2), the launch of community pilots (see Chapter 5), and at the end of the project.

The interviews were supported and guided by a pre-designed set of questions adapted to different phases of the project and the specific context of each TCL. This approach helped ensure relevance and meaningful dialogue. While the interview guide provided structure, it was not followed rigidly; rather, it served as a flexible guide. We aimed to cover all key themes across the interviews to support comparability and depth, but allowed the conversation to flow naturally, returning to earlier questions or exploring emerging reflections as needed. The Reflection Interviews were thus designed to capture the complexities and changing dynamics of the project’s co-creation process and helped reveal how these processes played out in practice and what kinds of impacts they had.

Researchers often struggle to have enough time for meaningful reflection while a project is actively unfolding (Probst & Berenson, 2014), as was the case for EmpowerUs. In consideration of the time pressures in the TCLs, we decided to do the interviews online to save time. Interviews were recorded, transcribed, and summarised into written content summaries by the interviewer. Afterwards, the summaries were corrected and elaborated by the interviewee if needed. This was an important process for validating the co-constructed interpretations developed in the interviews. This aspect was also important as the reflection notes were used as data in other parts of the project.

Time is not the only challenge in peer-debriefing. Another important point is the trust needed to talk about challenges and perhaps even failures and frustrations. One measure to support developing trust was to have the same peers interviewing each TCL, allowing for ongoing dialogue between academic or local partners. This approach ensured consistency and continuity in the reflective process, enhancing the depth and relevance of the insights generated.

9.5 Reflection on strengths and weaknesses

Through our experiences using this method for synthesising, we’ve observed its impact firsthand. Conducting these interviews shortly after participatory workshops and other key events provided valuable real-time insights into the work happening within the TCLs. Reflecting on challenges and successes – whether related to methods, facilitation, or community engagement – has brought us closer to the realities of the participatory fieldwork, deepened our understanding, and helped us stay attuned to the evolving needs and dynamics of the project. For example, it has fostered a deeper understanding of the challenges involved in reaching migrant populations, and we’ve been able to actively contribute to discussions around new and alternative approaches to addressing this issue.

From the perspective of the TCLs, the Reflection Interviews were seen as both useful and meaningful. Several researchers described them as a space for learning – and even a kind of informal therapy – where it felt easier to talk than to write things down. For instance, an academic researcher in Bulgaria shared that they felt far more comfortable in these conversations than when filling out structured tools like Excel forms. Others valued the opportunity to speak with someone from ‘outside’ the immediate

local context, which helped validate their work and offered reassurance about the direction they were taking. Also, peer debriefing helped alleviate the stress of not always achieving ambitious goals of co-creation and inclusion, when others recognised how difficult this can be. In Ireland, a field researcher highlighted that the interviews provided an outlet to reflect on observations and experiences that might otherwise go unrecorded, such as how the composition of workshop participants shaped different outcomes, or how language and identity affected inclusion in the community. In the Norwegian TCL, the interviews served as both a reminder of past activities and a prompt to think ahead and created a space to talk about topics that might not usually come up in day-to-day work. There, the interviews evolved into group discussions that also included the local organisation involved in the TCL, and the shared reflections proved valuable, as they helped bridge different roles, experiences, and perspectives between the academic and local partners.

Reflection Interviews also played a role in refining practices as the project progressed. In some cases, discussions prompted by the interviews led participants to reconsider their approaches – for example, reflecting on difficulties engaging community or civil society members in early events, sparked new ideas for outreach and engagement. This led to more intentional efforts to invite a broader and more diverse group of participants to later activities. In this way, peer reflection helped build reflexivity and became a tool for increasing inclusion and responsiveness in the co-creation process.

While reflection interviews provided valuable insights, the approach also has limitations. In striving for inclusivity and aiming to involve diverse community stakeholders while reflecting on power dynamics and community relationships, we actively considered the positionalities of those involved. However, although researchers may consciously reflect on and account for their positionality, they cannot fully understand the perspectives or interpretations of others.

Also, questions about the breadth and depth of representation are not always apparent – either to researchers or other external observers. For example, we cannot assume that one young person speaks for all young people in a community. Representation cannot be reduced to simply counting categories of participants, and the nuances of individual experiences and identities are not easily captured.

Differences in interpretation can lead to misunderstandings or misrepresentations of individuals' lived experiences. We have, for example, reflected upon how a researcher might interpret a conversation among stakeholders as conflict due to the tone or language used, but the stakeholders themselves may not perceive the interaction as conflictual; instead, they may view this manner of speaking as a normal and culturally appropriate way of expressing disagreement or debate. While researchers may aim to address imbalances through peer debriefing, these efforts could be limited by the difficulty of representing the nuanced, complex positionalities within the community accurately. On the other hand, one can argue that the in-field researchers were quite well-positioned due to long-term engagement in and knowledge of the community.

As previously noted, good reflections between peers/researchers also depend on trust between them, securing a feeling of confidentiality where challenges can be talked about openly. The 'risk of misunderstanding' may also exist here, due to many different disciplinary/cultural/historical backgrounds and related understandings of core concepts such as participation, inclusion, and power amongst the researchers.

Despite these challenges, reflection interviews remain a valuable tool for fostering critical self-reflection and supporting the ethical responsibilities of researchers in participatory projects. They provide a structured yet adaptable framework for capturing the complexities of co-creation and for addressing inclusion and stakeholder dynamics in collaborative research.

9.6 Concluding remarks and future directions

The reflection interviews in the EmpowerUs project served as a tool for both reflection and reflexivity, enhancing the feedback loop to discuss issues of power, inclusivity, and co-production of knowledge. These discussions not only supported individual and collective learning but also informed broader project development, offering valuable feedback that could be integrated into ongoing processes and within and across TCLs. Reflection interviews can serve as a model for other participatory research and innovation projects seeking to incorporate reflexivity, reflection, and inclusivity of methodologies and stakeholder engagement in their project.

By documenting reflections and creating spaces for continuous dialogue, researchers can enhance the quality and inclusivity of their work while also addressing the ethical complexities in participatory research. Since the reflection interviews are somewhat time-consuming and resource-intensive, it's important to build buy-in and understanding at the beginning of the project. The reflection interviews also represent a good opportunity for a first-stage analysis of the various steps, events, and developments in the communities.

Part IV: METHODS AND METHODOLOGIES FOR EMPOWERMENT

Figure IV: Åland. Credit: Viktor Eriksson

10. Community Empowerment Tools for strengthening coastal social-ecological resilience

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10.1 Introduction to the concept of ‘Empowerment Tools’ in a socio-environmental context

The concept of ‘empowerment’ originated in the fields of social work and community development during the mid-20th century. Empowerment commonly refers to ‘the process of gaining freedom and power to do what you want or to control what happens to you’ (Cambridge Dictionary). Empowerment aims to support marginalised communities and groups, strengthening their capacity to overcome challenges and improve their quality of life. In a socio-environmental context, empowerment refers to giving individuals and communities the knowledge, resources, and decision-making power to address environmental challenges while promoting social equity (Grown et al., 2005); it involves ensuring that people have an active and meaningful role in environmental decision-making and can actively participate in environmental use, management and conservation of environment, co-create sustainable and local solutions fit for the context. Community empowerment can also enhance social-ecological resilience towards multiple pressures like climate change or trends in economy and policy. As such, community empowerment can help coastal communities recover from difficulties and can enhance capacity for positive adaptation and transformation in the face of intertwined sustainability challenges.

In the context of the EmpowerUs project, Empowerment is understood as the process through which actors gain the capacity to mobilise resources and institutions to achieve a goal. This process of ‘gaining capacity’ is unpacked along three dimensions: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies to mobilise them

and (3) the willingness to do so (Avelino et al., 2017). One key objective in EmpowerUs was to develop a diverse, integrated, and adaptable set of solutions, instruments, strategies and resources to support the Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) in developing adaptation strategies for various coastal challenges. TCLs, bringing together researchers, local organisations and local communities, were tackling ‘wicked problems’, sustainability challenges and create solutions together for sustainable, resilient and inclusive coastal regions (EmpowerUs, 2024; also see Chapter 2). Ultimately, the goal of the project was to strengthen the resilience and capacity in the coastal communities to navigate socio-environmental challenges. To achieve this, the project required a comprehensive, evidence-based overview of how empowerment tools and Nature-based Solutions (NBS) can contribute to the resilience of coastal communities and social-ecological systems, ensuring that interventions were grounded in the latest knowledge, local goals and best practices.

The term ‘empowerment tools’ was introduced by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) over a decade ago to advance environmental justice (Khoday et al., 2014). These tools are designed to assist communities in undertaking targeted actions to drive social-ecological transitions and foster resilience (Laverack & Wallerstein, 2001). Despite their growing relevance, the literature lacks consensus on the definition and categorisation of empowerment tools; yet these have been generally described in relation to their scope of action – whether political, community, or a hybrid of both as well as the sector or purpose they address, such as public and environmental health, resource management or science and research. Inspired by Arnstein’s classification of

participation (1969), empowerment tools can transform communities and their stakeholders from mere participants towards active and (ideally long-term) involved co-owners of processes and projects and have a direct influence on their social and environmental futures.

10.2 Evidence-based synthesis of Empowerment Tools performed by Eklipse

To deepen the understanding of the link between community empowerment and coastal resilience, EmpowerUs engaged Eklipse (<https://eklipse.eu/>), a well-established, self-sustaining knowledge brokering mechanism, to develop an evidence-based catalogue of existing empowerment tools, that would be further tailored to the TCLs. An Expert Working Group (EWG) was convened to undertake this task, bringing together six scientists with relevant expertise in natural and social sciences to conduct a Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA). Active from June 2023 to June 2024, their objective was to answer the critical question: ‘How can community Empowerment Tools and Nature-based Solutions contribute to addressing coastal challenges and building resilient communities?’. Through this process, the EWG aimed to provide a robust, evidence-based foundation for integrating empowerment strategies into coastal resilience efforts within the TCLs.

After establishing a common definition of empowerment tools as ‘a diverse set of strategies, resources, or mechanisms tailored to augment the self-efficacy, autonomy, and active participation of individuals or communities in decision-making processes’ (Sieber et al., 2024); adapted from Laverack & Wallerstein (2001), the EWG conducted a structured search of both international

academic peer-reviewed literature (‘scientific’) and grey literature. The search was based on relevant keywords, title, and abstracts to assess the relevance of records for further review. Through content analysis of the full texts, the EWG identified, clustered, and examined various tools through which empowerment was targeted, including participatory approaches and methods used in community interventions, that have proven effective in enhancing social-ecological resilience in coastal communities. Although different approaches could be classified based on their scope of action and the level of stakeholder involvement, much of the literature on empowerment tools requires interpretation. Often, participatory and empowerment approaches are presented in the scientific literature, through concise applications and case studies, necessitating abstraction to extend their relevance to a broader applicability. This process requires a solid understanding of participatory and empowerment methodologies beyond the context of Nature-based Solutions (NBS) topics, as classifications were conducted retrospectively. Within this framework, the identified tools were categorised based on their intended outcomes, target audience, stakeholder involvement, and depth of engagement.

10.3 Classification of Empowerment Tools and compilation of a catalogue

Altogether, six distinct groups of empowerment tools were identified: **Education and Awareness, Knowledge tools, Platforms/Dialogue, Governance tools, Co-creation, and NBS approaches** (Figure 1), comprising 35 tools that identified strengthening local governance structures, enhance knowledge-sharing and capacity-building, as well as financial and technical resource mobilisation. (Figure 1).

Figure 10.1 Six distinct categories of empowerment tools clustered by the Eklipse EWG on ‘Building Resilient Coastal Communities through NBS and Empowerment Tools’. (copyright authors)

Those empowerment tools should be understood in their broader sense, encompassing different approaches, frameworks, and processes to foster empowerment, participation and creating

ownership. This categorisation provides a structured overview of how different empowerment tools can contribute to resilience-building, offering a toolbox for application in the TCLs (Table 10.1).

Empowerment Tool Group and Description	Example of tools
<p>Education/awareness – raising tools</p> <p>Methods and approaches to educate communities and raise general awareness on environmental, social-ecological, and socio-economic issues, allowing citizens to make informed decisions, informing communities in a timely manner matters, by creating awareness and information, communicating science and equipping citizens with basic understanding needed to make decisions. This increases the capacities of communities to act and participate in decision-making.</p>	<p>Visual displays, media campaigns, Open Days/ Information</p> <p>Sessions, science/world cafes</p>
<p>Knowledge tools</p> <p>Methods and approaches directed at knowledge production to answer community or societal questions and needs, including stakeholder involvement and consultation in knowledge production processes in a timely manner.</p>	<p>Interviews, Narrative assessments, preference assessments, stakeholder-based problem analysis, Surveys, Questionnaires, Participatory Mapping, Citizen/Community sciences, social learning</p>
<p>Platform/Dialogue tools</p> <p>Methods and approaches to foster new or strengthen existing modes of communication and networks, bringing together strategic alliances for enhanced community decision-making. Community participation often ranges from consultation to collaboration.</p>	<p>Participatory stakeholder analysis, focus groups, participatory mapping, PGIS and PPGIS, Joint Fact Finding</p>
<p>Governance tools</p> <p>Methods and approaches supporting new and transformative governance structures that ensure community empowerment through collaboration for just, equitable and democratic policy and decision-making, fostering bottom-up approaches and new organisational structures including polycentric governance as well as stakeholder and community collaboration and co-design.</p>	<p>Citizen Panels, Participatory spatial planning, participatory scenario planning, stewardship building, polycentric governance</p>
<p>Co-creation tools</p> <p>Methods and approaches to create novel, transformative modes of collaboration and decision-making, creating new arenas for new, integrative and co-designed research and collaboration amongst stakeholders, communities, enterprises and science.</p>	<p>Living Labs, Ownership building, participatory study design, community based participatory research, action research</p>
<p>Community-led Nature-based Solutions:</p> <p>Community-based environmental and nature-based actions that enhance resilience with local to regional co-benefits, whilst simultaneously strengthening community collaboration and co-design.</p>	<p>Community led gardens, community led habitat restoration, adaptive coastal design, nature-based food production</p>

Table 10.1 Simplified table with empowerment tool groups, descriptions and examples, based on the catalogue of tools from Sieber et al. 2024

10.4 Reflections on the concept of empowerment tools and their tailoring to communities

10.4.1 Importance of a shared understanding of the concept of empowerment tools and their effectiveness for empowerment and resilience of communities

Empowerment tools have been presented very recently in socio-ecological and sustainability contexts, and a clear common definition is crucial to explain the importance of it to communities and their stakeholders. Such tools and approaches are central elements of any empowerment process, yet many knowledge gaps remain on how such empowerment tools can be the most effective in their implementation.

While participation and empowerment are not necessarily causally linked, empowering or participatory methods, alongside knowledge co-production, can directly contribute to community empowerment (Laverack & Wallenstein, 2001). Hence, empowerment can be understood as both a process and an outcome, or a dynamic continuum. In this context, a stable institutional environment that values participation, transparency, and accountability offer a stronger foundation for implementing empowerment initiatives within a given territory, facilitating their adoption.

Participatory and Empowerment processes need to be inclusive: yet there are challenges to reach different parts of the community for various reasons: difficulty of access to communities, fatigue of stakeholders, power relationships, mistrust in science, etc. To have sufficient feedback from the community, a broad range of stakeholders need to feel a strong self-efficacy, ownership, and responsibility on key focus areas of empowerment, in order to be able to engage in the co-selection or co-design of empowerment tools. Community empowerment has not only proved to increase the quality of life and well-being, but also has a positive impact in shaping sustainable, resilient, self-sufficient and independent societies (Dushkova & Ivlieva, 2024).

The use of empowerment tools (while developing NBS, for example) can contribute to community resilience by increasing their capacity to act in the face of change. They are also linked to social-ecological resilience by contributing to co-design locally fit solutions as opposed to abstract ideas of solutions derived from outside the coastal communities.

10.4.2 Tailoring the empowerment tools to communities as essential step

Selecting suitable empowerment tools and approaches tailored to a community is not an easy

task and requires a deep understanding of local realities (needs, strengths, culture, and challenges) and perceptions of empowerment. Rather than choosing one singular Empowerment tool, a careful orchestration of different tool groups and tools is recommended, depending on the project stage. Different empowerment tools can support the stakeholder-based planning, implementation or evaluation stages. For example, governance approaches are usually needed to implement community-led Nature-based Solutions, that require establishing platforms for knowledge co-production and co-creation.

The selection of empowerment tools can be facilitated by different methodologies. Examples include decision-making/support and prioritisation methods, user-centric methods, focus groups, Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), or multiple expert consultation applied with Delphi. To support the co-designed identification of priorities (environmental, economic, social etc.) and increase empowerment. A clarification of what ‘resilience’ means to local communities and their context, participation of stakeholders and communities is key at this point.

The EmpowerUs project proposed to foster empowerment by suggesting different types of empowerment tools supporting actions and iteratively adapt them in collaboration with coastal communities, through pilot activities. Each TCL pilot was co-created and co-developed with the TCLs and aimed to empower different stakeholder groups to find and realise effective sustainable future alternatives for coastal communities in both short-term and long-term. To ensure TCLs were sufficiently equipped for the continued implementation of their activities, the relevance of the empowerment tools was assessed through a survey, including questions on their usefulness in the local context, and further information and training needs.

While a broad body of literature offers guidance on methods to engage local citizens and stakeholders, the experience of the TCLs shows that selecting and implementing Empowerment Tools in practice remains a dynamic and context-sensitive process. Empowerment is not achieved through participation alone, but through tailored strategies that build capacity, autonomy, and long-term engagement. The insights gained from EmpowerUs underscore the value of grounding these tools in local realities, co-creative processes, and shared goals – demonstrating their potential to strengthen resilience and foster transformative change in coastal communities.

11. Strategic Ocean Literacy: Ensuring European project activities meaningfully align with both their ambitions and the evolved concept of ocean literacy

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Ocean literacy has been dubbed by some to be ‘the enabling factor’ for success in all ocean issues, yet ‘enabling people’ is difficult. People are much more likely to look after something that they both care for and understand. We also know that to feel empowered to face an issue, communities need access to resources and institutions, strategies to mobilise them, and the willingness to do so (Chapter 1). EmpowerUs recognised that it had both potential to improve ocean literacy across the focal communities through the co-creation process and general engagement, but also a duty to be strategic about delivery, as ocean literacy could contribute to enabling empowerment and ultimately sustainability for some communities. However, if delivered without consideration of local limitations, contexts, resources, ethical issues or recognition of barriers to efficacy (section 11.6), ocean literacy could risk inadvertently disempowering participants.

EmpowerUs committed to delivering a minimum of two ocean literacy activities in the coastal communities of each Transitional Coastal Lab (TCL), and a minimum of twelve new ocean literacy resources across the project. Some ocean literacy activities were core to the TCL pilot actions (Chapter 4) whilst others were developed independently by the TCL hosts, wherever possible underpinned by information gathered about the transitioning needs of each community. EmpowerUs wanted its engagement to push beyond the traditional concept of ocean literacy as knowledge, ‘bolt on’ outreach and marine education, and instead asked **‘How can we improve awareness of ocean literacy amongst the transdisciplinary team, and make ocean literacy both inclusive and empowering?’** To answer this question, we developed a strategic approach to design and delivery, utilising the dimensions known to influence ocean literacy as a framework by which to ground our desired impact (based on dimensions summarised by McKinley et al., 2023).

This chapter introduces ocean literacy, then reflects on the process undertaken by EmpowerUs to ensure that activities were developed to maximise their impact on societal ocean literacy. We first present the approach to a continuous dialogue between the ocean literacy developers (TCL hosts and partners) and research team (a dedicated ocean literacy researcher and project communicators), that focused primarily on raising awareness of what ocean literacy entails, so they are empowered to deliver it, with access to resources, strategies to mobilise them and the ultimately willingness to do so. We then present selected examples of how this influenced several communities to present their activities in ways beyond the traditional concept of ocean literacy as knowledge building and awareness raising actions.

Figure 11.1 The EmpowerUs team at the launch of the, *Hekta på Træna* (Hooked on Træna), cultural trail in collaboration with the *Stolpejakten* app, at Træna Festival 2025. Credit: Træna TCL Team

Spain. Credit: Silvia Gomez Mestres

11.1 What is ocean literacy?

The ocean literacy concept was initially rooted in the idea that, in order to be ocean literate, citizens must have an understanding of seven Essential Principles of Ocean Science (NMEA, 2010, republished in 2021 and in The Ocean Literacy Framework in 2024; Santoro et al., 2017), all of which are knowledge-based. However, it is now commonly accepted that the way we absorb, interpret, and use our ocean knowledge is influenced by at least nine other dimensions, including our access and experience of the ocean and the ‘emoceans’ we connect with it (McKinley et al., 2023). ‘Emoceans’ can be defined as emotional connections with the ocean that play a part in the way people think about the ocean, and the way they behave to care for it (McKinley et al., 2023). The evolved concept of ocean literacy has become an increasingly important thread across all the challenges associated with the Ocean Decade, where ‘restoring society’s relationship with the ocean’ is acknowledged as essential for creating ‘transformative ocean science solutions for sustainable development, connecting people and our ocean’ (Glithero et al., 2024).

Traditionally, ocean literacy was considered to be marine education, which was interpreted by many as a push of knowledge, often targeting children and youth. Marine science projects may deliver their ‘outputs’ as marine education activities through workshops, one-off school visits and informational leaflets, to an often-unreceptive audience, and by storing them in unfindable repositories. These more traditional means of education, often with one-off or short-term impact, showcase the more traditional view of ocean literacy, but do not always maximise the potential longer-term impact of working with the evolved concept of ocean literacy that works with wider dimensions. Recent research into the experience of delivering marine education and ocean literacy finds that to achieve a societal understanding of what the ocean does for us, and what we can do for the ocean, we need to reach a range of specific audiences including industry, businesses and government, while also not forgetting the next generations.

To access different audiences, ocean literacy practitioners must focus on innovative ways to strategically design and deliver it to relevant end users, around dimensions known to affect the way we use our **knowledge**. These dimensions currently include awareness, attitudes, access and experience, emoceans, behaviour, communication, activism, adaptive capacity and trust and transparency (McKinley et al., 2023). For instance, **experience** of the ocean, even digital experience, can increase your

care for it; **awareness** of where there are issues, for example in your industry supply chain, will increase **advocacy** for these issues; whilst knowing how best to, and where to, **communicate** with policy makers or council managers to express concerns about the environment will inherently increase **activism** and potentially **adaptive capacity** of individuals to make a collective difference in their transitions. Using a thought process inspired by a ‘theory of behavioural change’, on how we get to our end goal, we can take lessons from environmental education, behavioural change and marketing research on how to improve the efficacy of our messaging towards our end goal, rather than thinking of the linear push of knowledge from the scientist to the student.

11.2 Empowering project partners to deliver strategic ocean literacy

To ensure that all those involved with the production of ocean literacy activities and materials had the tools and information they needed, each were invited into a (mentoring) dialogue that was specific to their place-based needs, comprising:

- a. **Access** to resources, including signposting to relevant resources and examples, finance and support from an ocean literacy researcher, science communication team and graphic designer if required;
- b. An adaptable **strategy** to mobilise their ocean literacy, constructed around both the knowledge generated in early stages of EmpowerUs about empowerment needs in each community (derived from Q-method in Chapter 7), and how this could be linked to ocean literacy dimensions;
- c. Nurture a **willingness** to deliver meaningful ocean literacy by working on the awareness of issues and potential positive solutions relevant to both their needs and ocean literacy.

11.3 Strategy: Utilising dimensions of ocean literacy as a framework to push beyond knowledge

For many academic and non-academic partners across EmpowerUs, we required a change of culture in development of ocean literacy activities and resources from one of pushing knowledge in an ‘output’ style to a way of working with ocean literacy through their pilots: strategically creating ocean literacy initiatives through consideration of its aim, the relevant audience, dimensions beyond knowledge and inclusion of local knowledge systems, through co-creation of activities and resources.

We first presented the current understanding of ocean literacy as a framework, opening the dialogue with partners that underpinned a persuasive strategy to ensure that ocean literacy activities and resources were developed in line with the wider project objectives (empowerment). This framework acted as a guide by which to discuss the development of materials through a series of questions (Box 11.1) during several iterations of calls with both ocean literacy and communications experts on the team.

Box 11.1. Pushing beyond knowledge: Questions to guide the strategic development of ocean literacy in line with project goals and dimensions of ocean literacy

- What does the project know about the ocean literacy and / or project (empowerment) needs of the community? (informed by previous co-creation of knowledge)
- Can ocean literacy materials or activities strive to meet any project (empowerment) needs identified in earlier stages, or utilise material generated elsewhere in the project?
- Can we contribute to any dimensions of ocean literacy?
- What is the aim of this activity / resource, and how can it achieve its end goal?
- Will the activity appeal to the right audience?
- Can it be co-created with, or delivered to, the relevant target audience (inclusivity)?
- Might anybody be left behind? (If so, what can we do to address it?)
- Does the activity address any of the seven Essential Principles of ocean science (knowledge)?
- Is there a better way to deliver this knowledge, focusing on other ocean literacy dimensions? For example: can it be delivered more emotively, yet objectively?
- Can we learn from other examples of ocean literacy resources or activities?

We regularly re-asked ‘can our ocean literacy present knowledge generated, or fill gaps identified, elsewhere in the project (such as those revealed in the perceptions of change and injustice in Chapter 7), in a way that was both relevant to empowerment and ocean literacy?’ Projects can often uncover or contribute to making traditional local knowledge more visible, which, when integrated into ocean literacy resources, has the potential to be more engaging and empowering as place-based learning than relying solely on externally generated scientific

facts. The type of presentation is also important, as interactive and immersive experiences (digital or in person) can increase participants’ care for a subject. Engagement can be further strengthened when knowledge and resources are co-created with communities, ensuring a mindful and context-sensitive approach (see ethics, section 11.6). These discussions formed the basis of an assessment of dimensions bespoke activities could be strategically developed around, and which were either less relevant or beyond the reach of the project.

Some examples of how the project informed the development and changes in different ocean literacy materials are presented in Box 11.2.

Box 11.2. Examples of the evolution of Ocean Literacy activities and resources developed for EmpowerUs, utilising a strategic approach to delivery.

- **Træna, Norway. The [Hekta på Træna] / ‘Hooked on Træna’ cultural trail.** A one-off treasure hunt developed into a cultural story trail of the island community’s connection to the sea, thus raising the profile of this strong identity as ‘havfolk’ (sea people) at several levels. The co-development of this cultural trail with the community through the collection of stories touched the hearts and minds of those involved. Through its co-creation, the trail revealed and overcame several stories of disempowerment and injustices.

Figure 11.2 Credit: Norway TCL team

The community decided to use some of its EmpowerUs budget to finance a series of murals of the stories to be told and displayed by a local artist. As a result of developing this as a co-created, multidisciplinary activity, the trail was adopted by a national hiking trail (or pole hunt) mobile App, facilitated by NGO ‘Stolpejakten’, as its first example of a story trail. Discussions are also underway to develop this into a European Council Cultural Route. This activity started as an ocean literacy ‘outreach’ activity, centred on developing emocean; but ended as a truly co-created and empowering aspect of the pilot, focusing on access & experience, communication, knowledge and awareness, highlighting the adaptive capacity of this coastal community.

- **Åland, Finland. The ‘Cherish our fishing waters [Vårda våra fiskevatten]’ campaign.** The Åland Fisheries Agency intended to disseminate information to Ålandic households about the local fisheries and duty of care homeowners have to their local seabeds and fish stocks.

Figure 11.3 Leaflet from the ‘Cherish our fishing waters’ campaign

Through the strategic ocean literacy dialogue, the household leaflet developed into a campaign with positive and self-gain framing dialogue targeted to their audience, a resource website (hosted by the Åland Fisheries Agency, including a fisheries management plan, a checklist for successful conservation projects, potential funders and mentors, and various knowledge tools), and a water owner seminar to support water owners with more detail.

- **Cap de Creus, Spain. The Food Sovereignty Forum.** In a targeted attempt to engage foreign residents in dialogues surrounding the Cap de Creus National Park, an initial workshop/ food display aimed to develop the common connection of people and marine space through food, both locals and foreign residents. The activity inspired a similar activity in the Norwegian and Finnish TCL. The Spanish example developed into the establishment and long-term hosting of a Food Sovereignty Forum: a legacy through which ocean literacy can continue to be strengthened through dimensions of advocacy, communication, ocean as well as traditional knowledge.

Figure 11.4 The Food Sovereignty Forum in Spain. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

11.4 Strengths of a strategic approach to ocean literacy

The strength of our strategic approach to ocean literacy across EmpowerUs is that the process in itself has shared capacity with partners to think about and deliver ocean literacy in line with their project goals in the future. Partners and readers can use the strategic dialogue outlined in Box 11.1 to embed ocean literacy in project designs, and feel empowered to consider ocean literacy as a ‘way of working’ towards impact, rather than adding it as an ‘output’ or ‘outreach’ at the end of a project. Ultimately, if more projects adopt our framework approach, it might inspire a change in culture in the way ocean literacy is delivered, which could ultimately empower the way we tackle ocean issues from individual and community to researcher and policy level.

11.5 Challenges and lessons learned

Transdisciplinary projects are increasingly grounded in principles of co-creation and bottom-up approaches. However, marine education was traditionally delivered after a scientific project, in a more top-down approach: scientists external to the community would ‘reveal’ knowledge and present it to the community. In an attempt to improve society’s relationship with the ocean, projects often commit to delivering the evolved concept of ocean literacy. However, it is rarely considered as part of the science in project design, nor is its development considered applicable for the co-creation or bottom-up approach. As such, ocean literacy still risks being considered an output in the later stages of a project. To ensure that a project adopts a ‘strategic culture’ (or way of working) for developing their ocean literacy materials and activities, leaders could ask at inception, **‘Is ocean literacy relevant to you, your knowledge holders, your audience and your project overall?’** This is a useful checkpoint for project managers to develop their bigger question with the rest of the team, ‘How can ocean literacy be embedded and introduced to align with our project goals?’ We learned through EmpowerUs that not everybody has been previously introduced to the principles or dimensions associated with ocean literacy, and some cannot see the relevance to the project, their community/participants, or to them as researchers. Others have existing practices in marine education and known, easy to access audiences, both of which may not be entirely relevant to their current project. If promising ocean literacy, we learned the value of engaging with relevant researchers, practitioners and communication specialists early on to mentor your partners and

consider the target participants for each of your potential activities. If partners are not able to identify the local relevance or potential impact ocean literacy could have through their projects early on, projects may lack ‘willingness’, one of the three pillars that could empower ocean literacy to move forward.

Whilst we strive to embrace ocean literacy as a way of working across scientific projects, a strategic approach to ocean literacy as a way of increasing impact, is very labour intensive and resource heavy.

11.6 Barriers to ocean literacy

Projects must consider the ethics of:

- exposing personal or family experiences of participants, either through the co-creation process or through wider advertising;
- presenting knowledge, or practices, that may be contested and carry cultural sensitivities;
- recognising local power relations that may present barriers to the efficacy of ocean literacy activities, and how ocean literacy interventions may widen power gaps and/or inflame any existing conflicts;
- promising change or hope where it is not feasible, particularly where working with dimensions of activism. For example, encouraging school children to write post-cards regarding their suggested solutions to local ocean issues to politicians is a pro-active example of nurturing activism, but with it could feed eco-anxiety and feelings of hopelessness, whilst sharing negative stories of ocean threats may also negatively impact mental health and must be framed carefully;
- using inclusive language, suited to the specific target audience;
- ensuring safe access and experiences to ocean spaces – negative experiences, such as being encouraged to explore local tidal areas and becoming cut off or swept into a tide, could feed feelings of blue fear and have negative consequences on individual or institutional behaviour (Morris-Webb et al., 2025).

11.7 Conclusions

Ocean literacy can be both inclusive and empowering when co-developed in a strategic and mindful way, but it can also be exclusive and dis-empowering when the local context is not considered. The evolved concept of ocean literacy, and specifically the dimensions of ocean literacy, can be utilised as a participatory, bottom-up, ‘way of working’ to improve the impact of your scientific project, rather than an output. However, to achieve this, transdisciplinary projects need to dedicate time to develop their ocean literacy strategy early on. To ensure all relevant people have clear ocean literacy ambitions that are relevant to their project ambitions, teams should work backwards from their goals, ensuring they have access to the resources they need, strategies to mobilise them and the ultimately willingness to do so. To be considered an inclusive methodology that empowers those involved, projects should consider the following essential elements early in their development:

- Who are your collaborators, contributing to the knowledge base for your project? Can you nurture increased ocean literacy through your dialogues with them? (they could be industries, scientists, decision makers, or members of the public)
- Who is your audience for different outputs of your project? (audience can be from individuals to high level, even or other scientists). Can you use the dimensions to deliver ocean literacy that is ‘beyond knowledge’ to these users, in a way that the audience can use it in the long term?
- Is it ethical to enter ocean literacy dialogues in your context?
- Consider and address the barriers to delivering effective ocean literacy through your project, including significant dedicated financing, strengthening awareness within your project, and supporting your team. Do you need a communications specialist, ocean literacy researcher, ocean literacy practitioner or environmental educator?

Spain. Credit: Silvia Gomez Mestres

12. Digital Twin ‘EmpowerCoast’ platform

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12.1 Introduction

Coastal communities face a number of challenges. Rising sea levels, marine habitat loss, marine species degradation, pollution, and extreme climate change disasters can destabilise the livelihoods and socio-economic status of local communities. Our team – through the EmpowerUs project – wanted to harness climate-technology of geospatial digital twins to address these challenges. Digital Twin (DT) technology is transforming the world – by providing a digital model of the real world, innovative technologies can be used to simulate many processes of the physical world. Our research team wanted to explore and build a geospatial DT technology ‘prototype’ to simulate real-world coastal processes. Particularly, we wanted to capture the social and environmental conditions of EmpowerUs’ Transitional Coastal Labs (TCLs). Thus, the EmpowerCoast DT was conceptualised as a geospatial digital twin platform to visualise the diverse socio-ecological conditions of EmpowerUs TCLs.

The EmpowerCoast DT aimed to provide a decision-making platform prototype that can empower coastal communities and policymakers. The platform, firstly, planned to integrate historical datasets of TCLs to gain an understanding of the local coastal challenges and to build momentum for actionable community-centred solutions. Secondly, the platform also sought to provide Internet of Things (IoT) sensor-based monitoring and surveillance tools for the coastal communities to track their local socio-ecological conditions. The actionable insights provided through the real-time DT functionalities were built to facilitate mitigation, climate interventions and implementations of sustainable solutions. Thirdly, the DT was also built to provide ‘Future’ predictive scenarios for the selected TCLs. Historical data were combined with spatial machine learning (a form of artificial intelligence) methods to predict future trends for the TCLs. Besides, the possibility of the DT to be an optimisation tool, allowing TCL leads to test and validate the impact of alternative pilot solutions, virtually, was also explored alongside the three primary objectives of the DT development.

This chapter will explore the participatory methodologies applied during the design and development of the EmpowerCoast DT with reflections on how to utilise this technology as a tool for empowerment and recommendations on how to increase the inclusiveness of DT platforms.

12.2 Applications in Various TCLs

EmpowerCoast DT’s development was rooted in the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) Living Lab co-creation framework (Etal., 2024). The aim of the EmpowerCoast DT was to empower TCLs coastal communities with data-driven, actionable insights that can enable them to take immediate (reactive) interventions, or long-term (proactive) adaptation measures. To achieve this, our team adopted active stakeholder engagement with the TCL stakeholders throughout the application development lifecycle of the project.

12.3 Scenarios for Decision-Making and Engagement

The EmpowerCoast DT provides historic, real-time and predictive, social and environmental, spatial data models within the TCLs. However, the platform can be used as a transformational tool delivering data-driven decision-making capabilities as well. Regarding co-benefits, the project recognises that the effects of a DT on social empowerment are far-reaching. For example, a DT can increase the transparency of social processes and enhance the return on investments from social initiatives – such as Climate Change, Water Management, Soil Management, Biodiversity, Public Health and Wellbeing, as those researched in the EmpowerUs project (Raji et al., 2024).

The positive impact of EmpowerCoast DT was most noticeable in enhancing the relationship between human societies and the natural environment. On EmpowerCoast, the TCLs could visualise their social enterprises, flood risk zones, green mobility pathways, and marine protected areas by layering with over ten base map choices that provide contextual geographic information such as roads, elevation, coastlines, land use, and satellite imagery. Combining thematic layers with base maps

has the potential to improve citizens' contextual understanding of complex issues like coastal scenarios, marine spatial planning, climate change, and community resilience. For instance, through the EmpowerCoast DT, it is possible for the platform users to visualise how close a cycling path is to a busy motorised road or how the Posidonia sea-grass habitats overlap with marine-protected coastal zones or identify low-lying houses in the event of flood disasters. The interactive, dynamic user functionalities of the DT platform make complex socio-ecological data simple and comprehensible – thereby providing the critical stakeholders with evidence they need to make informed and locally grounded decisions.

12.4 The Design & Development of EmpowerCoast DT followed four phases:

12.4.1 Phase 1: Pre-development

The EmpowerCoast DT had to reflect its target users' needs, aspirations, and interests; hence, the initial phase of 'pre-development' focused on gathering information about the coastal challenges from diverse local stakeholders. The development team conducted stakeholder consultations with the TCL subject experts, community members, local municipal administrations, researchers, businesses, and NGOs to ensure inclusivity and participatory engagement. The EmpowerUs workshop notes from participatory approaches workshops (see Chapter 2) were also used to identify the local coastal challenges of the individual TCLs. The information on coastal challenges was further utilised for comprehensive research and analysis, ensuring that diverse community perspectives and the TCL priorities shaped the subsequent DT Phase 2 – Design & Development phases.

12.4.2 Phase 2: User Functionalities – Design and Development

During the second phase of User Functionalities – Design and Development, systematic approaches were followed to ensure that the application design, spatial data models (or thematic layers), and platform usability fell within the scope of TCL challenges identified in Phase 1. The EmpowerUs DT platform was designed to visualise the environmental thematic layers such as Microplastic concentration, Marine Protected Areas (MPA), flood risk zones, and Solar Renewable energy. Social data layers like population, housing footprints, and social and community enterprises were also designed to be rendered on the DT. The hosted environmental and social layers in the platform

were designed to provide place-based coastal information, the socio-ecological coastal dynamics, and spatial extent of 'potential' climate impacts for the platform users. Based on the feedback received from the EmpowerUs consortium team – specifically the Træna TCL leads – a citizen-science Storymap functionality was also added to the EmpowerCoast DT. Through the Storymap component, the EmpowerCoast DT could capture diverse information – in the formats of text narratives, maps, images or videos – directly from coastal citizens. A collection of citizen stories, local or traditional knowledge and cultural heritages could potentially inform decision-making in a way that reflected local values and citizen perspectives. Altogether, the second design and development stage ensured the EmpowerCoast DT provided user functionalities that contributed to integrated decision-making and evidence-based coastal planning needs of the TCLs.

12.4.3 Phase 3: Iterative Development

The third phase of DT development followed iterative developmental strategies where the developed prototypes were showcased to the TCL stakeholders. Real-time feedback on prototype options, collective brainstorming, and the exchange of ideas strengthened trust and established a cohesive vision for co-creating and co-developing the EmpowerCoast DT. Following the continued feedback from consortium members, the DT design that best aligned with the TCL needs and aspirations was finalised for application development. The subsequent DT development cycles included collaborative stakeholder engagements, periodic feedback sessions, and multiple iterative DT development cycles.

Understanding the TCL challenges and priorities during Phase 1 helped our team contribute to the progress of TCL Sustainability Indicators, the Tailored Empowerment Program and the DT application development. For example, in Limassol, Cyprus, several coastal challenges were identified alongside the evolution of potential pilots and methods for monitoring and surveillance to track improvement. Key among them was waste management in in-land waterscapes and seawater. While we supported the evolution of pilots focused on Nature-based Solutions to improve water quality, our DT development efforts also focused on deploying IoT-based physical sensors to track and monitor water quality parameters like pH, Temperature (T), Dissolved Oxygen (O), and Oxygen-reduction potential (ORP). In doing so, the DT aspired to address wastewater management challenges by providing scientific and evidence-based

assessments. Hence, the Smart Citizen open tools for environmental monitoring, developed under Smart Citizen EU H2020 program, were deployed along the Pentakomo coast of Cyprus.

Figure 12.1 Water Quality Sensor Installation in Pentakomo, Cyprus. Credit: Maria Hadjimichael.

However, shortly after deployment, the water quality sensor components – including the battery pack – were stolen, resulting in complete loss of function or supply of IoT-triggered real-time data. The challenge highlighted a significant deployment vulnerability – especially the safeguarding measures for sensor installations in open-access coastal zones. While we evaluated the potential secure installation methods – such as casing redesigns, sub-surface mounting, and remote alert systems – it was not viable to redeploy the sensors due to limited project resources and budget. Nevertheless, the key learning for future adaptation was recognised – robust protection methods for sensors' physical components are required prior to installing equipment in open-access public areas or coastal waters. In addition to securing the installations, the team also realised the importance of actively engaging with local community members (living in the proximity of the installation site) to raise awareness of the importance of the physical components and shared responsibility for its protection.

As a part of our work with the Irish TCL, we began to understand the priorities of local communities and local social enterprises. For the local communities, we found that the emphasis was on improving household energy reliability and exploring renewable energy solutions. For the Social Enterprises, the priorities were focused on reducing energy costs and achieving energy independence. Hence, we collaborated with the Ireland TCL partners and Aran

Islands Energy Cooperative to install solar sensors and assess the site's solar irradiance potential. Aran Islands Energy Cooperative is a Galway-based local energy cooperative that focuses on reducing community dependence on fossil fuel energy and achieving energy independence.

Real-time data of the solar energy potential, thereby generated through the DT, can inform policymakers, enterprises, and communities on decision-making around green energy. Using the solar energy data, the policymakers and enterprises can potentially implement appropriate renewable energy infrastructure (solar micro-grids or centralised Installation) and optimise the photovoltaic (PV) system design. The data can also support bottom-up community engagement and co-development of localised solar energy solutions. For Træna, Norway TCL, the EmpowerCoast DT allows users to visualise the housing or building footprints, and Marine Protected Areas of the region. In Træna municipality, housing is not just about social infrastructure – it is about community livelihood and social sustainability. With a small and ageing population on one side, and a seasonal influx of tourists on the other, it was important for the community stakeholders to visualise where the houses are located, and how spatially dispersed they are across the island. On EmpowerCoast DT, community stakeholders can visualise the housing layers, identify 'accessible' locations for potential elderly housing or short-term vacation letting. The socio-ecological vulnerabilities of the houses can also be visualised on the DT. By overlaying the building footprints over satellite imagery (basemaps), planners can see how close a neighbourhood is to shoreline, cliffs, or flood-prone zones the municipality. For the Træna TCL, protecting the 'sea' was as important as empowering the coastal communities. To support this objective, the DT incorporated the deployment of IoT-based chlorophyll sensors to monitor the amount of chlorophyll in the selected Træna waters. Hence, we, along with the Træna TCL team, partnered with Gaia Salmons – a salmon farming organisation in Husøya, Træna – to deploy in-situ IoT sensors to track the chlorophyll content in real-time. The amount of chlorophyll in water is a key sign of algae and water health. The chlorophyll measurements rendered on the DT could inform users about the critical indicators of water health. If the chlorophyll levels are too high, it could indicate changing marine conditions and if the levels are too low, it could signal possible water pollution. This information can be used by fisheries stakeholders, marine conservationists, and local planners to protect both fish stock and marine health.

In Burgas, Bulgaria, the TCL's priorities were focused on sustainable mobility. The Bulgaria TCL leaders provided a map of bike lanes – green mobility areas – on EmpowerCoast. The layer was integrated into the DT with an objective to help locals and tourists find safe cycling paths in the locality.

Figure 12.2 Burgas bike lanes on the EmpowerCoast platform. Credit: Beulah Evelyn Lazarus (ATU).

For the Åland Islands, Finland, and Cap De Creus, Spain, TCLs, the priorities were to protect marine resources and marine waters. In the past, the focus of marine protection was more about protecting marine resources (fish) and more recently, the priorities were more about protecting marine waters (habitats). Fishing is a way of life on the Åland Islands, and any access to spatial data, such as fishing habitats, seasonal movement of pelagic species, or water quality indicators, will benefit local fishers to protect spawning areas and practise sustainable fishing. Hence, a map of fishing pelagic regions from EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network) was rendered to show the intensity and distribution of fishing activity in the Åland archipelago. The local fishers can use this information to quickly identify local fishing productive zones, and marine conservationists could use the same information to advocate for marine protection. In Cap de Creus, Spain, the EmpowerCoast DT provided information on the spatial distribution of Posidonia meadows – from EMODnet – that helps in identifying marine protected zones and scope for potential marine spatial planning. Marine conservationists and local coastal communities could use this information to advocate against human activities such as tourism (especially tourist boats), anchoring or fishing activities on sensitive Posidonia habitats.

The EmpowerCoast DT also enabled visualisation of flood-risk zones of Connemara, Ireland and Eastern Limassol, Cyprus. Through predictive and scenario modelling capabilities, the EmpowerCoast DT allowed community stakeholders to better prepare and adapt towards flood risk.

Apart from the TCL-specific layers, it was important for the DT to involve communities directly in social or environmental monitoring of coastal regions. Hence, an online location-based survey was integrated into the application as 'Citizen Science' functionality. The Citizen Science functionality allowed local residents to share their first-hand observations about their surroundings, challenges or social concerns directly on to the platform. Through a survey-based online form – termed Citizen Science surveys – local coastal residents could answer a few simple questions, take a photo, auto-pick or provide their geo-location, and submit it on the web. The process was designed to be simple, intuitive and accessible so that even those with non-technical background could submit their observations. All citizen science submissions were automatically rendered on the EmpowerCoast Citizen Science StoryMap section. This feature supported actioning the Leaving No One Behind principle of the EmpowerUs project. This feature allowed direct community contributions, which were 'digitally' recorded, stored and rendered as a story on the map. If widely adopted, the citizen science functionality could become a valuable mechanism for gathering local and traditional knowledge and ultimately serve as a digital repository archiving 'live' local insights about the coast.

12.5 Building Capacity and Ensuring Accessibility

In order to maximise the impact of DT it was necessary for the TCL stakeholder to adopt the EmpowerCoast DT. Hence, methodological training was provided through a combination of virtual meetings, workshops, and technical support. The online DT literacy workshops with training were provided on a range of topics but were focused on sensor management, real-time data applications, and scenario analysis of DT.

In addition, user-centred design and infrastructure were identified as key accessibility challenges during the EmpowerCoast DT development lifecycles. To overcome this barrier, the development team recommended thematic maps, simplified dashboards, and visually intuitive designs. The EmpowerCoast DT was also designed and optimised for low-bandwidth environments to overcome the barrier of infrastructure adaptations: for example, the EmpowerCoast DT use of low-bandwidth client code stack could increase adoption in remote areas where there is limited internet connectivity. These technical optimisations ensure the DT is accessible to various stakeholders across the six TCLs.

12.6 Conclusion

During its early stages, the EmpowerCoast DT platform set out to be a comprehensive tool for visualising social and environmental data – spanning historical, real-time, and predictive models – within the TCLs. Over time, the platform transformed into a powerful tool for data-driven decision-making. It allowed TCL stakeholders to easily visualise key elements like social enterprises, water quality, green mobility pathways, flood scenarios, and marine protected areas in real time through intuitive digital tools. Designed with accessibility in mind, the platform empowered non-experts to engage with complex issues such as coastal planning, climate change, and community resilience, making complex themes more understandable and actionable.

The EmpowerCoast DT platform also helped stakeholders evaluate the potential impacts of various pilot solutions suggested by the EmpowerUs research project. By providing predictive and scenario modelling capabilities, the platform enabled communities to better prepare for and adapt to pilot solutions. Ultimately, the EmpowerCoast DT application provided coastal communities and policymakers with accurate, scientifically backed information about the EmpowerUs TCLs. Through these combined efforts, the EmpowerCoast DT application has become an invaluable tool for empowering individuals, communities, and policymakers, facilitating meaningful social change and fostering a more informed, engaged society.

End Note: EmpowerCoast Digital Twin can be viewed at <https://researchproject.educationhost.co.uk/>

Norway. Credit: Ida Jørgensen

13. Inclusive methodologies for successful Nature-based Solutions: towards just sustainability transition

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13.1 What are Nature-based Solutions (NBS)?

In recent years, Nature-based Solutions (NBS) have gained significant attention in sustainability, resilience, and urban planning as a research concept and a practical approach (European Commission, 2021; Raymond et al., 2023). The term was formally introduced by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in the late 2000s as actions that protect, restore, and sustainably manage natural or modified ecosystems in ways that tackle societal challenges while benefiting both people and nature (IUCN, 2020). The European Commission broadly promoted NBS to help achieve various sustainability goals (European Commission, 2016). NBS design and implementation bring together ideas from different fields, such as ecosystem-based adaptation and mitigation, ecological restoration, and blue-green infrastructure, which are underpinned by community participation and empowerment to facilitate transformative changes, making societies and ecosystems more sustainable and resilient (Figure 13.1). The key features of NBS aims to (Albert et al., 2021; Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019; European Commission, 2016; IUCN, 2020):

- solve socio-economic and environmental problems using nature’s potential;
- benefit from natural processes and ecosystem functions;
- be adapted and well-integrated into the local context;
- offer a cost-effective alternative to traditional (‘grey’ or ‘hard’) engineering solutions;
- provide multiple co-benefits (e.g. environmental, social, and economic) simultaneously;

- strengthen social-ecological resilience against challenges such as climate change, loss of biodiversity, pollution;
- be grounded in co-creation and participatory approaches.

NBS can not only help tackle climate change and support biodiversity, but also provide many other societal co-benefits at the same time such as making places more attractive, improving health and quality of life, creating green jobs, and promoting social integration and inclusion (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019; Dushkova & Haase, 2023; European Commission, 2021; IUCN, 2020). The effort to create NBS that fit well within local community needs often happens through Living Labs or similar approaches (e.g. Transition Labs, Real-world Labs).

Figure 13.1. NBS as an umbrella concept (based on Dushkova & Haase, 2023)

Bringing together the various stakeholders such as researchers, policymakers, businesses, and local communities to co-develop, test, and refine NBS in real-life settings (Lupp et al., 2021; Sieber et al., 2024) through Living Labs help to ensure solutions are effective, sustainable, multifunctional, and inclusive (European Commission, 2016; 2021; Dushkova & Haase, 2023).

The EU is increasingly recognising the potential of NBS (European Commission, 2016, 2021, 2023), with new opportunities for strengthened investment and promoted inclusivity and justice in regard to NBS (e.g. as emerging out of the European Green Deal, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and Nature Restoration Regulation). Many projects worldwide demonstrate that NBS are effective and crucial for helping coastal communities deal with challenges like extreme weather (floods, heat, drought), coastal erosion, loss of biodiversity, pollution, rising sea levels, and overtourism (Moraes et al., 2022; O’Leary et al., 2022; Sieber et al., 2024; UNDP, 2023). The EmpowerUs project integrates an NBS approach in designing TCLs’ sustainability transition pathways where several NBS types and social innovations to support them have been co-developed, using participatory approaches. This chapter aims to introduce the NBS concept and its practical application emphasising the principles of inclusivity and Leaving No One Behind and justice as essential for their design and implementation towards the sustainability and resilience of coastal communities.

13.2 Inclusivity as a one of the main principles for NBS design and implementation

Inclusivity is one of the main principles of NBS, ensuring that everyone, including vulnerable and marginalised communities, benefits from these solutions (Gionfra et al., 2023; IUCN, 2020). When designing NBS, the principle of inclusivity should therefore be considered, meaning that people from different backgrounds and with different perspectives are involved in the process. By doing so, NBS can be tailored to the community’s specific needs and priorities. Further, justice principles need to be addressed in terms of the fairer distribution of benefits, resources and opportunities. The idea of Leaving No One Behind is a key goal of major global and European initiatives, such as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN, 2020), the European Green Deal (EC, 2023), and the EmpowerUs project. NBS follow this vision by making *inclusivity* a core part of their design, implementation, and assessment (see the stepwise approach for designing *inclusive* NBS below).

Nevertheless, some vulnerable groups – such as women, youth and elderly people, people with special needs/disabilities, migrants, and low-income households – may face difficulties in obtaining these benefits (Gionfra et al., 2023). For example, safety concerns can prevent women and girls from using certain parks, forests, or other green spaces due to the risk of gender-based violence. Also, low-income communities often have fewer or less well-maintained green spaces and limited access to them, making it harder for people with lower socioeconomic status to enjoy the benefits of NBS (EEA, 2022). Our experience shows that designing NBS to be fair and accessible for everyone is not easy, and it means moving from top-down decisions to working together with local communities – something that can make the NBS process more complicated (especially, due to conflicting views and values), but also more meaningful and effective. By combining local communities’ knowledge with scientific evidence, NBS can contribute towards more resilient and sustainable futures in the transitional processes these communities are facing. Integrating the needs of the local population and groups, including indigenous communities, through knowledge exchange and co-production is crucial for the success of NBS projects and reducing risks of possible negative impacts of these measures (Gionfra et al., 2023; Lupp et al., 2021; World Bank, 2023).

13.3 The role of inclusive NBS in just sustainability transition

A *just sustainability transition* means achieving long-term changes within the societal system, so it becomes more sustainable while also being fair (IPBES, 2019). This involves defining/adjusting principles, processes, and practices that aim to change how we think, act, and organise systems such as energy, transport, land use to better protect the environment and improve people’s quality of life (Gionfra et al., 2023). However, for sustainability transition to be just, it must also address social, economic and environmental inequalities and work towards Leaving No One Behind (Avelino et al., 2024; EEA, 2022).

When designed inclusively, NBS provide multiple benefits, such as cleaner air, improved biodiversity, better community well-being, creating green jobs, reducing social inequalities, improving human-nature relationships (European Commission, 2023; Gionfra et al., 2023). A *just transition* supported by inclusive NBS ensures fairness in the shift toward sustainability and resilience by focusing on three key areas (Albert et al., 2021; Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019; European Commission, 2021; Raymond et al., 2023):

1. **Inclusion** – actively involving various stakeholders in entire NBS process from the very beginning, so everyone’s voice is heard and valued.
2. **Justice** – working towards a fair distribution of benefits, resources and opportunities, especially with disadvantaged communities.
3. **Participatory/multilevel governance** – incorporating different governance models (top-down/governments, bottom-up/civil society or academia, public-private partnership, multi-actor/hybrid) in decision-making.

However, to make this happen, NBS must be planned and implemented carefully, based on a co-creation approach and considering power dynamics and barriers that might hinder NBS implementation (e.g. limited resources, low recognition of NBS value/low awareness of the concept, and a lack of capacity or support for local leaders to drive and sustain these initiatives). To address them, a stepwise approach for planning and implementing inclusive NBS toward just sustainability transition, accompanied by the *checklist of actions* has been proposed in the section 13.4).

13.4 How can coastal NBS contribute to sustainable futures?

Through a literature review and co-creation activities with the TCLs’ communities (e.g. identifying and analysing the main challenges, context and reasons behind, and the future sustainability visions, including the barriers and opportunities for their realisation), the relevant types of coastal NBS have been explored. They are divided into five types:

1. **NBS for effective restoration and adaptation** to support the rehabilitation of ecosystems, especially habitat-forming species that act as ‘climate rescuers’, and other coastal and terrestrial ecosystems;
2. **NBS for effective conservation** to support additional biodiversity conservation strategies (conservation and management in special protection areas);
3. **NBS for sustainable management of marine resources** include sustainable harvesting of fish and seafood by fisheries to be flexible, adaptive and managed on a whole ecosystem basis, as well as sustainable land use, participatory planning and management;

4. **Nature-based tourism** that refers to the solutions for innovative eco-tourism, revitalisation of the coast for eco-tourism and recreation to protect biodiversity, promote human well-being, and boost livelihoods;
5. **NBS for ocean literacy and awareness raising** on ecological conservation, restoration, sustainable use of the ocean and coast, and ecological education (see Chapter 11).

By ensuring that NBS are designed with inclusivity in mind, we can create strategies to address the triple planetary crises in the way that they protect both people and the environment while addressing the unique needs of various community groups. Based on literature review and expertise from NBS-related projects, we formulated a stepwise approach with *checklist of actions* for designing inclusive NBS to support *just sustainability transition*.

Step 1: Co-defining challenges and mapping stakeholders

- **Identify key/relevant stakeholders and analyse reasons for and benefits from their involvement.** Use brainstorming and snowball principle to identify all individuals or groups affected by or involved in the NBS project (e.g. government bodies, academia and research organisations, private organisations, civil society groups, incl. NGOs). After identifying relevant stakeholders, analyse them based on the following factors: interest in NBS project and its outcomes, influence on the NBS project (negative/positive), impact of the NBS project on various stakeholders (e.g. benefits/disbenefits), and attitudes/perceptions/uncertainties in regard to the NBS project.
- **Explore community context through knowledge exchange.** Listen actively and take time to discuss the current challenges and impacts, including those caused by climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution. This helps gather information for the baseline assessment and collectively decide on the best NBS to address these issues. Additionally, learning from the community about their unique connections to nature, their values, and attitudes helps tailor NBS to the local context while identifying available resources and strengths.

Step 2: Co-developing shared sustainability vision

- **Ask different community groups about their needs and priorities.** Engage with various community members to understand how current challenges, including climate change and environmental degradation affect them. This will help identify the most vulnerable groups and the specific risks/challenges they face. Ask those experiencing the greatest risks/negative impact to share which adaptation strategies have worked and which have not.

- **Consider diversity of needs, perspectives and roles.** For NBS to be effective in achieving sustainability goals, they need to reflect the diverse needs and priorities of all community members. Cultural traditions, social roles, and responsibilities can affect who can participate and benefit from these initiatives. As experience shows, involving communities in sustainable activities can be more engaging if they have hands-on learning opportunities, practical guidance and a clear understanding of co-benefits and their roles in the NBS project. When discussing NBS purpose and benefits, co-creation activities (e.g. meetings, surveys, etc.) need to be in the languages spoken by local communities, in terminology that is widely understood, and in locations that are easily accessible.

Step 3. Co-planning/co-designing NBS and related co-creation activities

- **Decide on suitable type of NBS intervention.** Considering challenges identified with communities and their sustainability vision, select the NBS type that can best address them based on scientific evidence and available resources and capacities. For selection of NBS intervention, there are various handbooks for practitioners (e.g. European Commission, 2021; Connop et al., 2020; IUCN, 2020; <https://naturvation.eu/atlas> & <https://oppla.eu/>)

- **Ensure inclusive and integrated NBS design.** Plan NBS related activities with respect to timing and location preferences. Make sure that the vulnerable and marginalised groups are actively involved – or if they are not willing or able to participate directly – ensure as far as possible that their perspectives and interests are integrated – when designing NBS, so the efforts are beneficial for everyone. Discuss the roles and responsibilities of different community groups (see Dushkova & Kuhlicke, 2024), which shape their perspectives, and ensure they have enough resources and capacities to contribute, also in the

maintenance in the long run. Consider that NBS design should integrate ecological, technical, and social dimensions to enhance climate resilience, biodiversity, and community well-being.

Step 4. Co-implementing and maintaining NBS

- **Work together with individuals and networks** on implementing NBS interventions, making sure it is sustainable, just and inclusive. Actively involving stakeholders identified earlier in the construction or realisation of the co-planned and co-designed NBS intervention. Implementation serves as a real-world testing phase, offering opportunities to refine the intervention and enhance its attractiveness and long-term viability.

- **Foster broad community involvement.** Ongoing participation, especially during the NBS implementation phase, is essential, to strengthen ownership and commitment. This, in turn, motivates sustained care and maintenance of the NBS.

- **Identify and overcome barriers.** Participation can sometimes lead to competing interests or conflicts. To address them, collaborate with local experts who can mediate and help ensure a fair distribution of NBS benefits. Consider applying social innovations and empowerment tools (see Chapter 10 and catalogue of empowerment tools – see Sieber et al., 2024), which offer practical solutions, instructions, strategies, and resources to strengthen self-efficacy, autonomy, and active participation of individuals or communities in decision-making.

Step 5. Co-monitoring and evaluating NBS impact

- **Maintain continuing monitoring and evaluation of both the NBS process and its outcomes,** focusing on sustainability impact and empowerment dimensions. Key indicators may include environmental, economic, place regeneration, human health and well-being, participatory planning, and governance aspects (see Supplementary material in Dushkova et al., 2025; European Commission, 2021; Connop et al., 2021). Consider that monitoring and evaluation starts at the earliest stages and continue throughout the entire NBS lifecycle. This ongoing process helps assessing whether the NBS is achieving its intended transformative impacts, and may be part of a continuous stakeholder empowerment process to drive change and shape a shared vision of sustainability (Dushkova et al., 2025).

- **Work towards keeping the relevant community stakeholders** engaged in all NBS stages – planning, design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Create inclusive and safe spaces where all individuals, especially those often underrepresented, can express their views and contribute meaningfully. The overarching ambition is for the NBS process to remain participatory, transparent, and perceived as legitimate.

This *checklist of actions* will help to make NBS accessible to all by fostering inclusivity through active listening, shared learning, and community-driven leadership (note that tailoring approaches to the community's reality helps make NBS more impactful).

Table 13.1 provides an overview of how the suggested checklist of actions can be applied in

real-life contexts following the given stepwise approach. It includes examples of coastal NBS proposed for TCLs and highlights aspects of inclusivity and justice in these initiatives. Across all TCLs pilot activities, including NBS, efforts were made to engage diverse stakeholders throughout the process. Particular strategies were developed to ensure that the aspects of inclusivity and justice continue to be prioritised. For example, local stakeholder workshops (Chapter 2), surveys and interviews (Chapter 5), and Q-sorts (Chapter 7) were conducted to incorporate the knowledge, perspectives, and values of a broad range of stakeholders across different sectors, age groups, genders, ethnicities, and languages. It also emphasises how these NBS contribute to both empowerment and sustainability transition.

Spain. Credit: Silvia Gomez Vazquez

TCL	Step 1: Co-defining challenges mapping stakeholders			Step 2: Co-developing shared sustainability vision		Step 3: Co-planning and co-designing NBS		Step 4: Co-Implementing NBS		Step 5: Co-monitoring and evaluating NBS impact	
	Challenges	Stakeholders involved	Pilot	Sustainability vision	Suitable NBS intervention types	Aspects of inclusivity and justice	Empowerment aspects achieved through NBS	Blue-green transition			
Trenea, Norway	Housing shortage, youth outmigration, limited job and business prospects, aging population, poor infrastructure, high building costs, financing barriers, weak social ties, frequent population shifts, extreme weather, biodiversity decline, invasive species, and tight municipal budgets	Local government, public authorities, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs	Current pilot: Hooked on Trenea (Blue-Green development arena) Future option 1: Sustainable and fair housing program. Future option 2: Blue-Green learning environments	Attractive and accessible Trenea for all: better connectivity, sustainable transportation and housing, nature-based tourism and food production, and social integration	1) Nature-based tourism to prevent human pressure and loss of biodiversity and boost livelihoods; 2) NBS for restoration of habitat-forming species; 3) community garden as NBS; 4) coastal walking paths to ensure preservation and dissemination of culture and history connecting people and nature	Due to the small community, many stakeholders hold multiple roles across sectors. Strategies focus on engaging non-Norwegian speakers, seasonal workers, young fishers, and increasing public participation in decision-making	Promoting sustainability through skill-building in green practices, better access to information, stronger municipal collaboration, and co-creation of inclusive blue-green solutions	Aiming for improved blue-green links, stronger social integration via Nature-based Solutions, and reduced reliance on seasonal economies through more green jobs			
Connemara, Ireland	Population decline, few job options, housing issues, aging communities, poor road access, isolation, underdeveloped social enterprises, low local awareness of opportunities, threats to cultural identity and Irish language, pressures from marine development, climate change impacts, tourism strain, limited public funding, and complex bureaucracy	Regional government, public authorities, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs, social enterprises	Current pilot: Social enterprise support Future option 1: Community housing program for the Connemara Gaeltacht Future option 2: Planning technical aid service for the Connemara Gaeltacht	Social Enterprise Support Program for developing skills, knowledge, and capacities for sustainable use of natural resources of the coast, nature-based and inclusive business, sustainable housing and community resilience	1) revitalisation of the coast for nature-based tourism to protect biodiversity, promote human health and strengthen livelihoods for all; 2) nature-based recreation to support biodiversity, human health and well-being; 3) inclusive NBS for social housing (community gardens, rain gardens, pocket parks, etc. for climate adaptation, social integration, place attractiveness, etc.)	Fosters diversity and engagement by connecting with fishers diversifying livelihoods, migrants, and ongoing inclusion projects, while supporting women, youth, people with disabilities, and nature-based inclusive businesses	Supporting social enterprises that protect marine resources through sustainable coastal use, by raising awareness, building skills and capacity, improving access to information and funding, fostering community collaboration, and co-developing solutions driven by social enterprise	Promoting sustainable and efficient coastal resource use through social enterprises			
Burgas, Bulgaria	Youth outmigration, limited business prospects, declining fish stocks, low education levels, weak civic engagement, fragmented green-blue infrastructure, extreme weather, heat stress, coastal erosion, overtourism, regulatory gaps, lack of clear strategies, and top-down decision-making	National government, local government, public authorities, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs	Current pilot: Burgas on Three Lakes Future option 1: ecotourism brand 'Symbiotic' Future option 2: Adaptive governance and co-management digital model for the Lakes Future option 3: Capacity building: adult ecological, climate & disaster education	Burgas on Three Lakes as a bench-mark and model for nature conservation, ecotourism, sustainable coastal development, better connectivity, climate change adaptation, and ecological education	1) Nature-based tourism through wetland restoration & preservation; 2) NBS that promote recognising wetland ecosystems value of lakes' area (wetland restoration, awareness raising, integrated ecosystem management through participatory decision-support tools); 3) blue-green network extension to connect city and lakes area, promote community engagement and integration; 4) NBS for inclusive ecological education	Promotes citizen inclusion in economic growth and its benefits (like tourism), ensures Blue Justice by fairly sharing costs and benefits, and develops creative ways to engage marginalised and hard-to-reach groups	Promoting nature conservation and sustainable resource use by raising awareness, strengthening community ties to lakes, building skills through education and citizen science, supporting sustainable economic models and NGO capacity, encouraging community engagement through events, co-developing NBS (wetland restoration, ecotourism, and ecological connectivity)	Advancing blue-green connectivity and environmental awareness, with nature-based tourism as a sustainable alternative to current development			

TCL	Step 1: Co-defining challenges mapping stakeholders			Step 2: Co-developing shared sustainability vision		Step 3: Co-planning and co-designing NBS		Step 4: Co-Implementing NBS		Step 5: Co-monitoring and evaluating NBS impact	
	Challenges	Stakeholders involved	Pilot	Sustainability vision	Suitable NBS intervention types	Aspects of inclusivity and justice	Empowerment aspects achieved through NBS	Blue-green transition			
Cap de Creus, Spain	Declining youth in fishing, coastal privatisation, poorly managed area closures, insecure migrant jobs, loss of maritime heritage, limited ecological awareness, overfishing, extreme weather, wind farm impacts, marine pollution, tourism pressure, insufficient ecosystem monitoring, low-selectivity fishing gear, and weak coastal oversight	Local government, public authorities, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs	Current pilot: NaturCap Digital Solution and Food Fair Future option 1: Sea Fair	Facilitating synergies to strengthen eco-social networking and cross-sectoral collaboration for sustainable resource management, alignment of blue economy with biodiversity & improved knowledge of eco-social practices	1) NBS for innovative eco-tourism (using NaturCap app); 2) revitalisation of the coast for recreation, eco-tourism, human well-being and boosting livelihoods; 3) NBS to protect biodiversity (restoration of habitat-forming species that act as 'climate rescuers'; rehabilitation of the coastal and terrestrial ecosystems); 4) NBS for low-impact sustainable fisheries and restoration of habitats by engaging fishing sector	The Empower Cap de Creus app promotes inclusive and responsible tourism, supporting migrants and vulnerable groups. Sea Fair fosters event inclusivity, empowering women from maritime and diverse cultural backgrounds	Supporting sustainable coastal development and consumption by raising awareness, building skills for eco-social collaboration, improving access to information through digital tools and events, strengthening community interaction, co-developing NaturCap app and Sea Fair to support eco-social networking and activism	Moving toward nature-based tourism, sustainable water and coastal resource management, and a more unified community			
Åland, Finland	Resource conflicts between fishers and tourism, limited data on fishers and supply chains, threats to local food systems, competing sea-use values, declining fish stocks and spawning, overfishing risks, land-use tensions, stakeholder disputes, bureaucratic hurdles, unclear fishing rules, complex international governance affecting traditions, and poor coordination in conservation efforts	Public authorities, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs	Current pilot: Åland fisheries appeal Future option 1: Protection of spawning sites & restoration of degraded sites Future option 2: Licensing, evaluation & monitoring of tourism & recreational fisheries Future option 3: Ålandic traditional fisheries as UNESCO heritage	Improving fisheries management, including sustaining fish populations, conservation, and securing sustainable use of resources in Åland	1) NBS for ecological restoration of habitat-forming species; 2) NBS for climate adaptation: rehabilitation of the coastal and terrestrial ecosystems; 3) NBS for biodiversity conservation in the special protection areas; 4) NBS to promote sustainable use of marine resources and sustainable fisheries; revitalisation of the coast for biodiversity, promote human health and well-being, and to boost livelihoods	A strategy to address power imbalances within the community by using tailored methods to engage underrepresented groups (like women) and diverse knowledge holders, while promoting language and cultural assets	Promoting sustainable and traditional fishing by raising awareness of sustainable practices and land-use conflicts, building local skills and knowledge in conservation and resource use, improving access to information through mapping and exchanges, fostering community interaction via events and workshops, and co-developing solutions for fisheries and site restoration	Moving toward improved fisheries management and nature conservation that uphold traditional fishing values			
Eastern Limassol, Cyprus	Industrial pressures, weak links between communities and the coast, lack of community-led eco-development, dominant stakeholder influence, impacts from waste facilities, energy infrastructure, and aquaculture, top-down planning, risk of unregulated high-rise development, and undervaluing coastal ecological and social roles	National government, regional public authorities, local government, academia and research organisations, private business organisations, NGOs	Current pilot: The Cape Dolos Strategic Community Development Plan Future option 1: Implementing solutions within the Development Plan Future option 2: Implementing solutions within the Strategic Development Plan (with area extension)	Coastal Master Plan for the Eastern Limassol Region to better connect the sea and the communities; to tackle conflicts between the blue economy, residential/tourism use and nature conservation; to adapt to climate change; to strengthen cost value	1) Revitalisation of the coastal area for nature-based tourism and recreation to protect biodiversity, promote human health and well-being, boost livelihoods (green coast); 2) ecological restoration of habitat-forming species, rehabilitation of the coastal and terrestrial ecosystems; 3) sustainable management of marine resources (incl. sustainable harvesting, and management)	Engaging a wide range of stakeholders through diverse co-creation methods and consultations – including across gender, age, and ethnicity – to reveal overlooked leaders and address power imbalances dominated by public authorities	Raising awareness of the coast's ecological, social, and economic value, building skills for sustainable coastal management, improving access to information through participatory mapping and community exchange, fostering stakeholder engagement in shaping a Coastal Master Plan, and co-developing solutions to enhance sea access and social integration	Advancing sustainable coastal management, climate resilience, and stronger links between communities and the coast			

Table 13.1. Process of NBS co-creation in TCLs considering aspects of inclusivity, justice and empowerment

13.5 Conclusions

NBS are increasingly recognised as a powerful approach to address environmental and social challenges. The key features of NBS such as the use of natural processes, multifunctionality, cost-efficiency, and adaptability to local contexts, make them essential tools for fostering more sustainable and resilient communities. One of the most important principles for the successful implementation of NBS is *inclusivity*, ensuring that everyone, especially vulnerable and marginalised communities, can benefit. Inclusivity goes beyond the NBS design, it also concerns how decisions are made and how benefits are shared. Involving diverse community groups in co-creating NBS and ensuring equitable benefit distribution promotes social equity and helps mitigate social injustices.

The concept of a *just sustainability transition* reinforces the importance of inclusivity in NBS projects. By prioritising social and environmental

justice, NBS can contribute to long-term structural transformation toward more equitable and sustainable systems while empowering local communities.

However, to truly support a fair transition, NBS need to be intentionally designed with attention to social and political factors such as power balances, stakeholder participation mechanisms, and removing potential barriers to NBS implementation and benefit access. The suggested *checklist of actions* for designing *inclusive* NBS that support *just sustainability transition* can help address these issues and ensure that NBS deliver both environmental and social benefits for diverse groups of people. Hence, integrating the principles of inclusivity and justice at every stage of NBS co-creation process (planning, design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation) is essential to achieving long-term sustainable development and building a more just and resilient future.

Bulgaria. Credit: Spas Uzunov

Part V: CONCLUSIONS

Figure V Træna TCL. Credit: Liz Morris-Webb

14. Concluding reflections: Inclusive methodologies, empowerment and equitable coastal transition

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14.1 Introduction

While megatrends such as climate change, urbanisation, migration, expectations of blue growth and geopolitical challenges greatly affect coastal communities, the aim and ambition of the EmpowerUs project has been to understand and to contribute to the empowerment of local communities, enabling them to set their own agendas for the future. A core question has been: **how** can we promote sustainability and resilience within coastal community transitions while ensuring inclusivity as well as equity?

EmpowerUs has been a large and very ambitious, interdisciplinary but social science-based research project. Combining multiple methods, both qualitative and quantitative, has allowed for exploration and testing of how different methods and methodologies may contribute to inclusivity and empowerment in coastal transitions. One ambition has been to understand barriers and enabling factors of such a transition and produce a transdisciplinary synthesis of transferable lessons for upscaling. Some of the main findings and conclusions have resulted in a Roadmap for Inclusive Coastal Transformation and this **Handbook** on inclusive methodologies.

At the heart of the project were six **Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs)** in six countries across Europe; Burgas, Bulgaria; Limassol, Cyprus; Åland, Finland; Connemara and the Aran Islands, Ireland; Træna, Norway; and Cap de Creus, Spain. Inspired by the Living Lab methodology, they have been the basis for co-creation in EmpowerUs, having meant working with communities in real-life settings to co-develop, test, pilot, evaluate, and refine for equitable coastal community transitions.

Parallel with co-creation at the local level within the TCLs, co-creation also takes place across disciplines, across involved research bodies, and we found to some extent also across authorities and governance structures. This Handbook aims to support assessing, co-monitoring and co-evaluating transformation mechanisms' success, understanding the barriers and enabling factors that can be upscaled,

leading to more sustainable, balanced and inclusive coastal development.

The conclusions presented here are emergent from the Handbook chapters and from the Reflection Interviews (**Chapter 9**) done with Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) leads throughout the project, that created a space for reflection and reflexivity on inclusion and the used methodologies. Altogether, this allows for an analysis, assessing inclusive methodologies and reflection on future directions.

Stakeholder involvement became paradigmatic within social science methods from the 1990s and onwards, recognising the need for inclusion of local actors, local involvement and embeddedness. The book 'Participation: the new tyranny?' (Cooke & Kathari, 2001) showed how participation and participatory methods may become problematic and misused, e.g. turning local stakeholders into 'hostages' for various development projects. Substantial research and literature followed as a reaction. Co-creation and the Leaving No One Behind paradigm represent a continuation of the development of theoretical and methodological approaches within the participatory field.

The work in EmpowerUs has been guided by conceptual frameworks of empowerment, of coastal communities as **Users of the Sea** and of **Leaving No One Behind** as an inclusionary principle in the Blue Economy and the EU Green Deal. Users of the Sea incorporates underlying concepts such as gender and intersectionality (see **Chapter 1**), while Leaving No One Behind directly addresses the concepts of inclusion and equity.

These frameworks encompass environmental, social, economic and intergenerational (blue) justice and are interlinked with all these concepts and dimensions.

There is a transformative promise of the UN SDGs and the EU's Green Deal to Leave No One Behind, which the EmpowerUs project is aiming to contribute to. While the concept of Leaving No One Behind is ambitious, it is not very clear in terms of how to achieve it. In practice it presents

many ethical, practical and value-based tensions, trade-offs and dilemmas (Gustavsson et al., 2025). This Handbook thus focuses on **how**, in terms of methodology, and for **whom**, in terms of inclusion and inclusive methodologies, we can contribute to local empowerment and more just processes for coastal development.

A justice approach involves recognitional, distributional and procedural dimensions (e.g., Sovacool & Dworkin, 2014). Acknowledgement, seeking to strengthen marginalised voices, and recognition in decision-making processes; access to and fair distribution of resources; and procedures that can enhance democratic governance by improving access to decision-making arenas. This correlates to the concept of empowerment understood by Avelino's (2017) framework of interplay between access to resources, the capacity to mobilise them, and the agency or willingness to act.

Local knowledge has not been mentioned specifically here but must be seen as an inherent part of stakeholder involvement and their contribution in co-creation and may thus also be seen as part of recognitional justice.

The concept of **blue justice** has many interrelated dimensions, including the fact that the ocean, to a large extent, is a commons crucial for livelihoods and food preparedness. Oceans are also of overarching importance for climate and environmental challenges, solutions and interlinked **'blue transitions'** locally and globally. A conceptualisation of Leaving No One Behind by Gustavsson et al (2025) stresses context – e.g. historical and present factors, marginalised geographies and neglected ecologies in coastal development. We interact with coastal communities that face threatened livelihoods due to a number of factors – from climate change to conservation regulations to dispossession, displacement, ocean grabbing, and more general demographic and structural changes. Below we will demonstrate how these are addressed through the methodologies applied in EmpowerUs.

14.2 Co-creation: planning, designing and doing

EmpowerUs has aimed for Transdisciplinarity – with its main approaches situated within Social Sciences and the Humanities (SSH) while collaborating with ecological/nature science and technology-oriented researchers. Transdisciplinarity, as used in EmpowerUs, has a bold ambition of integrating the perspectives of research, local communities, organisations, and individuals beyond academic

ambitions to achieve a real-world impact on society, contributing to empowerment of local communities. In contrast, the concept of Multidisciplinarity is carried out by multiple disciplines working more in parallel; while interdisciplinarity aims to integrate these different perspectives to create something larger than its parts.

Within inter- and transdisciplinary collaborations, different scientific paradigms, approaches, and understandings meet, and tensions between these may occur, EmpowerUs being no exception. The qualitative research approach of SSH, aiming at in-depth understanding, may clash with more positivist, instrumental approaches of natural sciences and technology. It is important to tease out the nuances in vocabulary that describe similar but different phenomena. One recommendation, in particular for large projects, is to allow sufficient time to agree upon joint understandings of central concepts – or appreciation of how the concepts are used by different groups – whether among researchers or various stakeholder groups.

There were also tensions between EU bureaucratic needs for predetermined methods, timelines and deliverables, and the research project's need for flexibility when dealing with real life coastal people, situations and communities. Predetermined frames may be in direct conflict with a bottom-up approach in a co-creation process (as discussed in **Chapter 3**).

The co-creation process itself has been based upon a concrete, yet flexible, step-by-step process. The various methods and approaches have had their strengths and weaknesses, which we will briefly sum up below. Before we proceed, we need to stress that co-creation might be setting unrealistic expectations for the level of engagement demanded from volunteering participants. As researchers responsible for projects, we constantly need to reflect critically upon what is considered 'real' inclusion in research, and what is desired by those volunteering their time to participate?

14.2.1 The Transition Coastal Lab (TCL)

The TCLs may be seen as an umbrella covering the wide array of different methods and approaches to develop, test and refine solutions, working towards the development of a pilot through an Action Fund in each of the six TCLs as a focal point. Each TCL brings together coastal communities, academic researchers (academic leads), and local organisations (local hosts) with knowledge of, and connections within, the community.

The collaborative structure of the TCLs builds a partnership between researchers and local organisations and ensures that research is grounded in local realities and that solutions are both practical and relevant. This involves working with communities in real-life settings to co-develop, test, pilot, evaluate and refine solutions.

The TCLs represent a large responsibility for the academic leads and local hosts. While some of them had longstanding collaboration and/or intimate knowledge of the area and the stakeholders, others were relatively new to the community, which may have both pros and cons in terms of being an insider versus an outsider. The leads have faced a wide array of expectations, frustrations and fatigue among stakeholders, but also optimism, creativity, innovation and a sense of achievement and empowerment.

The local host's role should be stressed; in anchoring the project, building trust in the community, networking, and also as an institution where the pilots and later, the Tailored Empowerment Programmes can live on after the end date of the project.

14.2.2 Workshops

The workshops were an instrumental part of the co-creation process (see **Chapter 2**) and serve as a platform for dialogue and stakeholder collaboration. Bringing new people together in the same room and creating new constellations of collaboration is a major benefit. They may enable social learning across different stakeholder groups, promoting community-owned solutions, and facilitating the sharing of experiences – creatively and collaboratively.

Figure 14.1 Group photo with stakeholders from workshop 2, Spain TCL. Credit: Beatriz Patraca

Two workshops have taken place in each of the six TCLs to engage local stakeholders and co-define the challenges and potential solutions together. In Workshop 1, community members were asked to identify and discuss the key challenges that needed

to be addressed, while in Workshop 2, participants explored possible solutions and activities to co-create the basis for the 'pilots', supported by the Action Fund.

Originally conceptualised as focusing more specifically on presenting Nature-Based Solutions to the communities and working with participatory future scenarios, the Academic Leads and Local Hosts found that these second workshops instead ought to involve local stakeholders discussing possible solutions for the pilots based on the previous workshop and the other methods and activities. This reflected better the project status at the time of the workshops, contributed to a more bottom-up process and matured the perspectives and discussions. While contributing to driving a bottom-up change was crucial in the project design, we do appreciate the inherent paradoxes, acknowledging that the project was initiated and driven from outside, partly top-down, adhering to EU regulations, to various scientific approaches and paradigms, and to pragmatic choices necessary for project implementation.

While the design of research activities was similar across the TCLs, however, with different contexts and people, 'what is inclusive in one TCL may not be in another TCL', as stated in **Chapter 2** (Section 6). Workshops may facilitate participation in ways that privilege certain actors and types of action and foreclose others and may become an arena for power asymmetry related to formal training and education, social and cultural capital, as well as practicalities, such as the time for participation. While this varied between the TCLs, some examples are immigrants needing translation, but mainly not perceiving this as relevant to them, fishers and others in the blue economy that have to follow the seasons and the fish itself, and parents, mainly women, attending to childcare. The format of the workshops may not be perceived as accessible to all types of stakeholders so, even though one tries to invite a breadth of stakeholders, not all want to or can take part.

Another aspect is partly linked to research fatigue, time constraints, but also to perception of relevance. Several stakeholders felt that since they had already been interviewed or taken part in other project activities, their presence at workshops was not necessary. Workshops may represent an arena for those used to expressing themselves, with an inherent power asymmetry or simply favouring more extroverted personalities. We ran two workshops within each of the TCLs, and it became clear that the issues highlighted within the two differed depending on those present, their agendas and their ability

to speak up. A recurring issue was the definitions of Users of the Sea, Leaving No One Behind and what true inclusion may entail in different contexts and within the different TCLs. While large efforts were put into including all – or representatives – of all groups, some TCLs found that they needed to narrow their focus for the inclusion of Users of the Sea. While women were some of the most active ones in e.g. Træna, they were quite invisible in water management in Åland, despite holding formal water rights and thus became important to target. More traumatic, in Cyprus, historical injustice, dispossession and outcomes of inter-communal conflict meant that one group with legal ownership rights were displaced and excluded from their land over 50 years ago. This displacement continues to affect generations and has implications on how these communities can engage in such participatory processes today.

One observation was that some stakeholders have adjusted to 'the new normal', resigned or given up getting heard in those cases most important to them. When finding themselves a 'minority' at the workshop, other topics were focused on instead. This is a crucial argument for method triangulation – applying several methods – for getting out the different voices and preventing marginalisation.

A 'digital bridge' was applied in the Spanish TCL which overcame some of these challenges; a WhatsApp group proved effective as a collaborative tool, making logistics easier and allowing more voices in, but also with some drawbacks in terms of uneven participation. However, it may reach groups and individuals who otherwise would not take part. The work in the TCLs revealed multiple situations in which method triangulation became a crucial part of securing inclusion.

14.2.3 The Action Fund, the creation of pilot initiatives and Tailored Empowerment Programmes (TEPs)

A novel aspect has been the Action Fund of 50,000 Euro for each TCL. It allowed for designing and implementing pilot activities within each of the six TCLs. If successful, the pilots can be scaled up and integrated into broader research programs or long-term pathways, referred to as Tailored Empowerment Programs (TEPs), ensuring a lasting impact beyond the EmpowerUs project. The overall vision of the EmpowerUs TEPs is to 'Redirect the Blue Economy to Support Thriving Coastal Communities' (see the EmpowerUs Roadmap for details). The pilots have formed one part of achieving this wider vision. There are already indications that several of the pilots are about to become more long-term structures or activities.

While the modest amount of money for the pilots set some clear limitations for activities and ambition levels within the TCLs, the money component itself was never an important part of the discussion. The pilots and the funding were seen as a tool to strengthen the work on testing and developing positive solutions and actions locally.

We encountered some of the paradoxes and dilemmas of bottom-up versus top-down mechanisms. E.g., despite being urged to set up the TCLs as 'bottom-up' initiatives by the EU call and the external reviewers, the EmpowerUs consortium was initially also criticised for setting up open-ended Action Funds that the TCLs could utilise at a later point for needs defined first through bottom-up processes (see **Chapter 3**). While the pilot funding requires some monitoring of what type of activities and costs, co-creation implies that pre-promised and pre-determined activities can present challenges, or even be detrimental, to the overarching objectives of co-creation processes.

Through this Handbook and the Roadmap of EmpowerUs, our ambition is to support the establishment of such processes that other community co-creation projects and activities can draw upon in their own work.

The specific pilot projects for each TCL are introduced in **Chapter 4**.

14.3 Methods and methodologies for scientific knowledge production

As part of the co-creation process, EmpowerUs applies a variety of inclusive methods and methodologies to support the empowerment of coastal communities in facing these transitions. Some of those (methods and methodologies) are scientific methods per se, while others are methodologies or approaches for empowerment processes and inclusion. While not mutually exclusive categories, in this section we focus directly on those methods and methodologies primarily concerned with scientific knowledge production. This does not exclude the fact that these methods and methodologies have importance for empowering communities – in this case, through knowledge production.

14.3.1 Governance Audit

Context is key to recognising the contested nature of community itself and ensuring that inclusion efforts not only reach the visible and vocal but also the often-overlooked, hard-to-reach, and marginalised groups present in every place. Investing time and resources in understanding local challenges and opportunities is essential, especially

in complex, disputed, or conflict-prone settings and communities with legacies of historical injustices.

A Governance Audit (see **Chapter 5**) was carried out in all the TCLs, reviewing how the community is governed, helping to understand policy processes and their implications. The audit includes a desk-based study of relevant plans, legislation and policies, stakeholder mapping, semi-structured in-depth interviews with key stakeholders, some TCLs also involved participant observations, and ethnographic methods. Together, this provides a foundational understanding of formal policy arenas, structures and assessment of the institutional and policy context within which various forms of power and disempowerment are enacted.

The stakeholder mapping has been valuable also in terms of the navigation of stakeholder engagement versus stakeholder fatigue. The context is important, and there will be different needs, different people and different power dynamics.

14.3.2 Realist Evaluation

Changes caused by the interventions through the EmpowerUs project were assessed through Realist Evaluation, the key question being whether the communities get better lives (see **Chapter 6**). Exemplified by the Irish coastal TCL, the approach involves establishing the context for which the Governance Audit had shown that blue growth, especially tourism and renewable energy, privilege certain forms of economic growth, but with little remaining locally, and with negative effects on traditional Irish-speaking Gaeltacht areas. The TCL and pilot aimed at developing an alternative economy, based on the social enterprise and cooperative infrastructure as an intervention. It was hypothesised that investing in social enterprise and capacity building could capture and generate wealth locally.

The mechanism – prioritised action – was to strengthen the social economy via a technical assistance programme centred on training. The evaluation showed however that rather than formal training, more bespoke and technical assistance was wanted, as well as support to finance and digital capacity. Learning (how to) was more needed than knowledge (about). Consequently, the Realist Evaluation led to a change in content but reached the same outcome: Stronger local economy.

Improving the economic viability of the area by building community ownership does contribute to keeping the Irish language alive, but this has been secondary to the work with the pilot. However, this emphasises the need to identify how mechanisms (a viable community economy) are linked to

critical outcomes in the sustainability of coastal communities, their culture and their language.

Realist evaluation may not necessarily be more effective than many other methods but has evident advantages in understanding the empowerment effects of real-time interventions when outputs/outcomes are unknown or uncertain.

14.3.3 Q-methodology

Q-methodology combines quantitative and qualitative techniques to systematically explore the perspectives of different groups on specific issues (see **Chapter 7**). The method was used in the EmpowerUs project to establish a baseline for empowerment amongst TCL participants. Challenges are especially related to developing statements that captures the essence of the situations without being too academic, and the wording ensuring sufficient linguistic and cultural nuances and clarity. Statements had to be translated to local languages, and the meanings were not necessarily comparable across contexts.

Q-methodology was probably the approach that met with the most diverted opinions among the stakeholders. While several of the participants found this method ‘too hypothetical’ in its design, and felt frustrated about having to choose between statement options that did not feel right to them, others enjoyed this method as it differed from most other activities that they had been part of, and some participants reported that it made more sense to them in the aftermath. One clear recommendation (see **Chapter 7**) is to address language nuances and to ‘Carefully translate statements to account for idioms and cultural differences, ensuring clarity and comparability across languages’.

14.3.4 Photovoice

Photovoice and ‘lighter’ versions of photovoice are flexible methodologies that allow inclusive research, and for participants to increase awareness and reflect upon their local environment and surroundings (through what may become an empowering process – see **Chapter 8**).

The method may be attractive to some participant groups, especially younger and those acquainted with mobiles, videos and social media, while recruiting other groups may be challenging. As for all methods, researchers must consider when one should not try to pursue the method further.

Participants’ contributions through photovoice are considered data collection, but the photographs and connected narratives should also be regarded as the participants’ intellectual property. Participants should therefore be given the opportunity to

choose if they wish to be credited for their photos (if appropriate).

While there are some general ethical dimensions and responsibilities attached to all methods (see below), some are particularly relevant to audio and visualising methods. Participants need to be aware of their surroundings and surrounding people when using a visual methodology, such as photography, to ensure confidentiality of both the participants and those (potentially) captured in photographs. While photovoice-participants are not restricted in what they photograph, they are encouraged to pay respect to those around them. Faces, identifiable features and so on may, for example, be blurred or black-boxed. All those who are featured without having been blurred/black-boxed should have given consent to be featured in research dissemination.

14.3.5 Reflection interviews

Reflexivity and reflection must be at the core of all scientific work. It may, in our context, be understood as the continuous process of critically reflecting on the researcher’s own role, positionality, and influence on research and practice. A novel feature of EmpowerUs was the implementation of reflection interviews (**Chapter 9**) as a structured methodology involving repeated, in-depth, interviews with the local academic researchers and sometimes also the local community hosts (or organisations) that had active roles in the six Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs).

The interviews were repeated four times throughout the project, allowing participants to reflect on the process and potential changes over time. The reflection interviews took place in connection to important project events; after each of the two local workshops, the launch of community pilots, and towards the end of the project.

These interviews aimed at promoting researcher reflexivity, critical reflection on the co-creation processes, stakeholder participation, and the power dynamics within the TCLs and throughout the project. This created a feedback mechanism that collected research data as well as supported academic and local partners by allowing them to reflect on their experiences, challenges, and the broader implications of their work, as well as to identify areas of improvement with regard to an overarching ambition to secure inclusivity.

As for all methods, the resource/time use must be considered and balanced. Simplified versions of reflection interviews can also be worth exploring.

14.4 Methods and methodologies for empowerment

As self-reflexive social scientists we know we cannot decide from a top-down position that various groups in coastal communities should and can be empowered through us – the EmpowerUs’ project. However, the toolbox of experiences, analyses, and alternative strategies – in other words methods – that we have gathered and developed can make a difference. In this section we discuss the chapters that specifically address empowerment methods and methodologies.

14.4.1 Community Empowerment Tools

The concept of a Tailored Empowerment programme (TEPs) includes a programme of activities and tools that the TCLs may take with them after the project ends. While tailoring approaches to specific contexts can enhance relevance and impact, it is important to critically examine what ‘tailored’ means in practice. It also raises questions about scalability, comparability, and potential exclusion of perspectives that do not fit into predefined frameworks. The Community Empowerment Tools (**Chapter 10**) provide a catalogue of tools that are aimed at empowerment of local communities. Importantly this resource should help communities to identify tools that can meet their specific needs. Sensitivity towards places, contexts and histories is crucial and local empowerment cannot be achieved through instrumental application of ‘tools’. Yet tools can support the work of local communities when they seek to transition in more equitable ways.

14.4.2 Ocean literacy

Ocean literacy is both a concept and a method which may foster a stronger connection to (local) marine environments, strengthen or raise the profile of marine identities and stewardship, and encourage people to make informed decisions around ocean issues. The traditional approach to ocean literacy has revolved around community activities and marine educational initiatives often targeting children and youth with time-limited impact. More recently research has shown other dimensions, including emoceans - emotional connections with the ocean – that influence society’s understanding and care for the ocean, providing opportunities to develop more empowering ocean literacy materials.

The EmpowerUs approach was a continuous dialogue between the ocean literacy developers (TCL hosts and partners) and research team (a dedicated ocean literacy researcher and project communicators).

Some key aspects of ocean literacy are to experience the ocean, which may increase peoples' care for it, awareness, advocacy and where to communicate, e.g. with policy makers or council managers to express concerns about the environment, thus inherently increasing activism and potentially, the adaptive capacity of individuals to make a collective difference in their transitions (see **Chapter 11**, and also below under 14.5.3 Ethics and risks).

The strategic approach to ocean literacy across EmpowerUs means that embedding ocean literacy in project designs, considering ocean literacy as a 'way of working' towards impact, rather than adding it as an 'output' or 'outreach' at the end of a project. If more projects adopt this framework approach, they might inspire a change in culture in the way ocean literacy is delivered, which could ultimately empower the way we tackle ocean issues from individual and community to researcher and policy level.

Chapter 11 argues for a 'strategic approach to ocean literacy' as a way of increasing impact but the authors highlight this may be labour and resource intensive. Developing the ocean literacy strategy should start early on, and it is recommended to work backwards from the set goals, ensuring access to the resources needed, strategies to mobilise them and ultimately the willingness to do so. The need to include an ocean literacy communication specialist must be considered. A number of ethical dimensions need to be considered, highlighted below under Ethics and Risks.

14.4.3 Digital twin

Digital Twin is a digital model of the real world, used to simulate processes in the physical world to be used for example, in visualising and decision-making capabilities. The initial ambition was to develop the EmpowerCoast DT (see **Chapter 12**) platform as a comprehensive tool for visualising social and environmental data – spanning historical, real-time, and predictive models – within the TCLs. TCL stakeholders may visualise key elements like social enterprises, water quality, green mobility pathways, flood scenarios, and marine protected areas in real time. The aim is to empower non-experts to engage with complex issues such as coastal planning, climate change, and community resilience, making complex themes more understandable and actionable.

The idea is also to, through predictive and scenario modelling capabilities, enable communities to better prepare for and adapt to pilot solutions. While scenarios potentially can be very fruitful, the general experience from EmpowerUs is that it has been difficult to involve stakeholders in developing scenarios.

A Citizen Science functionality allowed TCL residents to share their first-hand observations about their surroundings, challenges or social concerns directly on to the platform, and can be a fruitful way to engage groups of stakeholders familiar with the technology.

The applicability of digital twin may vary between TCLs and contexts. Especially there may be limits for its applicability where bottom-up driven tool developments are defined as central. Different TCLs requested different things which is challenging the design and coherence of the tool itself.

The EmpowerUs Digital Twin is oriented on mainly handling technical and environmental data for these coastal communities as a tool for stakeholders. Alexandridis et al (2024) points out a potential for digital twins to also handle information more directly concerning social processes in communities. This may be promising in terms of bridging digital gaps, e.g. between communities and within societal groups, however, the ethical risks of handling this type of information needs careful consideration.

14.4.4 Nature-based Solutions

Nature-based Solutions (NBS) are solutions that work with nature to address societal challenges and may entail various environmental and climate measures and include governance (see **Chapter 13**). In some TCLs such Nature-based Solutions were applied as a concrete pre-decided action, while in some this approach did not fit in, or only emerged later on in the project.

While the potential benefits can be extremely important, as an interdisciplinary project with a primary emphasis on social science methods, EmpowerUs encountered some principal and methodological tensions concerning the processes of implementing Nature-based Solutions. The pivotal issue is whether such measures could or should be predefined within a more technical, positivist framework, or instead merge as outcomes of socially driven processes encouraged through the project. However, this also reminds us about the inherent tensions between top-down and bottom-up approaches generally, and of course, both approaches are necessary also out of mere practicalities.

We found that social science-based methods, securing a wide involvement of different Users of the Sea, made a basis for dialogue, knowledge exchange, and acknowledgement of the local context, thus easing the implementation of better adapted environmental measures and governance. One example is Åland where pollution and increased

populations of the protected seal and cormorant represented major challenges for local fisheries. Here the processes and pilot initiatives have contributed to an improved environmental governance for Åland waters. A deeper and mutual understanding of the socio-environmental and human-nature dynamics developed among respective authorities and local Users of the Sea which influence formal governance as well as fishers and others' approaches to sea management.

Figure 14.2. One of the water owner seminars in Åland.
Credit: Linda Sundström

14.5 Key insights and lessons learned

14.5.1 Method and methodology triangulation

'Studying the facilitation of interactive processes among diverse stakeholders in a complex real-world situation requires methodological pluralism (Burton et al., 2009) with mixed methods and data triangulation' (Yin, 2014).

Inclusion goes beyond mere participation. It requires equitable access, active engagement, and capacity-building to empower individuals to voice concerns and address issues (Leino & Puumala, 2020; Quick & Feldman, 2011). True inclusion is not just about involving 'someone' but also recognising and integrating their perspectives, knowledge, and values while ensuring power-sharing in shaping both the process and the focus of an initiative (Sørensen et al., 2025).

All methods have their strengths and weaknesses, also in terms of their attractiveness to stakeholders. A main lesson from EmpowerUs is that method triangulation is crucial to ensure that the voices or perspectives of the various stakeholders concerned are included – in particular those who will not necessarily respond to some or any of the implemented co-creation methods or activities.

This also implies a responsibility for Academic Leads and Local Hosts to attempt to include perspectives of those not necessarily physically present at any of the activities carried out.

This also implies that measuring the success of inclusion is not a straightforward matter. Method triangulation was instrumental in aiming to reach the various groups, but still some groups could not be reached for participation in any of the EmpowerUs activities. However, we did find that the pilots allowed for benefits for and empowerment of more groups than those directly participating in the TCLs processes.

14.5.2 Processes versus outcomes

The possibility for the continuation of the project's Tailored Empowerment Programmes (TEPs), including pilot initiatives and other positive outcomes of the project, is crucial – not only for long-term impact but also for maintaining motivation and minimising the risk of research or project fatigue. Several of the EmpowerUs pilots demonstrated clear potential for continuation and even expansion, with the potential to reach and empower new groups over time.

Importantly, while it was not possible to include all relevant actors in the co-creation processes, many of the implemented pilots and actions have already begun to reach some traditionally hard-to-reach groups. These developments challenge conventional assumptions about participation, highlighting the need to distinguish between direct involvement in the process and the broader benefits that may emerge from the outcomes.

We found that the goal of Leaving No One Behind and including all Users of the Sea in the process may be unrealistic. This is partly due to asymmetric power dynamics, as well as practical barriers. Examples of this from different TCLs varied because of the different contexts; including labour migrants who were unable or unwilling to invest time, blue sector workers needing to be at sea, and in some cases, women, elderly, or young people. Limited availability, competing commitments, and the challenges of voluntary or part-time participation are crucial factors.

We therefore suggest that equity can be said to go beyond Leaving No One Behind, if understood as a physical, active participation in activities. Considering the three pillars of justice – recognitional, procedural and distributive justice – they can also be achieved for these groups through careful processes, that will need to include some top-down elements as well.

Many of the pilots introduced changes, activities and developments that could still benefit or appeal to hard-to-reach groups even if they did not actively participate in the EmpowerUs' process. In other words, inclusion should not be viewed as dependent solely on participation in the process. The outcomes themselves, by creating opportunities or opening up space, can also contribute to empowerment for some of these groups.

14.5.3 Ethics and risks

While triangulation enhances the validity of findings and broadens participation, it also raises important questions about when and how to include different voices to achieve 'effective inclusion' without overburdening those involved.

A well-known risk in co-creation and participatory projects is research and project fatigue, as well as over-saturation, which leans excessively on certain engaged stakeholders. We must be especially aware of the increased pressure on vulnerable groups.

As researchers, project coordinators, and local coastal TCL coordinators, we intervene in communities with complex social, economic, cultural, and personal dynamics – many of which we cannot fully comprehend. This carries an ethical responsibility, both in how projects are carried out and implemented, and concerning their outcomes. While our aim is empowerment, such interventions may also unsettle or disrupt local power dynamics. Although this can promote equity for previously marginalised groups, it may also destabilise existing social or socio-economic structures, potentially escalate current conflicts or creating new ones.

Leaving No One Behind is also about negotiating power in different ways. It may necessitate that someone has to give something up, and we may happen to challenge powerful and/or very difficult individuals or groups. Negotiating power takes time, and within a three-year project period, this is inevitably challenging. Co-creation efforts can help resolve certain tensions, but in some cases, it may be necessary to narrow the focus to what is realistically achievable and to avoid some of these mentioned risks.

Large-scale projects are often top-down initiated, with many of the problems being defined by an expert or intellectual 'elite'. There is thus a responsibility to consider whether the attempts of Leaving No One Behind entail a somewhat colonial – or at least patronising – approach to the needs of various groups or individuals we have categorised as 'left behind'? Do all want to go in the same direction, is a challenging question we ought to ask in these types of co-creation and development projects.

When stakeholders and others are invited in as either co-investigators or research participants, researchers are responsible for providing a safe environment for them to voice their views and opinions. This includes clarifying the voluntary aspect of participation and the option to answer anonymously. Confidential information, such as political, cultural, and philosophical opinions, must of course be handled with the utmost care.

As pointed out in **Chapter 8**, the methods should be a fair exchange between the researchers and participants, recognising the value for the community, and ensuring that the outcomes reach the community fittingly (if desired or relevant, which community-oriented research normally will have as an objective).

Research fatigue and burnout among active community members remains a significant concern in participatory, collaborative, and co-creation projects. It is thus a risk and an ethical responsibility that must be addressed. Above all, the project and its activities need to feel relevant to the local communities we ask to get involved. 'What's in it for us?' must have a positive answer and is crucial to minimising the risk of stakeholder fatigue and mitigating the other risks mentioned. As concluded in **Chapter 2** about the TCLs: inclusivity needs to be considered as existing within a context of relationships that endure beyond the project to be truly successful.

Also, the resources available to the TCLs are crucial, and no doubt there was also fatigue among local TCL leaders who were both trying to motivate participation and contribution as well as handling expectations of what may be achieved. Local hosts may be faced with considerable pressures, also those of expectations and possible failures and setbacks.

Leaving No One Behind is complex and there is a need to navigate and negotiate between different forms of 'left-behindness' when striving towards equitable coastal community transition (Gustavsson & Solnør, 2025). This suggests that our approaches and definitions of participation and co-creation should not be too rigid or restrictive. Rigid perceptions of co-creation could be setting unrealistic expectations for the level of engagement demanded from volunteering participants. Therefore, flexibility and adaptability are essential, and our focus should be on aiming for the objectives, rather than strictly adhering to predefined processes and definitions. It also implies an ethical and practical responsibility for the academic leads and local hosts to integrate the knowledge acquired through the various methods to influence the design of the pilots and other activities to reach for inclusion in the outcomes.

Chapter 11 on ocean literacy highlights some further ethical risks or dimensions, e.g. through exposing personal or family experiences of participants; through presenting knowledge, or practices, that may be contested and carry cultural sensitivities; promising change or hope where it is not feasible; and when working with dimensions of activism that could feed eco-anxiety and feelings of hopelessness. Further, using inclusive language, suited to the target audience; and very practically: ensuring safe access and experiences to ocean space as negative experiences could have negative consequences on individual or institutional behaviour. In other words, there is a considerable ethical responsibility of the research team, its researchers, local hosts and academic leads.

14.5.4 Main barriers in these processes and ways to overcome them?

Several types of barriers were identified in these processes including social and cultural resistance to the methods themselves and challenges related to social innovations, Nature-based Solutions, policy and regulatory frameworks, as well as other local contextual factors. The pilots developed include strategies that address these barriers as the work has progressed, and some will continue to evolve. They include efforts to promote ocean literacy, raise awareness and understanding, strengthen collaboration with local communities and officials, and ensure that local voices and needs are reflected in local and regional governance models. Clearly, the project has helped to highlight weaknesses in existing regulations and governance structures.

TCL leaders have experienced that individuals, single events and external decisions at the local or regional authority level can undermine processes and trust that have been developed throughout the EmpowerUs project. For example, the building and development permissions given for Cape Dolos in the Cyprus TCL during the project did not take the protests from the local communities into consideration, which may undermine the co-creation and collaborative efforts of the pilots. Distrust and an increased sense of hopelessness may result (see **Chapter 4**), and such risks cannot be fully eliminated. One reflection here is that pilots and measures aimed at capacity building, ocean literacy and related initiatives may be more resilient to such external pressures and changes. In other words, knowledge and capacity built through the process may remain with individuals and communities in spite of external events undermining the more concrete, physical measures that the particular process may have aimed at.

Inclusive methodologies require reflexivity, which is a craft or even an art form that partly comes with experience. Social scientists are generally well trained in self-reflexivity, while environmental and technological sciences may hold more positivist approaches. Continuous reflection, reframing and readjusting to learning during the process characterises much of the work in EmpowerUs. Transdisciplinary projects are demanding but important in order to integrate different knowledge, perspectives and ways of working (together).

And, as we are reminded of in Chapter 3.5; "Methodological integrity sometimes requires negotiation (with communities, with funders, and with researchers), not just innovation"!

Figure 14.3 Visit To Burgas, Mandra Lake. Credit: Anna Antonova

14.6 Future directions – final reflections

How effective or successful has EmpowerUs then been in reaching its intended goal of inclusion? First of all, we are extremely pleased and impressed by the engagement, work and the pilots developed in the six Transitional Coastal Labs (TCLs). Further, structures have been created that will enable that work to continue beyond the EmpowerUs project. Through the TCLs we have reached a variety of groups, both those that actively engaged in the co-creation processes, and others beyond that who will benefit from the pilots and tools developed, reflecting our reflections concerning 'process' and 'outcome'.

The EmpowerUs project highlights both the challenges and advantages of employing inclusive methodologies in a research and innovation setting. While inclusivity fosters rich insights, it also presents difficulties such as balancing diverse perspectives, ensuring participation, and maintaining sensitivity to the people involved.

Based on the insights from the experiences and work in the six TCLs and their achievements, we question to what degree ‘more’ inclusion was realistic. Seen across all the six TCLs, most social groups were reached through the diversity of methods and pilots, however, not all within each TCL. In terms of gender, that varied between TCLs. Some of the TCLs specifically targeted young people in their activities and others navigated ethnic challenges in their work. In terms of intersectionality, no doubt certain groups were poorly represented, and none of the TCLs reported a specific focus on, for example, sexual or religious minorities.

EmpowerUs’ ambition has been to contribute to empowerment and action from within, driving a bottom-up change. We do, however, acknowledge it is initially driven from outside, partly top-down, also in terms of choosing the methods we set out to explore together with the coastal communities through the TCLs.

Some of the methodological approaches were unfamiliar and time-demanding to several of the stakeholders. As a result, some individuals were either unable or unwilling to participate. Others may have felt excluded, not necessarily by design, but due to perceived gaps in cultural or social capital associated with certain methods, or even the project itself. These dynamics underscore the importance of recognising how method choice and framing can unintentionally shape who feels welcome or able to engage. Navigating this dilemma has therefore been an ongoing effort.

The lessons learned about inclusive and trans-disciplinary approaches can be adapted to other research and innovation projects, particularly community-driven and environmental initiatives. These methods can help ensure that solutions are both contextually relevant and widely accepted. While some of our conclusions and recommendations are tied to a large project approach, we also find that most aspects of the project’s approaches and conclusions may have relevance for all sizes of projects and actions.

EmpowerUs has been an exceptionally large project with resources for carrying out a multitude of different methods and approaches, which most other research, development, and community projects normally do not have. However, the fundamental principles and lessons from EmpowerUs can and should be transferred, seeking to Leave No One Behind, local empowerment, and aiming for method triangulation, also within

small-scale projects. Applying different methods or approaches, method triangulation proved crucial to understand and reach different community groups, uncovering their unique situations.

The continuation after the project end through the pilots is a major ambition. Seeing that structures are in place to secure the continuity of the effects of the pilots are crucial. A general recommendation is to look for mechanisms that may lead to long-term effects and/or activities, lasting beyond the project lifetime – what we in EmpowerUs have referred to as Tailored Empowerment Programmes (TEPs). We also wish to highlight the importance of continuing working with these structures and bring them forward in seeking and securing new funding opportunities.

EmpowerUs has mainly been a social science-based project, but with high aims for implementing Nature-based Solutions to face ongoing and future environmental risks, and thus also social and economic risks. An important conclusion is that social science-based methods focusing on the socio-economic and socio-cultural dimensions represented a necessary foundation for implementing e.g. Nature-based Solutions or other measures. It became clear that social science-based processes serve as a foundation to be able to understand, design and implement environmental and/or technical solutions adapted to the communities in question. This may be linked to perceptions by stakeholders of the research process and methodologies as contributing to justice, thus increasing their legitimacy.

The wider relevance of this conclusion applies to most other types of development and innovation work and projects. This implies that predetermined results are neither possible nor preferable. The findings underscore the importance of trust-building, inclusive facilitation, and strategic communication as prerequisites for uniting diverse stakeholder groups. Emphasis should be placed on relationship-building and mutual understanding, rather than on immediate consensus or decision-making.

What do the work and results from EmpowerUs mean for theories of inclusion and Leaving No One Behind as a principle? We believe sensitisation towards methodological and ethical dimensions of co-creation and participatory processes are key fundamentals and this Handbook illustrates such dimensions across its chapters.

Assuming that people are readily available and eager to participate overlooks the realities of limited time, competing commitments, and the practical constraints of voluntary or part-time involvement. This highlights how co-creation processes may set unrealistic expectations for participant engagement and underscores the need to balance inclusion with sensitivity to stakeholder fatigue.

True inclusivity can only be considered as an ongoing relation with key stakeholders and actors, taking into account their own agency and showing respect for their own interests and needs.

Moreover, inclusivity often goes beyond the (relatively) short-term concerns of a research project and instead depends on long-term goals evident in the community, which a project can only partly help influence. In that sense, inclusivity needs to be considered as existing within a context of relationships going beyond the project’s duration to be truly successful.

Treana, Credit: Norway TCL team

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Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101059957 (EmpowerUs). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participants in EmpowerUs are supported by UKRI Grant No. 10040189 (QUB).